

Fibonacci Sequence Type Selfie Numbers With Square-Root

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Abstract

By *selfie numbers*, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, **basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers**, etc. These operations are applied for single variable. In two variables, we worked with **binomial coefficients type selfie numbers with basic operations, factorial and square-root**. This paper extends authors previous work for **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers with square-root**. The work is up to 5-digits numbers.

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1 Introduction

Let's analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \tag{1}$$

Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it a represents number in its own digits. The first number similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in **reverse order**.

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(ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \quad (3)$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

(iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! \\ 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! \\ 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\ 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\ 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\ 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$408937 := -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!$$

$$715799 := -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!$$

$$720599 := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$$

1.1 Fibonacci Sequence

Below are few examples of **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers** studied by author in previous work [22]:

$235 := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5))$	$63 := 3 \times F(F(6))$
$256 := 2^5 \times F(6)$	$882 := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8)$
$4427 := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7))$	$1631 := F(13) \times (6 + 1)$
$46493 := F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3$	$54128 := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [22].

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

Selfie numbers with:

1. Basic Operations: [29];
2. Factorial: [26, 27];
3. Square-root: [14, 15];
4. Factorial and Square-root: [14, 15, 16];
5. Fibonacci sequence: [23, 24];
6. Triangular numbers: [21, 32, 33];
7. Fibonacci and Triangular numbers: [24];
8. Binomial coefficients: [22];
9. Binomial coefficients: Fibonacci: [31];
10. Binomial coefficients: Triangular: [34];
11. S-gonal numbers: [17];
12. Centered Polygonal: [17];
13. Concatenation-Type: [28];
14. Quadratic numbers: [25];
15. Cubic numbers: [29];

The aim of this work is to bring **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers by use of square-root**. The work is up to 5-digits numbers.

Remark 1.1. Due to high quantity of number there are lot of extra brackets like "(...)". These can be removed easily by making simple simplifications.

2 Selfie Numbers With Fibonacci Values and Square-Root: Digits's Order

This subsection brings **Fibonacci type selfie numbers** with basic operations. The results are in digit's order. The work is up to 5 digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and consecutive in blocks of 10. The second representations are for general values.

2.1 Two Digits

$$34 := F(\sqrt{3^4})$$

$$64 := F(6)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$89 := F(8 + \sqrt{9})$$

2.2 Three Digits

$$169 := F(1 + 6)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$374 := -3 + F(7 \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$379 := F(F(3) \times 7 + F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$466 := \sqrt{4} \times F(-F(6) + F(F(6)))$$

$$474 := (4 + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$484 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$486 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 6$$

$$597 := F(5 \times \sqrt{9}) - F(7)$$

$$648 := F(6) \times \sqrt{F(4)^8}$$

$$699 := F(F(F(6)) / \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$784 := (7 + F(8))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$966 := F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6)) - F(F(6))$$

$$984 := -\sqrt{9} + F(8 \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$985 := -F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(8) - 5)$$

$$987 := F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(F(8) - F(7) \right) \right)$$

$$988 := F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F(8 + 8)$$

$$989 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(8 \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$996 := 9 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F(6) \right)$$

2.3 Four Digits

$$1294 := F(12) \times 9 - \sqrt{4}$$

$$1296 := F(12) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + 6 \right)$$

$$1299 := F(12) \times 9 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$1369 := (1 + 36)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$1398 := -F(13) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$1599 := F \left(F(1 + 5) + 9 \right) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1728 := (-1 + F(7))^{F(\sqrt{2 \times 8})}$$

$$1729 := 1 + (F(7) - F(2))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1847 := -1 + 8 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$1849 := \left(1 + F(8) \times \sqrt{4} \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$1864 := F \left(F(-1 + 8) \right) \times \sqrt{64}$$

$$1867 := \sqrt{1 + 8} + F(6) \times F(F(7))$$

$$1869 := F(1 \times 8) \times F \left(F(6) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$1879 := -1 + 8 \times \left(F(F(7)) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$1974 := F(1 \times 9 + 7) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$2579 := -2 + F(5 + F(7)) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$2589 := \sqrt{25} + F \left(F(8) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$2594 := 2 \times 5 + F \left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$2597 := F \left((F(2) + 5) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(7)$$

$$2645 := (2 + F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2646 &:= F(2+6)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 6 \\ 2688 &:= \sqrt{2^{6+8}} \times F(8) \\ 2743 &:= -F(2) + (7 \times \sqrt{4})^3 \\ 2796 &:= F(F(2) \times F(7)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \times 6 \\ 2797 &:= F(2 + F(7)) + \sqrt{9^7} \\ 2962 &:= F(2) + \sqrt{9} \times F(F(6) \times 2) \\ 2963 &:= 2 + \sqrt{9} \times F(F(6) \times F(3)) \\ 2964 &:= (F(2) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times F(4) \\ 2977 &:= (-F(2) - \sqrt{9} + F(F(7))) \times F(7) \\ 3194 &:= F(3) \times F(19 - \sqrt{4}) \\ 3364 &:= (3 + F(F(3) + F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 3384 &:= (3 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8))) / \sqrt{4} \\ 3649 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) / \sqrt{F(4) \times \sqrt{9}} \\ 3659 &:= -F(F(3)) + 6 \times F(5 \times \sqrt{9}) \\ 3669 &:= F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) - F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 3844 &:= (-F(3) + \sqrt{8^4})^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 3944 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9}^4))) \times 4 \\ 3969 &:= (\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9}} \times F(F(6)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\ 3993 &:= (F(3) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 3 \\ 4179 &:= F(\sqrt{4} + 17) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\ 4181 &:= F(\sqrt{4} + 18 - 1) \\ 4182 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F((18 + F(2)))) \\ 4183 &:= (\sqrt{4} + F((F((1 \times 8)) - F(3)))) \\ 4184 &:= (F(4) + F((F((1 \times 8)) - \sqrt{4}))) \\ 4277 &:= ((F(\sqrt{4}) + F((2 + F(7)))) \times 7) \\ 4373 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + 3^7 \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4386 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (3^8) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\ 4394 &:= F(4+3)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \\ 4489 &:= (4 + F(4) \times F(8))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\ 4536 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (5) \right)^3 \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\ 4624 &:= \left(4 + F(6)^2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 4647 &:= \left(F \left(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) - \left(-(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\ 4766 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - ((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\ 4768 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - ((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times - (F(8))) \right) \\ 4776 &:= \left(\left(F \left((\sqrt{4} + F(7)) \right) \right) - (F(7)) \right) \times F(6) \\ 4792 &:= \left(\left(F((4 + F(7))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(2) \right) \\ 4793 &:= \left(\left(F((4 + F(7))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(3) \right) \\ 4847 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(- (F(8)) \times (\sqrt{4} - F(F(7))) \right) \right) \\ 4860 &:= \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 60 \\ 4864 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^8} \times \left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\ 4871 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (- (F(8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 1)) \right) \right) \\ 4872 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(8) \right) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)) \right) \\ 4873 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \\ 4874 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(F(8) \times \left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\ 4878 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 8 \times F(7+8) \\ 4879 &:= \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left(8 \times F \left(\left(F(7) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 4887 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - 8 \right) + (F(8) \times F(F(7))) \right) \\ 4889 &:= \left(- (4) - \left(- (F(8)) \times F \left(F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 4892 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8) \times F(F((9-2)))) \right) \right) \\ 4894 &:= F(4+8) \times F(9) - \sqrt{4} \\ 4895 &:= \left(F((F(4)+8)) \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5 \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4897 &:= 4 + \sqrt{F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})}} \times F(F(7)) \\4899 &:= F(4+8) \times F(9) + \sqrt{9} \\4925 &:= \left(\left(F \left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - 2 \right) \times 5 \\4945 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \\4956 &:= \left(\left(F \left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \times 5 \right) + (F(F(6))) \\4965 &:= \left(\left(F \left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) + 6 \right) \times 5 \\4998 &:= \sqrt{49} \times F(9) \times F(8) \\5184 &:= (51 + F(8))^{\sqrt{4}} \\5464 &:= \left(-((5+4)) - \left(F(F(F(6))) / -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\5469 &:= \left((F(F((5+F(4)))) - F(6)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\5696 &:= F(5+6) \times F(\sqrt{9})^6 \\5796 &:= \left(F \left(\left((-5) + F(7) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) / F(6) \\6498 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times - (F(4))) + (\sqrt{9^8}) \right) \\6656 &:= \sqrt{F(6)^6} \times (5 + F(6)) \\6744 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F \left(\left((7 - \sqrt{4}) \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\6746 &:= \left((-6) - F(7) \right) + F \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\6759 &:= \left(-6 \right) + F \left(\left((F(7) + 5) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\6764 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(F((F(7) + 6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\6774 &:= \left((F(6) + F((F(7) + 7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\6849 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - (8^4) \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\6924 &:= 6 \times \left(F(9)^2 - \sqrt{4} \right) \\6934 &:= 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} - \sqrt{4} \\6939 &:= 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} + \sqrt{9} \\6942 &:= 6 \times \left(F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(2) \right) \\6969 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \right) + (6 \times F(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6981 &:= \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) + F((F(8) - 1)) \right) \\6997 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\6998 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + F((F(9) - F(8))) \right) \\7448 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) \times 4) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 8 \right) \\7453 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4^5} \right) - 3 \right) \\7454 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4^5} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\7456 &:= \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + ((5 \times 6)) \right) \right) \\7459 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4^5} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\7464 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times F(4)) + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\7744 &:= (F(7) \times 7 - F(4))^{\sqrt{4}} \\7759 &:= \left(7 - \left(F((F(7) + (5))) \times -(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\7889 &:= \left(- (7) - \left(- (8) \times F \left(\left(8 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\7896 &:= \left(- ((F(7) - F(8))) \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\7917 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times F((1 + F(7))) \right) \\7919 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) - \sqrt{1 \times 9} \right) \\7943 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + F(\sqrt{4^3}) \right) \\7959 &:= \left(- (F(F(7))) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(5+F(\sqrt{9}))} \right) \right) \\7964 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) + \left(F(F(6)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\7969 &:= F(7) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + F(6 + 9) \right) \\7985 &:= \left(F \left(\left((- (7) + \sqrt{9}) + F(8) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\7990 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 0 \\7991 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 1 \\7992 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 2 \\7993 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 3\end{aligned}$$

$$7994 := \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 4$$

$$7995 := \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 5$$

$$7996 := \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 6$$

$$7997 := \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 7$$

$$7998 := \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 8$$

$$7999 := \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) + 9$$

$$8247 := F(8+2) + \sqrt{4^{F(7)}}$$

$$8294 := \left((F((F(8)-2)) - F(9)) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$8362 := F(-8 + \sqrt{3^6}) \times 2$$

$$8364 := \left(F(F(8)) - \left(F((3 \times 6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$8464 := (84 + F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$8749 := \left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{F(4) \times \sqrt{9}}} \right) \right)$$

$$8898 := \left(F(F(8)) - \left(8 \times \left(F(\sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$8989 := F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} - 8 \times F(9)$$

$$9259 := \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(F(F((F(2) + (5))))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9261 := \left(F((9 - F(2)))^{\sqrt{F(6)+1}} \right)$$

$$9263 := F(\sqrt{9}) + F(2+6)^3$$

$$9264 := \sqrt{9} + F(2+6)^{F(4)}$$

$$9269 := \left((9 - F(2)) + \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$9348 := - \left(\left(\left(F((F(9)/F(3))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$9349 := \left(- \left(F((F(9)/F(3))) \right) + F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$9375 := \sqrt{9} \times (-F(3) + 7)^5$$

$$9479 := 9^{F(4)} \times F(7) + F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$9576 := \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times ((-5) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)) \right)$$

$$9648 := - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (6^4) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$9726 := \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((F(7) + 2)) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$9782 := \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times ((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) - 2) \right)$$

$$9783 := \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times F(8) \right) - 3 \right)$$

$$9784 := \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times F(8) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$9786 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(F(7)) \right) \times (8 + 6) \right)$$

$$9788 := \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(F(7)) \times -((F(8) + F(8)))) \right)$$

$$9789 := F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)} + F(8 + 9)$$

$$9946 := - \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{F(4)} \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right)$$

$$9968 := \left(\left(9 - F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right)$$

2.4 Five Digits

$$10199 := 101^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$10394 := -10 + (3 \times F(9))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$10443 := (F(10) + 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 3$$

$$10446 := \left(- \left(\left(\left(10^{F(4)} \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$10649 := \left(1 + \left(\left(F(F(06)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$$

$$10769 := \left(((F(10) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$10796 := \left(\left(10 \times \left(- (F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$10864 := \left(\left(- ((10 \times 8)) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$10866 := \left(\left(- (10) \times \sqrt{8 \times F(6)} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$10869 := \left(\left(- ((10 \times 8)) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$10879 := \left(((- (F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (F(7))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$10888 := \left(\left(- (F(10)) + F(F(8)) \right) - F(\sqrt{8 + 8}) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10889 &:= \left((-F(10)) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{8/F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 10890 &:= \left((-F(10)) + F(F(8)) - F(F(\sqrt{9+0})) \right) \\
 10891 &:= \left((-F(10)) + F(F(8)) \times F(\sqrt{9}-1) \right) \\
 10892 &:= \left((-F(10)) + F(F(8)) + (\sqrt{9}-2) \right) \\
 10896 &:= \left((-F(10)) + F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{9}-F(6)) \right) \\
 10897 &:= \left((-10) + F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{9} \times F(7)) \right) \\
 10898 &:= \left(-\left(F(10) - (F(8)/\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 10899 &:= \left((-F(10)) + F(F(8)) + F(9-\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 10916 &:= \left((-10 \times \sqrt{9}) + F(F(F(1 \times 6))) \right) \\
 10926 &:= \left((-10 \times F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(2+6)) \right) \\
 10933 &:= \left((-10 - \sqrt{9}) + F(F(F(3+3))) \right) \\
 10935 &:= \left((-10 - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) + (F(F(3+5))) \right) \\
 10938 &:= F((10 - \sqrt{9}) \times 3) - 8 \\
 10942 &:= \left(F((F(10) - F(9))) - \sqrt{4^2} \right) \\
 10943 &:= \left(F((F(10) - F(9))) - F(\sqrt{4} + F(3)) \right) \\
 10944 &:= \left(F((F(10) - F(9))) - (4 - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 10948 &:= \left(F((F(10) - F(9))) + \sqrt{-4+8} \right) \\
 10949 &:= \left(F((F(10) - F(9))) + \sqrt{F(4) \times \sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 10953 &:= \left((10 - \sqrt{9}) + F(F(5+3)) \right) \\
 10957 &:= \left((10 + F(F(\sqrt{9}))) + F(F((-5) + F(7))) \right) \\
 10958 &:= \left((10 + \sqrt{9-5}) + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 10959 &:= \left((10 + \sqrt{9}) + F(F(5 + \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 10963 &:= \left((10 \times F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(6))) - 3 \right) \\
 10968 &:= \left((10 \times \sqrt{9}) - F(6) + F(F(8)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$10969 := \left((F((F(10) - F(9))) + F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$10976 := \left((10 \times \sqrt{9}) + F((F(7) + F(6))) \right)$$

$$10979 := -1 + F(09) + F(7 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$10996 := \left(\left(10 \times \sqrt{F(9) - 9} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$10998 := \left((F((1 + 09)) - \sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)) \right)$$

$$10999 := \left((F(10) - F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(F((9 - \sqrt{9})))) \right)$$

$$11046 := \left(\sqrt{(1 \times 10)^4} + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$11466 := \left(\left(- \left((F(11) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \times - (6) \right)$$

$$11468 := \left(\left((F(11) - \sqrt{4}) \times 6 \right) + F(F(8)) \right)$$

$$11589 := -1 + F(15) \times (F(8) - F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$11659 := F(11) \times (6 + 5^{\sqrt{9}})$$

$$11878 := \left(\left(\sqrt{(1+1) \times 8} \times F(F(7)) \right) + F(F(8)) \right)$$

$$11979 := 11^{F(\sqrt{9+7})} \times 9$$

$$12544 := (1 + F(2 \times 5))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 4$$

$$12579 := \left(((- (1) + F((2 \times 5))) \times F(F(7))) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$12749 := -1 + (F(2 \times 7) - \sqrt{4}) \times F(9)$$

$$12759 := \left(- (1) - \left((F(2) - F(F(7))) \times F((5 \times F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \right)$$

$$12769 := (1 + 2 \times 7 \times F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$12784 := \left((- (1) + F((2 \times 7))) \times F((8 + F(\sqrt{4}))) \right)$$

$$12789 := (-1 + F(2 + F(7))) \times \sqrt{F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})}}$$

$$12925 := (1 + F(2 \times 9)) \times \sqrt{25}$$

$$12979 := \left(- (1) + \left(F((F(2) + 9)) \times (F(F(7)) + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$$

$$12987 := \left(\left(12 + F((F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8)) \right) \times F(7) \right)$$

$$12994 := (F(12) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(9 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$13297 := \left((F((- (1) + F(F((3 \times 2)))))) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(7))$$

$$13488 := (F((1 \times 3)) \times (F(-((F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8)))))) - (F(8)))$$

$$13489 := (F(13 \times \sqrt{4}) + 8) / 9$$

$$13892 := (1 + 3 \times (F(8)^{\sqrt{9}})) / 2$$

$$13924 := (13 \times 9 + F(2))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$14284 := ((- (F(14)) - F(-((F(2) - F(8)))))) \times -(\sqrt{4})$$

$$14329 := ((1 + F((\sqrt{4} + F(F((3 \times 2)))))) / F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$14447 := (1 - ((\sqrt{4} - (4^{F(4)})) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$14469 := ((- (F(14)) - (- (4) \times F(F(F(6)))))) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$14589 := (1 + (4 \times ((- (5) + F(F(8))) / \sqrt{9})))$$

$$14637 := (((1 + F((- (\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)))))) / F(3)) \times 7$$

$$14739 := (1 \times 4 + F(7))^3 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$14783 := (- (1) + ((\sqrt{4} - F(F(7))) \times - ((8^{F(3)}))))$$

$$14784 := ((\sqrt{1 \times 4} - F(F(7))) \times - (\sqrt{8^4}))$$

$$14884 := (-1 + F(4 + 8) - F(8))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$14913 := 1 + 4^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(13)$$

$$14989 := -1 - 4 + F(9) \times F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$15129 := (- ((F(F((1 + 5))) - (F(12))))^{F(\sqrt{9})})$$

$$15379 := (-1 + 5 + 3) \times F(7)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$15435 := ((F(F((1 + 5)))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 35)$$

$$15492 := (1 + 5) \times (-\sqrt{4} + F(9 \times 2))$$

$$15496 := (1 + 5) \times F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) - F(6)$$

$$15497 := (1 + 5) \times F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) - 7$$

$$15498 := ((1 + 5) \times (- (F(\sqrt{4})) + F(- ((\sqrt{9} - F(8))))))$$

$$15646 := 1 \times 5^6 + F(\sqrt{4} + 6)$$

$$15679 := -1 + 5 \times (F(6) \times 7)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$15689 := 1 + 5^6 + F(8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15694 &:= 1 + 5^6 + F(9) \times \sqrt{4} \\15748 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{-1+5} \times (7^4) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \\15774 &:= \left(\left(-((1-5))^7 \right) - F\left(\left(F(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\15795 &:= (1 \times 5 \times F(7)) \times \sqrt{9^5} \\15842 &:= \left(\sqrt{-1+5} \times \left(F((8+F(4))^2) \right) \right) \\15859 &:= -1 + (5 + F(8)) \times F(5 \times \sqrt{9}) \\15969 &:= \left(- (1) - \left(\left(- (5) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F((F(6) + 9)) \right) \right) \\16374 &:= (1 - 6 + F(3)^{F(7)}) \times \sqrt{4} \\16379 &:= 1 - 6 + F(3)^{F(7)} \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\16382 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{16^{-F(F(3))+8}} \right) - 2 \right) \\16386 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} + F(3)^{8+6} \\16387 &:= F(\sqrt{16}) + F(3)^{F(8)-7} \\16397 &:= \sqrt{16^{-F(3)+9}} + F(7) \\16398 &:= \left(\left(\left((- (1) \times F(F(F(6)))) \times 3 \right) / - \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - (F(8)) \right) \\16413 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \times - (3) \right) \\16419 &:= \left(\left((- (1) \times F(F(F(6)))) \times - (F(4)) \right) / \left(- (1) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\16468 &:= \sqrt{16} \times (4^6 + F(8)) \\16483 &:= \left(1 - \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) - (F(8)) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \\16546 &:= \left((F(F((1+6))) \times - (5)) + F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\16574 &:= \left(\left(\left((1+6)^5 \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\16589 &:= -F(16) + (5 + F(8))^{\sqrt{9}} \\16617 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{16^{6+1}} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\16644 &:= \left(\left((1 - F(F(6))) + F\left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\16724 &:= \left(\sqrt{16} \times F((F(7) + (2 + 4))) \right) \\16728 &:= \left((1 + F((6 + F(7)))) \times \sqrt{2 \times 8} \right)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 16772 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{16} \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \times 72 \right) \right) \\
 16779 &:= \left(\sqrt{16} + F \left(7 \right) \right) \times F \left(7 + 9 \right) \\
 16798 &:= -1 - F \left(6 \right) + 7^{-\sqrt{9}+8} \\
 16799 &:= -1 \times F \left(6 \right) + 7\sqrt{F(9)-9} \\
 16829 &:= \left(F \left(\left(1 + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(F \left(8 \right)^2 \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 16929 &:= \left(1 + F \left(6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times \left(-F \left(2 \right) + F \left(9 \right) \right) \\
 16978 &:= \left(\left(16 \times F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 16982 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(1 + F \left(6 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + F \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 16996 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(1 + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(9 \right) \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 16998 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(1 + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(9 \right) \times F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 17199 &:= \left(F \left(\left(1 + F \left(\left(7 + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^9 \right) \right) \\
 17246 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \times - \left(2 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17369 &:= \left(\left(1 - \left(7^3 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17422 &:= -\sqrt{17^4} + F \left(22 \right) \\
 17469 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 17474 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 + 74 \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 17478 &:= \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right) + 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 17479 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(1 \right) - F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) + 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 17496 &:= \left(-1 + F \left(7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 9^6} \\
 17497 &:= 1 + \left(7 + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9^7} \\
 17569 &:= F \left(17 \right) \times \left(5 + 6 \right) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 17576 &:= \sqrt{\left(F \left(1 \times 7 \right) \right)^{5 \times F \left(7 \right)} \times F \left(6 \right)} \\
 17589 &:= F \left(1 \times 7 \right) + \left(5 + F \left(8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 17679 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(1 + 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) / F \left(7 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 17684 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\left(1 + 7 \right) \right) + \left(6 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17689 &:= ((1 + F(7)) \times F(6) + F(8))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 17690 &:= \left(- (F((1 + 7))) + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9+0}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17691 &:= \left(\left(- (F((1 + 7))) + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 17692 &:= \left(\left(- (17) + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 17694 &:= \left(- (17) + F \left(\left(F(6) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 17695 &:= \left(\left(- (F((1 + 7))) + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) + (5) \right) \\
 17699 &:= \left(F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (9 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 17709 &:= \left(F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) - F(\sqrt{09}) \right) \\
 17724 &:= \left(F((1 \times 7)) + F \left(\left((F(7) - 2) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 17745 &:= F(1 + 7) \times F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\
 17784 &:= \left((- (1) - F(F(7))) \times (- (78) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 17789 &:= \left((1 + 77) + F \left(\left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17889 &:= \left(178 + F \left(\left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17944 &:= \left(F(F((1 \times 7))) + F \left(\left((9 + \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 17945 &:= \left((1 + F(F(7))) + F \left(\left((F(9) / \sqrt{4}) + (5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17946 &:= \left(\left((- (1) + F(F(7))) + \sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17948 &:= \left((- (1) - (- (7) \times F(9))) + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17954 &:= - \left(\left(F(F((1 + 7))) - \left((F(9) \times 5)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 18179 &:= \left(F((1 + F(8))) + \left((1 + F(F(7))) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 18289 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(-((1 - 8)))) - \left(2 \times (F(8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 18336 &:= \left(F((1 + F(8))) + \sqrt{(F(3) + 3)^{F(6)}} \right) \\
 18480 &:= \left(\left(F(F(-((1 - 8)))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 80 \right) \\
 18493 &:= -\sqrt{1+8} + (4 \times F(9))^{F(3)} \\
 18494 &:= (F(1 + 8) \times 4)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - \sqrt{4} \\
 18499 &:= (F(1 + 8) \times 4)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + \sqrt{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18524 &:= (1 + F(8)^{5-2}) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 18694 &:= \left((F((1 + F(8))) + F(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}))) - 4 \right) \\
 18698 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + F((6/\sqrt{9}) \times 8)) \\
 18699 &:= (1 + ((F(F(8)) - F((F(6) + 9))) \times F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 18779 &:= (((-1) - F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F((F(7) - F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 18799 &:= ((-1) + F(F(8))) - ((F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times -(F(9))) \\
 18872 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(1+8)^8} \times F(F(7))} \right) - F(2) \right) \\
 18873 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(1+8)^8} \times F(F(7))} \right) \times F(F(3)) \right) \\
 18874 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(1+8)^8} \times F(F(7))} \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 18899 &:= -1 + F(8) \times (F(8) + 9)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 18946 &:= \left(((-1) + F(8))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(F(\sqrt{4} + (6))) \right) \\
 18948 &:= \left(((-1) + F(8))^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 18968 &:= F(18) + F(\sqrt{9})^{6+8} \\
 18969 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(1+8)^9} \right) + (F(F(6)) \times -(F(9))) \right) \\
 18984 &:= \left((F(F(-(1-8))) - (\sqrt{9^8})) \times -(F(4)) \right) \\
 19046 &:= \left((1 \times 90)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 19138 &:= \left(((-1) + \sqrt{9})^1 3 + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 19396 &:= \left(- \left((F(-(1-9))^3 \right) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6))) \right) \\
 19456 &:= 19 \times 4^{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}} \\
 19539 &:= - \left((F((-1) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) + (5)))) - ((3^9)) \right) \\
 19664 &:= -1 + \left(\sqrt{9^{F(6)}} - 6 \right) \times F(4) \\
 19679 &:= \left((-1) - \sqrt{9} + (F(F(6)) / 7)^9 \right) \\
 19682 &:= -1 + \sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \times F(8/2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19684 &:= 1 + \sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \times F(8 - 4) \\
 19686 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(\sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{8 + F(6)} \right) \right) \\
 19693 &:= 1 + \left(\sqrt{9^{F(6)}} + \sqrt{9} \right) \times 3 \\
 19772 &:= -1 + 9 \times F(7)^{\sqrt{7+2}} \\
 19792 &:= 1 + 9 \times \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} + 2 \right) \\
 19796 &:= \left((1 - (9 \times F(F(7)))) - \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 19799 &:= -1 + 9 \times F(7) + \sqrt{9^9} \\
 19845 &:= \left(\sqrt{1 \times 9} \times F(8) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\
 19873 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right) \right) / 7 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 19897 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + F \left(\left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(8) \right) \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^7} \right) \right) \\
 19916 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{1 \times 9^9} \right) + F(F((1 + 6))) \right) \\
 19917 &:= \left(\left(1 + \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) + F(F((1 \times 7))) \right) \\
 19938 &:= -1 + \sqrt{9^9} + F(3)^8 \\
 19976 &:= \left(\left(- (1) + F \left(\left(9 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(F(F(7)) - (6) \right) \right) \\
 20229 &:= (F(20) - 22) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 20283 &:= \left(F(20) - \sqrt{2 \times 8} \right) \times 3 \\
 20289 &:= \left(F(20) - \sqrt{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 20291 &:= (F(20) - F(2)) \times \sqrt{9} - 1 \\
 20292 &:= (F(20) - F(2)) \times \sqrt{9} \times F(2) \\
 20293 &:= F(20) \times F(2) \times \sqrt{9} - F(3) \\
 20294 &:= (F(20) - F(2)) \times \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{4} \\
 20298 &:= (F(20) + F(2)) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \\
 20299 &:= (F(20) + 2) \times \sqrt{9} - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 20329 &:= F(20) \times \sqrt{3^2} + F(9) \\
 20449 &:= \left(\left(- (F(2)) + F \left((F(04) \times 4) \right) \right) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 20499 &:= \left(F(20) + \sqrt{4} \times F(9) \right) \times \sqrt{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20736 &:= (-F(2) + F(07))\sqrt{F(3) \times F(6)} \\ 20868 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(0 - \sqrt{8^6}\right) + F(F(8))\right)\right) \\ 20895 &:= \left(\left(F((-2) + F(08))\right) - F(\sqrt{9})\right) \times 5 \\ 20905 &:= \left(F\left(\left(20 - F\left(F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)\right)\right) \times 05 \\ 20994 &:= \left(\left(-F(20) - F\left(F\left(\left(9 - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \times -F(4) \\ 21464 &:= \left(\left(-214 + F(F(F(6)))\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 21647 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(21) - (6)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - F(F(7))\right) \\ 21659 &:= \left(\left(2 \times F(F(F((1 \times 6))))\right) - F\left(F\left(\left(5 + F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)\right)\right) \\ 21698 &:= F(21) + F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(8) \\ 21744 &:= (F(21) - 74) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 21794 &:= \left(F(21) - 7^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 21824 &:= \left(\left(F(21) - F((8 + F(2)))\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 21836 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(-1 + F(F(8))\right) - \sqrt{3^6}\right)\right) \\ 21844 &:= (F(21) - F(8) - F(4)) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 21845 &:= (F(21) - F(8)) \times \sqrt{4} - 5 \\ 21848 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(1 + F(F(8))\right) - \left(\sqrt{4} + F(8)\right)\right)\right) \\ 21849 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(21) - F(8)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - F\left(F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \\ 21864 &:= (F(21) - 8 - 6) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 21869 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))\right) - F(F(6))\right) - F(\sqrt{9})\right) \\ 21874 &:= \left(\left(\left(-2 + F(F((1 \times 8)))\right) - (7)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\ 21877 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \left(-1 + F(F(8))\right)\right) - F(\sqrt{7 \times 7})\right) \\ 21879 &:= \left(F(2) + \left(\left(F(F((1 \times 8))) - (7)\right) \times F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \\ 21884 &:= \left(F(21) - \sqrt{8+8}\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 21886 &:= F(21) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8} - 6} \\ 21889 &:= F(21) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{8+8} - \sqrt{9}} \\ 21891 &:= 2 \times F\left(\left(-1 + 8\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21893 &:= F(2) + F\left((-1 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(3) \\
 21894 &:= (F(21) - 8 + 9) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 21897 &:= \left(\left((-F(2)) + F(F((1 \times 8)))\right) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + (7)\right) \\
 21898 &:= \left(\left((2 + F(F((1 \times 8)))) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - F(F(8))\right) \\
 21899 &:= (F(21) + 8) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - 9 \\
 21934 &:= \left((F(21) + F(F((9 - 3)))) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 21946 &:= \left(2 \times \left(F(F(-((1 - 9)))) + \sqrt{F(4)^6}\right)\right) \\
 21947 &:= (F(21) + F(9)) \times \sqrt{4} - F(7) \\
 21956 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left((-1) + \sqrt{9}\right)^5 + F(F(F(6)))\right)\right) \\
 21957 &:= F(21) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + 5 \times F(7) \\
 21958 &:= \left(2 \times \left(1 + \left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^5 + F(F(8))\right)\right)\right) \\
 21964 &:= \left(\left((2 + F((1 \times 9))) + F(F(F(6)))\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 21974 &:= (F(21) + F(9) + 7) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 21994 &:= F(21) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(9) \times F(4) \\
 21996 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(F((1 + 9)) - \sqrt{9}\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right)\right) \\
 22148 &:= 2 \times F(21) + \sqrt{4^8} \\
 22468 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(2 \times F\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6\right)\right) + F(F(8))\right)\right) \\
 22599 &:= \left(-F(2) + 2^5\right) \times 9^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 22647 &:= \left(F(2) - \left(-2\right) \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 23197 &:= F(23 + 1) / F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(7) \\
 23488 &:= \left(-F(2) - \left(-3\right) \times F\left(-\left(\sqrt{4} - F(8)\right)\right)\right) - F(F(8)) \\
 23489 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(2^3\right)\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) + (F((8 + 9))) \\
 23674 &:= \left(\left(-F(2) + F\left(-\left(F(F(3)) - F(F(6))\right)\right)\right) \times 7\right) / \sqrt{4} \\
 23689 &:= \left(F(2) - \left(F\left(F(3) \times F(6)\right) \times \left(-8\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 23696 &:= \left(F(2) + \left(F\left(F(3) \times F(6)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times F(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$23864 := \left(- (2) \times \left((F(F(3)) - F(F(8))) - F \left((F(6) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$23869 := \left((2 \times (F((F(3) \times 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) + \sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$23945 := \left(\left(2 - (3 \times F \left((F(9) / \sqrt{4}) \right)) \right) \times - (5) \right)$$

$$23997 := \left(- (2) + \left((F(F(3)) + \left((F(9) \times \sqrt{9}) \right)) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right)$$

$$23999 := \left((F(2) - (- (3) \times F(9))) \times F \left(F \left((9 - F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$24334 := (F(2 \times 4) + F(3))^3 \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$24467 := \left(2 - \left(- \left((\sqrt{4} + F(4)) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$24468 := \left(F(24) + \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(F(F(6))) \right) - 8 \right) \right)$$

$$24484 := \left(\left((2 + 4)^4 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$24573 := -F(2) + F \left(\sqrt{4 + 5} \right)^{F(7)} \times 3$$

$$24574 := -2 + F \left(\sqrt{4 + 5} \right)^{F(7)} \times F(4)$$

$$24579 := \left(F(2) + F \left(\sqrt{4 + 5} \right)^{F(7)} \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$24625 := \left(- (2) + F \left((\sqrt{4} \times F(6)) \right) \right) \times 25$$

$$24647 := \left(F(2) - \left(- (F(4)) \times F(F(F(6))) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) \right)$$

$$24674 := \left(2 + F \left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \right) \times F(7)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$24694 := \left(- (2) - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / - (F(4)) \right) \right)$$

$$24696 := \left(2 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) / 6 \right) \right)$$

$$24746 := \left(2 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) + F \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$24843 := \left(\left((2 + F((F(4) + 8)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$24964 := (-2 + 4 \times (F(9) + 6))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$24966 := \left(\left(2 - \left(\sqrt{4} \left((F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) / - (F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$24989 := -F(2) + \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(9) \right) \times F(8) \times F(9)$$

$$25595 := \left(2^5 \times 5 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 5$$

$$25599 := \left(\left(\left((2^5) \times 5 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25664 &:= \left(2 + \left((5 + F(F(6))) \times F\left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 25746 &:= \left(\left(F(2) + \left(5 \times 7\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \times F(F(6))\right) \\
 25839 &:= \left(-F(2) - \left(-5 \times F\left(F(8) - 3\right)\right) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 25998 &:= 2 \times \left(F\left(5 \times \sqrt{9}\right) + 9\right) \times F(8) \\
 26047 &:= \left(F(2) + 60\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 7 \\
 26449 &:= \left(F\left(-F(2) + F(F(6))\right)\right) + \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + \left(F(4)^9\right)\right)\right) \\
 26450 &:= \left(\left(2 + F(F(6))\right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 50\right) \\
 26460 &:= F(2 + 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 60 \\
 26569 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(2 + 6)\right)\right) + \left(5^6\right)\right) - F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \\
 26586 &:= 2 \times F(F(6)) \times \left(\sqrt{5^8} + F(6)\right) \\
 26645 &:= \left(\left(-F\left(2 \times 6\right)\right) - \left(F\left(F(F(6))\right) / -\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \times 5 \\
 26648 &:= \left(-F(2) - \left(-6 - F(F(6))\right) \times F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 8\right)\right)\right) \\
 26649 &:= \left(F\left(2 \times F(6)\right)\right) \times \left(\left(6 / \sqrt{4}\right) \times 9\right) \\
 26694 &:= \left(2 \times \left(F\left(F(F(6))\right) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) / \sqrt{9}\right)^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 26767 &:= \left(F(2) + 6 \times \sqrt{7^6}\right) \times F(7) \\
 26784 &:= \left(-F(2) + \left(F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))\right)\right) - \left(F(F(8)) \times -\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \\
 26795 &:= \left(\left(2 + F(F(6))\right) \times \sqrt{F(F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})}}\right) \times 5 \\
 26895 &:= \left(2^{F(6)} \times F(8) + \sqrt{9}\right) \times 5 \\
 26924 &:= \left(F\left(-F(2) + F(F(6))\right) - F(9)\right) \times \sqrt{2^4} \\
 26946 &:= \left(\left(\left(-F(2) + F(F(6))\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 26964 &:= \left(F\left(-F(2) + F(F(6))\right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)\right)\right) \times 4 \\
 26969 &:= \left(F\left(F(2) + F(F(6))\right)\right) + \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \\
 26985 &:= \left(\left(2^{F(6)} + F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times \left(F(8) \times 5\right) \\
 26992 &:= \left(\left(F\left(-F(2) + F(F(6))\right)\right) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F(9) \times 2 \\
 26994 &:= \left(-2 + \left(\left(F(F(6)) + 9\right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 4\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26996 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left((F(F(6)) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (6) \right) \right) \\
 26999 &:= -F(2) + \left(6 \times \sqrt{F(9) - 9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 27144 &:= \left(\left(F(2) - \left(F(F(7))^{\sqrt{1 \times 4}} \right) \right) / \left(-\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 27364 &:= \left(-F(2) - \left(\left((-7) + F(3) \right) \times F(F(F(6))) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 27365 &:= \left(\left(F(F((F(2) + (7)))) / F(\sqrt{3+6}) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 27467 &:= \left(\left((-2) + F(7) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times \left(-6 + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 27469 &:= \left(\left((2 \times 7)^4 - F(F(F(6))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 27494 &:= \left((-2) \times F(F(7)) \times \left(-4 - F\left(9 + F(\sqrt{4})\right) \right) \right) \\
 27497 &:= \left(2 - \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(-9 \times F(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27649 &:= \left(\left(2^7 \right) \times \left(6^{F(4)} \right) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 27694 &:= - \left(\left(F((-2) + F(7)) + \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \times -F(4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27753 &:= \left(F(F((F(2) + (7)))) + \left(7^{\sqrt{5^{F(3)}}} \right) \right) \\
 27754 &:= \left(F(F((F(2) + (7)))) + \left(7^5 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 27756 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{2+7} + 7^5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 27783 &:= \sqrt{2+7} \times (F(7) + 8)^3 \\
 27796 &:= \left(\left(\left(2^{F(7)} + F(F(7)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 27846 &:= \left(\sqrt{2+7} \times \left(F(8)^{F(4)} + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 27889 &:= \left(-2 + F(7) \times (-8 + F(8)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 27928 &:= \left(- \left((2+7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F((2+F(8))) \right) \\
 27951 &:= \left(\left((-2) + F(7) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(F((5+1))) \right) \\
 27958 &:= \left(-2 + \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(\sqrt{9} \times (5 \times 8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 27960 &:= \left(\left(F((F(2) \times F(7))) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times 60 \right) \\
 27965 &:= \left(\left(F(2) - \left(F(F(7)) \times - \left(\sqrt{9} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 27966 &:= \left(\left(F(2) - \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 27984 &:= \left(\left((-2) + F(F(7)) \right) + F \left(- \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(8) \right) \right) \right) \times 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28047 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) - F(\left(\sqrt{04} + F(7)\right)) \right) \\
 28279 &:= \left((-F(2) + F((F(8) + 2))) - F\left(7 \times F(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 28296 &:= \left(-\left(\left(-2 + F(8)\right)^2\right) + F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6))\right) \right) \\
 28369 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) - \left(F((F(3) \times 6)) \times F(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 28398 &:= \left((F((2 + F(8))) - 3) - \left(F(\sqrt{9})^8\right) \right) \\
 28425 &:= \left((F(2) + F\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4}\right)) - F(F((2 + 5))) \right) \\
 28426 &:= \left((2 + F\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4}\right)) - F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \right) \\
 28457 &:= \left(\left(\left(-F(2) + F(F(8))\right) \times F(\sqrt{4})\right) / 5 \right) \times F(7) \\
 28469 &:= \left((F(2) + F\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4}\right)) - (F(F(6)) \times 9) \right) \\
 28479 &:= \left(-\left(F(2) - \left(F(8)^{F(4)}\right)\right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 28488 &:= \left((-F(2) + F\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4}\right)) + (-8 \times F(8)) \right) \\
 28498 &:= \left((F(-((F(2) - 8)))^4) - (\sqrt{9} \times F(8)) \right) \\
 28532 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - \sqrt{5^{3 \times 2}}) \\
 28534 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5^3) - \sqrt{4})) \\
 28549 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (54 \times F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 28564 &:= F(\sqrt{2 \times 8}) + (5 + F(6))^4 \\
 28569 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F((5 + 6))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 28589 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5 + (F(8) \times \sqrt{9}))) \\
 28594 &:= (F((F(2) + 8)) \times ((-5) + F(9))^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 28596 &:= \left((F((2 + F(8))) - F\left(5 \times F(\sqrt{9})\right)) - 6 \right) \\
 28597 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5)) - F(\sqrt{9} + (7)) \\
 28599 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((-5) + F(9)) \times F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 28625 &:= F(2 + F(8)) - \sqrt{(6 - 2)^5} \\
 28633 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(6) \times \sqrt{3 \times 3}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$28634 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) - F(F(6)) - \sqrt{F(3) + \sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$28643 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) - (6 + \sqrt{4^3}) \right)$$

$$28646 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) - \left((6/\sqrt{4}) + F(6) \right) \right)$$

$$28647 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) - \left((6/\sqrt{4}) + (7) \right) \right)$$

$$28649 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) - (6 - 4)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$$

$$28651 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) - \sqrt{6 \times (5 + 1)} \right)$$

$$28660 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + F\left(\sqrt{F(6) + F(6 + 0)}\right) \right)$$

$$28661 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \sqrt{F(6) + F(6 \times 1)} \right)$$

$$28663 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \sqrt{(6 + 6) \times 3} \right)$$

$$28668 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + F(6) + F\left(\sqrt{F(6) + 8}\right) \right)$$

$$28669 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + (6 \times 6) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$28681 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) \times \sqrt{8 + 1}) \right)$$

$$28684 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) + F(8)) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$28686 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + F(F(6)) + \sqrt{8 \times F(6)} \right)$$

$$28689 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) + F(8)) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$28691 := \left(F((F(2) + 8)) + F\left(\left((F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) - 1\right)\right) \right)$$

$$28692 := \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + F\left((6 + \sqrt{9})\right) \right) + F(2) \right)$$

$$28695 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + (6) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}^5) \right) \right)$$

$$28696 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + F(F(6)) + (\sqrt{9} \times 6) \right)$$

$$28697 := \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \left(- (F(6)) \times (F(\sqrt{9}) - (7)) \right) \right)$$

$$28698 := \left(\left(- ((F(2) - F(8))) + F(F(6)) \right) + F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(8))\right)\right) \right)$$

$$28699 := 2 \times F(8) + F(69/\sqrt{9})$$

$$28738 := F(2 \times 8 + 7) + \sqrt{3^8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28744 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \left(F((7 + 4)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 28749 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \left(F((7 + 4)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 28767 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + \left(\sqrt{76} \right) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 28784 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \left((F(F(7)) + (F(8))) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 28798 &:= \left((F((2 \times 8)) / 7) + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 28799 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(7) - F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 28819 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \left(81 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 28849 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) + \sqrt{8^4 \times 9} \right) \\
 28879 &:= \left(\left((F((2 + F(8))) - 8) + F(F(7)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 28887 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) - F(\sqrt{8+8}) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 28889 &:= \left((-F(2)) + F((-8) + F(8)) \right) + F \left(\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 28890 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9+0} \right) \right) \right) \\
 28891 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 28892 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 28893 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 3 \right) \\
 28894 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 28895 &:= (2 + 8 \times F(8))^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 5 \\
 28896 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 6 \right) \\
 28897 &:= \left(\left(F((2 + F(8))) + \left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 28899 &:= -F(2) + \left(8 \times F(8) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 28945 &:= \left(F((2 + F(8))) - \left(- (9) \times \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\
 28946 &:= \left(289 + F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 28977 &:= \left(2 \times F(8) + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times F(7) \\
 28985 &:= \left(F(2) + F \left(8 \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 8 \right) \times 5 \\
 28986 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(-((F(2) - F(8)))) / -(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times - (8) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28997 &:= \left(F \left((2 + F(8)) \right) + \left(F(9) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29169 &:= \left((2^9) + F \left(\left(- (1) + \left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29189 &:= \left((F(2) + (F(F((9-1))) \times - (8))) / - \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 29269 &:= \left(\left(- \left((2-9) \right) \times F \left(\left(- (2) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 29287 &:= \left(- (F(2)) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(\left(- (2) + F(8) \right) \right) \right) \times - (7) \right) \right) \\
 29369 &:= \left(- (F(2)) - \left(\left(\left(F(9)^{F(3)} \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 29384 &:= \left(- \left(\left(2 - (9^3) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 29498 &:= \left(\sqrt{29^4} + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29546 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(2) + (9^5) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \\
 29584 &:= ((2 + F(9)) \times 5 - 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 29597 &:= (2 + F(9) \times 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(7) \\
 29642 &:= \left(\left(- (2) + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left((4^2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29643 &:= \left(\left(- (F(2)) + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left((4^{F(3)}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29646 &:= \left(\left(2 + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29696 &:= 2^9 \times F(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 6 \\
 29736 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) \times - (3) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 29744 &:= (2 + 9) \times (F(7) \times 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 29789 &:= -2 + \left(\sqrt{9} + 7 + F(8) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 29791 &:= (2 \times 9 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} \times 1 \\
 29792 &:= (2 \times 9 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(2) \\
 29793 &:= (2 \times 9 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(3) \\
 29794 &:= (2 \times 9 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(4) \\
 29879 &:= \left(2 - \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(F(F(8)) - (F((7+9))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 29883 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 - F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 29982 &:= 2 \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + F(9) \times F(8)^2 \right) \\
 29984 &:= 2 \times \left(-F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(9) \times F(8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 31584 &:= (3 - 1)^5 \times F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \\
 31848 &:= \left((3 \times (-1) + F(F(8))) - F(\sqrt{4} \times 8) \right) \\
 31899 &:= 31 \times F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} / 9 \\
 32139 &:= \left((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) - F(13)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 32595 &:= \left((3 \times F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))) - (\sqrt{9^5}) \right) \\
 32646 &:= \left(3 \times \left(F(F((2 + 6))) - (\sqrt{4^6}) \right) \right) \\
 32649 &:= \left((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) - (F(F(6)) \times F(4))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 32679 &:= \left(3 \times \left((2 + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(7) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 32698 &:= \left(((F(3) + 2)^{F(6)}) + (-\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8)) \right) \\
 32746 &:= \left(\left((F(3)^{2+F(7)}) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \\
 32749 &:= \left((3 \times F(F((F(2) + (7)))) - (F(\sqrt{4} + 9))) \right) \\
 32756 &:= \left((-3) + (2^{F(7)}) \right) \times \sqrt{-5 + F(F(6))} \\
 32762 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} - \sqrt{6^2} \\
 32779 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + F(7) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 32784 &:= (F(3)^{2 \times 7} + 8) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 32789 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + \sqrt{F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})}} \\
 32793 &:= \left((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) - (F(7) + F(\sqrt{9}))) \times 3 \right) \\
 32795 &:= (3^{F(2)+7} - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\
 32799 &:= F(3)^{2+F(7)} + F(9) - \sqrt{9} \\
 32834 &:= \left((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (F(3) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 32836 &:= \left((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - F(\sqrt{3+6}) \right) \\
 32839 &:= \left((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + (3/\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 32840 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 0 \\
 32841 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 1 \\
 32842 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 2 \\
 32843 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$32844 := 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 4$$

$$32845 := 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 5$$

$$32846 := 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 6$$

$$32857 := 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 7$$

$$32868 := 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 8$$

$$32869 := 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} + 9$$

$$32876 := \left(- (F(F(3))) + \left(F(\sqrt{2 \times 8}) \times (F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \right) \right)$$

$$32889 := \left(\left(\left((3^2) + 8 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$32895 := \left(3 \times \left((-2) + F(F(8)) \right) + F(\sqrt{9} + (5)) \right)$$

$$32898 := \left(F(F(3)) \times (28^{\sqrt{9}}) + F(F(8)) \right)$$

$$32899 := \left(\left(\left((3^2) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(9) \right)$$

$$32912 := 32^{\sqrt{9}} + F(12)$$

$$32927 := \left(\left(3 \times F(F(2^{\sqrt{9}})) \right) + (F((-2) + F(7))) \right)$$

$$32931 := \left(3 \times \left(F(F(2^{\sqrt{9}})) + (31) \right) \right)$$

$$32939 := \left(\left((F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + F(9)) \times 3 \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$32943 := \left(\left(F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + (F(9) + F(\sqrt{4})) \right) \times 3 \right)$$

$$32958 := \left(3 \times \left(\left((2^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 5 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$32963 := \left(\left((3+2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3) \right)$$

$$32965 := \left(32 + \sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \right) \times 5$$

$$32979 := \left((F(F(F(3 \times 2))) + (F(9) + F(7))) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$33169 := \left(331 + \left(F(F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$33464 := \left(F(3) \times \left(\left(F(3) + F(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6))) \right) \right) \times 4 \right)$$

$$33466 := \left(F(3) - \left(\left(F(3) + F(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6))) \right) \right) \times - (F(6)) \right)$$

$$33488 := \left(\left((-3) - F(3) \right) - F(-(\sqrt{4} - F(8))) \right) \times - (8)$$

$$33489 := \left(F(3) \times 3^4 + F(8) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$33546 := \left(3 \times \left(\left(3 + F(F(5 + \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33547 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(F \left((F(3) \times 5) \right) \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33548 &:= -F(3) + F(3 \times 5) \times F(\sqrt{4} + 8) \\
 33569 &:= \left(F(3) + \left(\left(3^5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 33589 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(F \left((F(3) + (5)) \right) \times F \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33594 &:= \left(F(3) + \left(F \left((F(3) + (5)) \right) \times F \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33694 &:= \left(F \left((3 \times 3) \right) \times \left(F \left(\left(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 33697 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left(F \left((F(3) \times 6) \right) \times \left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33796 &:= \left(F \left((3 \times 3) \right) \times \left(7 + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33824 &:= \left(\left((F(3) + 3) \times F \left((F(8) - F(2)) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 33846 &:= \left(\left((F(3) + 3) \times F \left(\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 33876 &:= \left(3 \times \left((3 + F(F(8))) + \left(\sqrt{7^6} \right) \right) \right) \\
 33969 &:= \left(\left(F \left((F(3) + (3 + 9)) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 33978 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(3 + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 33994 &:= \left(\left(3 \times F \left(F \left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 33999 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(3)) - \left(\left((F(F(3)) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F(9) \right) \right) \right) \\
 34659 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(- (F(4)) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + \left(F \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 34674 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(F(6))) \right) + F \left(\left(F(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 34693 &:= \left(\left(F(3) \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) - \left((9^3) \right) \right) \\
 34749 &:= 3^4 \times F(7) \times \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + F(9) \right) \\
 34758 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4^7} \times 5 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 34816 &:= \left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{4}+8} \right) \times F \left((1 + F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 34848 &:= (3 + F(4) \times F(8))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \\
 34876 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8) \right) \right) - \left(F(7) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 34965 &:= F(3 + 4)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(6)^5 \\
 34969 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)) + \left((F(4) - F(9)) \times - (6) \right) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34976 &:= \left(-F(3) + \sqrt{4} \times \sqrt{9^7}\right) \times F(6) \\
 34986 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (F(9) \times F(8))\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right)\right) \\
 34992 &:= F(3 \times 4) \times \sqrt{9} \times 9^2 \\
 34995 &:= \left(3 + \left(F((F(4) + 9)) \times \sqrt{9^5}\right)\right) \\
 35189 &:= -\left(\left(F(F((F(3) + (5))))\right) - \left(\left(F((1 + F(8))) \times F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)\right) \\
 35396 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(-F((5 + F(3))) + F\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F(F(6)))\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 35419 &:= \left(F(3) \times F((F((5 + F(4))) + 1))\right) - \sqrt{9} \\
 35424 &:= F(3) \times F(5 \times 4 + 2) + \sqrt{4} \\
 35428 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(\sqrt{5+4} + F((F(2) + F(8)))\right)\right) \\
 35432 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(5 + F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F((3 \times 2)))\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 35436 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))))\right)\right) \\
 35448 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(F\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(8))\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 35464 &:= \left(F((F(3) + ((5 \times 4)))) + F(F(6))\right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 35478 &:= 3^5 \times \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + 7 \times F(8)\right) \\
 35799 &:= \left(F(F((3 + 5))) + (F((7 + 9)))\right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 35929 &:= -3 - 5 + (F(9) - F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 35934 &:= \left(35 - F(\sqrt{9})\right)^3 - F(4) \\
 35937 &:= \left(35 - F(\sqrt{9})\right)^{F(-3+7)} \\
 35939 &:= \left(35 - F(\sqrt{9})\right)^3 + F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 35943 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + (5)\right) + \left(\left(F(9) - F(\sqrt{4})\right)^3\right) \\
 35944 &:= F(3) + 5 + \left(F(9) - F(\sqrt{4})\right)^{F(4)} \\
 35964 &:= \left(\left(3^5\right) + \left(9 \times F(F(6))\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \\
 36162 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{3^{F(6)}} + 1\right) \times \left(F(F(6))^2\right)\right) \\
 36174 &:= F(3 \times 6) \times (1 + F(7)) - \sqrt{4} \\
 36179 &:= F(3 \times 6) \times (1 + F(7)) + \sqrt{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36399 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(3) + F(F(6)) \right)^3 - F(9) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 36438 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4} \right)^3 - F(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36446 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(\left(F(6)^{F(4)} + F \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36479 &:= \left(-F(3) + \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 36483 &:= 3 \times \left(-6 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right)^3 \right) \\
 36499 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(3) + F(F(6)) \right)^{F(4)} \times \sqrt{9} - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 36673 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)) + \left(\sqrt{6^6} \right) \right) \times \left(F(7)^{F(3)} \right) \right) \\
 36699 &:= \left(\left(-F(3 \times 6) - F(F(6)) + \left(F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 36799 &:= \left(\left(3 \times F(F(F(6))) - \left(F(F(7)) \times -F(9) \right) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 36849 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3) + F(F(6))) - \left(- \left(8^4 \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36949 &:= \left(\left(F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) + \left(\left(F(9) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 36964 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)) + \left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 36978 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(-6 \times \left(\sqrt{9} - F(F(7)) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 36993 &:= \left(F(3) + \left(F(6) \times F(9) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} / F(3) \right) \\
 37249 &:= \left(-3 + 7^2 \times 4 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 37396 &:= \left(\left(\left(-3 + F(F(7)) \right)^{F(3)} / F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 37446 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(3) \times \left(F(F(7)) + 4 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} / 6 \right) \right) \\
 37584 &:= \left(\left(F(3) + 7 \right) \times \left(-5 + F \left(F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 37629 &:= 3 \times F(7 + 6 \times 2) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 37638 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)) + F(F(7) + 6) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right) \\
 37649 &:= \left(F(3) + \left(\left(F(F(7) + 6) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 37674 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)) + F(F(7)) \right) \times - \left(F(6) - \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 37684 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(3 + F(7)) \right) \times -F(6) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$37689 := \left(\left((-F(3) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)) \right) - \left(F(F(8)) \times -(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$$

$$37696 := \left(\left(F((F(3) + F(7))) - F(F(6)) \right) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}^6) \right) \right)$$

$$37747 := \left(F(F(3)) + \left(F(F(7)) \times \left((F(7)^{\sqrt{4}}) - (7) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$37748 := \left(F(3) + \left((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{F(4)^8} \right) \right)$$

$$37794 := \left(3 \times \left(-F(F(7)) \right) - \left(-F(7) \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}^4) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$37966 := \left(-F(3) + \left(\left(F(F(7)) - \left(\sqrt{9}^{F(6)} \right) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right)$$

$$37986 := \left(\left((3 - F(F(7))) + \left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$38274 := \left(\left((F(F(3)) - F(F(8))) - \left(2^{F(7)} \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$38297 := \left(\left((-3 + F(F(8))) - F(2) \right) / F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right)$$

$$38416 := (F(3) + 8 + 4)^{\sqrt{16}}$$

$$38445 := \left((3 \times F(F((F(8) / F(4)))) \right) \times F(\sqrt{4} \times 5)$$

$$38478 := \left(3 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left((\sqrt{4} + F(F(7))) \times - (8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$38479 := \left(\left((3 \times F((8 + \sqrt{4}))) \right) \times F(F(7)) + F(9) \right)$$

$$38495 := F(3) + F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times (F(9) + 5)$$

$$38645 := \left(F(3 \times 8) / 6 - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5$$

$$38679 := \left((-((F(3) - (F(8) \times F(6)))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$38745 := \left((3 \times F(8)) \times \left(F(F(7) + \sqrt{4}) + (5) \right) \right)$$

$$38747 := \left(\left(F((-3 + F(8))) \times (F(7) + \sqrt{4}) \right) - F(7) \right)$$

$$38927 := F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(2 \times 7)$$

$$38976 := \left((F(F(3)) \times 8) \times \left((F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7))) \times - (F(F(6))) \right) \right)$$

$$38978 := \left(F(3) - \left(8 \times \left((F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7))) \times F(8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$38982 := F(3 + 8) \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + F(8)^2 \right)$$

$$38997 := \left((3 \times F(8)) \times \left(9 + F \left((F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(7))) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$39199 := -3 \times (F(9) + 1) + F(9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$39249 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)^2 \right) \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 9 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$39286 := \left(3 + \left(\left(F(9)^{F(\sqrt{2 \times 8})} \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \right)$$

$$39294 := \left(3^9 - 2 - F(9) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$39296 := \left(F(3) + F(9) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(6)$$

$$39297 := \left(F(3) + F(9) - 2 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - 7$$

$$39299 := F(3) - 9 + 2 + F(9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$39309 := F(3) + F(9)^3 + \sqrt{09}$$

$$39317 := F \left(3 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^3 + F(1 \times 7)$$

$$39324 := \left(\left(\left(3^9 \right) - F(F(3 \times 2)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$39338 := F \left(3 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^3 + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{38}} \right)$$

$$39346 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3^9 \right) \times F(3) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F(F(6)) \right)$$

$$39347 := \left(3^9 - 3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} - F(7)$$

$$39354 := \left(\left(\left(\left(3^9 \right) - F(F(3)) \right) - (5) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$39359 := 3^9 \times F(3) - 5 - F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$39373 := 3^9 \times F(3) + \sqrt{7^{F(3)}}$$

$$39379 := 3^9 \times F(3) + \sqrt{F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})}}$$

$$39386 := F(3) + \left(\sqrt{9} + 3^8 \right) \times 6$$

$$39389 := 3^9 \times F(3) + F(8) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$39399 := F(3) + 93 + F(9)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$39434 := F(3) \times \left(F(9) + F(4)^{\sqrt{34}} \right)$$

$$39440 := \left(\left(- \left(F(F(3)) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 40$$

$$39446 := -F(3) + F(9)^{F(4)} + F \left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right)$$

$$39447 := \left(- \left(\left(F(F(3)) - \left(F(9)^{F(4)} \right) \right) \right) + F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(F(7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$39448 := F \left(3 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{F(4)} + F(4 + 8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39456 &:= \left(\left(3 - \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \times - (F(6)) \right) \\
 39465 &:= \left(\left(- (3) - \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) \times - (F(6)) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 39473 &:= F \left(3 \times \sqrt{9} \right)^{F(4)} + F(7)^{F(3)} \\
 39485 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)) - \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) \times - (8) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 39546 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (5) \right) \right)^{F(4)} \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 39574 &:= \left(- (F(3)) + \left(F(9) \times \left((5 \times F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39585 &:= F \left(3 \times \sqrt{9} + 5 \right) \times F(8) \times 5 \\
 39594 &:= \left(\left((F((-3) + F(9))) - (5) \right) / F(9) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 39595 &:= \left(\left(- (3) - \left(- (F(9)) \times F \left(F \left((5 + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 39596 &:= \left((F((-3) + F(9))) - (5) \right) / F \left((\sqrt{9} + (6)) \right) \\
 39598 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left((F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) - (5) \right) + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39599 &:= \left(\left((F((-3) + F(9))) - (5) \right) / F(9) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 39603 &:= \left(F \left(F \left((F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) + F \left((F(F(6)) + F(03)) \right) \right) \\
 39606 &:= \left(\left(3 + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(06))) \right) \\
 39679 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F \left((F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) - \left((- (F(6)) + F(F(7)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 39690 &:= \left(\left(F \left((F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \times 90 \right) \\
 39796 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^7 \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 39836 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (F(F(8)) - F((F(3) \times F(6)))) \right) \\
 39874 &:= \left(\left(\left((3^9) + F(8) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 39915 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left(\left(F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(15) \right) \right) \\
 39925 &:= \left(F \left(\left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + 9 \right) \right) \times 25 \right) \\
 39930 &:= (F(3) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 30 \\
 39936 &:= F(3)^9 \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + \sqrt{3^{F(6)}} \right) \\
 39976 &:= \left(\left(F(3) \times (\sqrt{9^9}) \right) + F((7 + F(6))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40596 &:= \left(\left(F((4 \times 05)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times 6 \\
 40975 &:= \left(F(4) + F(\sqrt{09})^{F(7)} \right) \times 5 \\
 41469 &:= F(4) \times \left(-1 + (4 \times 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 41472 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(1 + 4 + 7)^2 \\
 41474 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(1 + \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(7) \right)^4 \right) \\
 41496 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(- (1) - F\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) \right) \right) \times - \left(F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 41597 &:= \left((4 \times F(F(F((1 + 5)))) - \left(\sqrt{9}^7 \right) \right) \\
 41687 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(16) \right) \times F(8) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 41810 &:= \left(F\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times - (1)\right) + F(8)\right)\right) \times 10 \right) \\
 41848 &:= \left(4 \times \left(- \left((1 + F(8))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 41984 &:= 41 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8^{F(4)} \\
 42439 &:= F(4^2) \times 43 - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 42443 &:= \sqrt{4} + F(2^4) \times 43 \\
 42632 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + F(2 \times 6) \right)^{F(3)} \times 2 \\
 42770 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F((2 + F(7))) \right) \right) \times 70 \\
 42849 &:= \left(F(4) \times (2 + F(8)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 9 \\
 42874 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + (28 + 7)^{F(4)} \\
 42896 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F((F(2) + 8)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \\
 42966 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left(2^{\sqrt{9} + F(6)} \right) \right) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 42984 &:= \left(F(4) \times \left(\left(F(2) - F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(8)\right) \right) \right) / - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43343 &:= \left(\left(F(F((4 + 3)))^{F(3)} \right) - F\left(F(\sqrt{4^3})\right) \right) \\
 43428 &:= \left(43 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(2 \times 8) \\
 43428 &:= \left(F\left(4^{F(3)}\right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} \times (F(2) + F(8)) \right) \\
 43464 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left(3^4 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43468 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(3) - \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 43576 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 43646 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left((F(3) \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(4^{F(6)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43648 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(3) - \sqrt{6^4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 43649 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(F \left(\left(F(4)^{F(3)} \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 4 \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43659 &:= \left(\left(4 \times F(F((F(3) + (6)))) \right) - \left(\left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43674 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((F(3) \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(7) - F(4))) \right) \right) \\
 43676 &:= \left(4 \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{3^6} \right) + F((F(7) + F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 43679 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left((-3) \times F(6) \right) + F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 43684 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \sqrt{3^6} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43689 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \left((-F(3)) - F(F(6)) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 43696 &:= \left(4 \times \left((-3) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43699 &:= \left(\left(4 \times \left(F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(9 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43720 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + 3^7 \right) \times 20 \\
 43732 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4^3} \right) \right) - F(7) \right) \times (F(3) + 2) \right) \\
 43738 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(- \left(\left(3^7 \right) \right) \times (F(F(3)) - (F(8))) \right) \right) \\
 43745 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + 3^7 \times 4 \right) \times 5 \\
 43746 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (3 \times F(7)) \right) - \left(- (4) \times F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 43748 &:= 4 \times \left(F(3 \times 7) - F(\sqrt{4}) - 8 \right) \\
 43749 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - F(\sqrt{4}) - F(9) \\
 43759 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - 5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 43776 &:= 4 \times F \left(3 \times \sqrt{7 \times 7} \right) - F(6) \\
 43777 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - \sqrt{7 \times 7} \\
 43778 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((-3) + F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 43779 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - 7 + F(\sqrt{9})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43781 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - \sqrt{8+1} \\
 43782 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) - \sqrt{8/2} \\
 43783 &:= (-\sqrt{4} + F(3 \times 7) \times 8) / F(3) \\
 43785 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) + F(3 \times 7) \times \sqrt{F(8) - 5} \\
 43788 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + \sqrt{8+8} \\
 43789 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + 8 - \sqrt{9} \\
 43791 &:= 4 \times (F(3) + F(7 \times \sqrt{9})) - 1 \\
 43793 &:= 4 \times F(3 \times 7) + \sqrt{9^{F(3)}} \\
 43794 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) + \sqrt{9}) - \sqrt{4} \\
 43797 &:= (\sqrt{4} + F(3)) \times F(7 \times \sqrt{9}) + F(7) \\
 43798 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times ((F(F(3)) \times 7) + (F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8)))))) \\
 43799 &:= 4 \times (F(3 \times 7) + \sqrt{9}) + \sqrt{9} \\
 43804 &:= (((\sqrt{4} + 3) + F(F(8))) \times 04) \\
 43818 &:= (((\sqrt{4} + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + F((1+8))) \\
 43819 &:= (((\sqrt{4} + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + (1 + F(9))) \\
 43824 &:= (((\sqrt{4^3} + F(F(8))) + 2) \times 4) \\
 43826 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times ((F(3) \times F(F(8))) + F((2+6)))) \\
 43828 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times ((F(3) \times F(F(8))) + (F(2) + F(8)))) \\
 43836 &:= (F((4+3)) + F(F(8))) \times \sqrt{F(3) \times F(6)} \\
 43838 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (((- (3) - F(F(8))) \times - (F(3))) + (F(8)))) \\
 43839 &:= (((\sqrt{4} + F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(F(3)) + 9))) \\
 43846 &:= (- ((F(\sqrt{4}) - (3 \times F(8)))) - (- (4) \times F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 43849 &:= (- (F(4)) + (F(3) \times ((F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{4}) + F(9)))) \\
 43868 &:= ((F(\sqrt{4^3}) + F(F(8))) \times \sqrt{F(6) + 8}) \\
 43869 &:= ((- (4) \times (F(F(3)) - F(F(8)))) + F((F(6) + \sqrt{9})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43873 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(3) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + F((F(7) - F(3))) \right) \\
 43878 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((F(3) \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7)))) + (F(8))) \right) \\
 43884 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(3) \right) + F(8) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43892 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(4)^3 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + F(2) \right) \right) \\
 43894 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F((- (3) + F(8))) \right) \times \left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43924 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) + 3 \times (9 + 2)^4 \\
 43929 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + ((F((F(3) \times 9)) / - (2)) \times - (F(9))) \right) \\
 43962 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times (F((F(3) + 9)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 2)) \right) \\
 43964 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) \times 9 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43968 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(3) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 43974 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4^3}) \times ((9 \times F(F(7))) - F(4)) \right) \\
 43976 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + ((- (3) + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \times F(F(6))) \right) \\
 43988 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times (((3 \times F(9)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) \right) \\
 44064 &:= \left(F\left(\left(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times \left(06^4 \right) \right) \\
 44279 &:= - \left(\left(F(F((4 + 4))) - \left(2 + F(F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 44296 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^- ((2 - 9)) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 44364 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F((4 \times 3)) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44368 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F((F(3) \times 6)) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 44436 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 44 \right)^{F(3)} \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 44496 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 9 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 44646 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(4 \times \left(\left(6^{F(4)} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44648 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times \left(6^{F(4)} \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 44666 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(F(F(6))) \right) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 44679 &:= \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left(4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) - 9)) \right) \right) \\
 44683 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(8)^3 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44708 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + F(F(7))\right) + F(F(08))\right)\right) \\
 44715 &:= \left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + \left(4 \times \left(F(F(7)) + F(F(F((1+5))))\right)\right)\right) \\
 44717 &:= F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + 4 \times 7 \times F(17) \\
 44718 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(4 \times \left(F(F(7)) + F(F((1 \times 8))))\right)\right) \\
 44726 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(F(7)) + 2\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right)\right)\right) \\
 44734 &:= \left(\left(\left(4^{F(4)}\right) \times F(F(7))\right) \times 3\right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 44739 &:= \left(\left(\left(-\left(4^{F(4)}\right)\right) \times F(F(7))\right) - F(F(3))\right) \times -\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \\
 44746 &:= \left(\left(-4\right) + \left(\left(F(4) + F(F(7))\right)^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) - F(F(F(6))) \\
 44767 &:= \left(\left(-4\right) + F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(7)\right)\right)\right) - \left(F(F(F(6))) \times 7\right) \\
 44769 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - F\left(\left(4 + F(7)\right)\right)\right) + F\left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 44776 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7)\right) + F(F(7))\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right)\right) \\
 44808 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\sqrt{4^8} + F(F(08))\right)\right) \\
 44876 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \times F(F(8))\right) + \left(F(7) \times F(F(6))\right)\right)\right) \\
 44878 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(F(7) \times F(8)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 44936 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F((9+3))\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right)\right) \\
 44967 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(4 - \left(-9\right) \times F(F(6))\right)\right) \times F(F(7))\right) \\
 44982 &:= F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \times F(4) \times F(9) \times F(8)^2 \\
 44983 &:= F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + F(4) \times F(9) \times F(8)^{F(3)} \\
 44984 &:= \sqrt{4} + F(4) \times F(9) \times F(8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 44988 &:= F(4) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F(9) \times F(8) \times F(8)\right) \\
 45369 &:= \left(F(4) + \left(\left(5 \times F(3)\right) \times F(F(6))\right)\right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 45436 &:= \left(\left(-4\right) \times F\left(F\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) + F\left(\left(3 \times F(6)\right)\right) \\
 45467 &:= \left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + \left(\left(-54\right) \times F(F(F(6)))\right) / -\left(F(7)\right)\right) \\
 45486 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(4)^{5+\sqrt{4}}\right) - F(8)\right) \times F(F(6))\right) \\
 45617 &:= \left(\left(-4\right) + \sqrt{5^6}\right) \times F\left(\left(1 + F(7)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 45648 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F((5 + F(6))) \times \sqrt{4}\right) + F(F(8))\right)\right) \\
 45669 &:= \left(\left(-F(4) \times F((5 + F(6)))\right) + F\left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 45695 &:= -\left(\left(F((F(4) \times 5)) + \left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}}\right) \times - (5)\right)\right)\right) \\
 45864 &:= \left(\left(- (4) \times (- (5) - F(8))\right) \times \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}\right)\right) \\
 45948 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + 5\right) \times 9^4 + F(8) \\
 45975 &:= \left(F(4) + F\left(5 \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times 75 \\
 45989 &:= -\sqrt{4} - F(5 + 9) + F\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 46134 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(13) - F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \\
 46136 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - F(F((6 + 1)))\right) + F((3 \times F(6)))\right) \\
 46138 &:= F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + F(6 + 1)^3 \times F(8) \\
 46139 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(F(F(6)) \times - \left(\left(13^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 46274 &:= \left(F\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + F(F(6))\right)\right) - \left(- (2) - \left(F(7)^4\right)\right)\right) \\
 46279 &:= \left(F((4 \times 6)) - F\left(\left(F(2) + (7) + \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 46289 &:= -\sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} + 2 + F\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 46305 &:= F\left(\sqrt{4} + 6\right)^3 \times 05 \\
 46315 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(F(F(6))^3\right)\right) \times (1 \times 5)\right) \\
 46349 &:= F(4 \times 6) - F(3)^4 - \sqrt{9} \\
 46354 &:= F(4 \times 6) - (F(3) + 5) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 46359 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (F(3) - 5) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 46373 &:= F(4 \times 6) + 3 + \sqrt{7 - 3} \\
 46375 &:= \sqrt{4} + F(6 \times (-3 + 7)) + 5 \\
 46377 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) + \sqrt{7 \times 7} \\
 46379 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(3) \times 7 - \sqrt{9} \\
 \\
 46380 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 0 \\
 46381 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 1 \\
 46382 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 2 \\
 46383 &:= \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$46384 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 4$$

$$46385 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 5$$

$$46386 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 6$$

$$46387 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 7$$

$$46388 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 8$$

$$46389 := \sqrt{4} \times 6 + F(3 \times 8) + 9$$

$$46398 := F(4 \times 6) + 3 \times \sqrt{9} + F(8)$$

$$46409 := \left((F((4 \times 6)) + 40) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)$$

$$46424 := F(\sqrt{4}) + F(6 + 4) + F(24)$$

$$46425 := \sqrt{4} + F(6 \times 4) + F(2 \times 5)$$

$$46432 := F(4 \times 6) + \sqrt{4^{3 \times 2}}$$

$$46434 := F(4 \times 6) + 4^3 + \sqrt{4}$$

$$46436 := F(4 \times 6) + \sqrt{4} \times F(3 + 6)$$

$$46446 := \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} - F(4) + F(4 \times 6)$$

$$46449 := F(4 \times 6) + F(4)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 9$$

$$46456 := F(4 \times 6) - F(\sqrt{4}) + F(5 + 6)$$

$$46457 := \left(F((F(4) + F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4} \times (5 + 7)) \right)$$

$$46489 := (F(4) + F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} + F(8 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$46494 := F(4) \times 6 \times \left(F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$46538 := F(4 \times 6) + 5 \times F(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}})$$

$$46546 := \sqrt{4} \times F(6 + 5) + F(4 \times 6)$$

$$46568 := F(4 \times 6) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \times 8$$

$$46575 := \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} \times 575$$

$$46576 := -\sqrt{4} + (6^5 - F(7)) \times 6$$

$$46593 := F(4 \times 6) + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{F(3)}$$

$$46596 := (-F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^5 - 9) \times 6$$

$$46598 := 46 \times 5 + F(\sqrt{9} \times 8)$$

$$46599 := \left(\left(F((4 \times 6)) + F \left(F \left(\left(5 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right)$$

$$46625 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 - 2^5$$

$$46628 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times 6^6 - 28$$

$$46634 := - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) - \left(\left(6^{F(3)} \right)^{F(4)} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$46635 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 - F(3 + 5))$$

$$46639 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 - F(3) \times 9$$

$$46646 := \sqrt{4} + 6^6 - 4 - F(6)$$

$$46650 := -F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 - 5 + 0$$

$$46659 := (-\sqrt{4} + F(6)) \times 6^5 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$46670 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 0$$

$$46671 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 1$$

$$46672 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 2$$

$$46673 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 3$$

$$46674 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 4$$

$$46675 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 5$$

$$46676 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 6$$

$$46677 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 7$$

$$46678 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 8$$

$$46679 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 6^6 + F(7) + 9$$

$$46690 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 0$$

$$46691 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 1$$

$$46692 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 2$$

$$46693 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 3$$

$$46694 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46695 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 5 \\
 46696 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 6 \\
 46697 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 7 \\
 46698 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 8 \\
 46699 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times (6^6 + F(9)) + 9 \\
 46743 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - F(3) \\
 46744 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 46809 &:= F(4 \times 6) + F(8)^{F(\sqrt{09})} \\
 46834 &:= (F((4 \times 6)) + (F(F((F(8)/3))) \times \sqrt{4})) \\
 46867 &:= F(4 \times 6) + \sqrt{8^6} - F(7) \\
 46875 &:= \sqrt{(-F(4) + F(6))^8} \times 75 \\
 46956 &:= \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} + \sqrt{9} \times 5^6 \\
 46974 &:= ((- (4) + F((F(6) \times \sqrt{9}))) + F((F(7) + \sqrt{4}))) \\
 46976 &:= ((- (\sqrt{4}) + F((F(6) \times \sqrt{9}))) + F((7 + F(6)))) \\
 46978 &:= F(((\sqrt{4} + 6) \times \sqrt{9}) + F(7 + 8)) \\
 46979 &:= ((F(\sqrt{4}) + F((F(6) \times \sqrt{9}))) + F((F(7) + F(\sqrt{9})))) \\
 47125 &:= F(\sqrt{4} \times 7) \times 125 \\
 47206 &:= (- (\sqrt{4}) + (- (7) \times (- (F(20)) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 47208 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times 7 \times (F(20) - F(8)) \\
 47266 &:= (F((\sqrt{4} + F(7))) - (F(2) \times - ((6^6)))) \\
 47297 &:= (- (\sqrt{4}) - (F(F(7)) \times - ((29 \times 7)))) \\
 47298 &:= (((4 \times F(F(7))) - 2) + F((\sqrt{9} \times 8))) \\
 47336 &:= (\sqrt{4} + (7 \times (- (3) + F(- ((F(F(3)) - F(F(6))))))) \\
 47346 &:= (- (\sqrt{4}) + (7 \times (- (F(F(3))) + F(- ((F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6))))))) \\
 47348 &:= ((F(\sqrt{4}) \times 7) \times (- (F(F(3))) + F(- ((F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8)))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47353 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(- \left(7 \right) \times F \left(\left(\left(F \left(3 \right) \times 5 \right) \times F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47354 &:= -F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \sqrt{7^{F(3)}} \times F \left(5 \times 4 \right) \\
 47355 &:= F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \times F \left(3 \times 5 + 5 \right) \\
 47356 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(7 \times F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(- \left(\left(3 - 5 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47357 &:= \sqrt{4} + F \left(\left(7 - 3 \right) \times 5 \right) \times 7 \\
 47359 &:= \left(4 + \left(7 \times F \left(\left(\left(F \left(3 \right) \times 5 \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47361 &:= \left(- \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(7 \times \left(- \left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47362 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right) \times \left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - F \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47363 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(7 \times \left(- \left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47364 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(7 \times \left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47367 &:= \left(- \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(\left(7 \times F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47368 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(F \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) + 3 \right) \right) \times - \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(8 \right) \right) \\
 47369 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right) \times \left(F \left(3 \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47374 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right)^{F(3)} - 7 \right) / F \left(4 \right) \\
 47376 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(7 \right) \right) \times F \left(\left(3 + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 47377 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(- \left(7 \right) \times \left(3 + F \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) + \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47384 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(7 \times \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) - \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 47433 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(F \left(7 \right) \times F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4^3} \right) \right) \right) \right) / 3 \right) \\
 47434 &:= \left(\left(4 + \left(F \left(7 \right) \times F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4^3} \right) \right) \right) \right) / F \left(4 \right) \right) \\
 47437 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(\left(7 \times F \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) / 3 \right) \times F \left(7 \right) \right) \\
 47467 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(4 \right) + F \left(7 \right) \right) + F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 47493 &:= \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} - F \left(4 \right) + F \left(9 \right)^3 \\
 47494 &:= \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} - \sqrt{4} + F \left(9 \right)^{F(4)} \\
 47499 &:= \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} + F \left(4 \right) + F \left(9 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 47524 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(5 + 2 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47538 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right) \times 5 \right) + F((3 \times 8)) \right) \\
 47574 &:= \left(F(4) \times \left(F(F(7)) + \left(5^{7-F(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 47643 &:= \left(F((F(4) + F(7))) + \left(\left(\sqrt{6^{4 \times 3}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 47697 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4} + F(7)) \right) \times 6 \right) + 9 \right) \times F(7) \\
 47736 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right) \times F((7 + F(3))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 47744 &:= \sqrt{4^7} \times \left(F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - 4 \right) \\
 47754 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \left(- (5) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 47767 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times - (6) \right) + F(7) \right) \\
 47793 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) + \left(F(F(7)) - F(9) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \\
 47796 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(4)^7 \right) + F\left(F(7) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \times F(F(6)) \\
 47829 &:= \left(4^7 - F(8)^2 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 47845 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 47879 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4} \times 7) \right) \times \left(F(8) + F(F(7)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 47910 &:= \left(F((4 + F(7))) \times (\sqrt{9} \times 10) \right) \\
 47946 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(7)) \right) \times F(9) \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 47959 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + \left(F(F(7)) - (9 + 5) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 47963 &:= \left(\left(F((4 + F(7))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F((F(6) \times 3)) \right) \\
 47964 &:= \left(\left(F((4 + F(7))) + F(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 47966 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F((F(7) + 9)) \right) - \left(F(F(F(6))) \times - (6) \right) \right) \\
 47985 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) + 9 \right) \times \left(F(8) \times - (5) \right) \right) \\
 47986 &:= \left(\left(F((4 + F(7))) + F(\sqrt{9} \times 8) \right) \right) + F(F(6)) \\
 47996 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(9) \times - (6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47997 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left(\left(F(F(7)) - (9 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48339 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4} + F(8)) \right) - F(F(3)) \right) + \left(\left(3^9 \right) \right) \\
 48357 &:= \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times \left(F(3 \times 5) - F(7) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48373 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(8)) \right) - \left((3 \times F(7))^3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 48374 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(8)) \right) + \left((3 \times F(7))^{F(4)} \right) \right) \\
 48377 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (F(8 \times F(3))) \times 7 \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 48384 &:= 4 \times F(8) \times \sqrt{(3 \times 8)^4} \\
 48395 &:= \left(\left((4 \times F(8 + F(3)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - (5) \right) \\
 48399 &:= \left(\left((4 \times F(8 + F(3)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 48426 &:= \left(\left((48^{\sqrt{4}}) + 2 \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 48486 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right) \times F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 48600 &:= \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 600 \\
 48664 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F((F(8) - (6))) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 48673 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) + 8 \times (6 \times F(7))^{F(3)} \\
 48674 &:= \sqrt{4} + 8 \times (6 \times F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 48679 &:= \left((4 \times F(F(8))) + \left((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 48769 &:= \left(F((F(4) \times 8)) + \left(7^{F(6)/F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 48796 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(8)) \right) \times \left((F(7)^{\sqrt{9}}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 48828 &:= \left(\sqrt{(4 + F(8))^8} - F(2) \right) / 8 \\
 48864 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4} + F(8)) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) + \left(F(F(6))^{F(4)} \right) \\
 48945 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(8)) \right) + \left(F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times - (5) \right) \\
 48946 &:= \left(\left(F((F(4) \times 8)) + F(9 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (6) \\
 48948 &:= \left(\left(- (4) + F(F(8) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + F((F(4) \times 8)) \\
 48949 &:= -F(4) + F(8 \times \sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) \\
 48964 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left(6^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 48966 &:= \left(F(4) \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48997 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (F(4)) + \left(F(F(8)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) - F(F(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$49096 := \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(0 - F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$49143 := \left(F \left(4 \right) \times \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^1 4 \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$49146 := \left(\left(F \left(4 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^1 4 \right) \right) - \left(6 \right) \right)$$

$$49149 := \left(- \left(F \left(4 \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^1 4 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$49176 := \left(F \left(4 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right)^7 \right) + F \left(6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$49179 := \left(F \left(4 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right)^7 \right) + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$49179 := \left(F \left(4 \right) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right)^7 \right) + 9 \right) \right)$$

$$49250 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - 2 \right) \times 50 \right)$$

$$49254 := \left(- \left(F \left(4 \right) \right) - \left(\left(9 \times F \left(F \left(F \left(F \left(2 \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) / - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$49259 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(9 \times F \left(F \left(F \left(F \left(2 \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$49264 := \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(9 \times \left(\left(- \left(2 \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$49269 := \left(F \left(4 \right) - \left(9 \times \left(\left(- \left(2 \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$49278 := \sqrt{4 \times 9} \times \left(2^{F(7)} + F(8) \right)$$

$$49282 := -\sqrt{4} + \left(-F(9) + 2^8 \right)^2$$

$$49283 := -F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(-F(9) + 2^8 \right)^{F(3)}$$

$$49284 := \left(\left(F(4) + F(9) \right) \times \left(-2 + 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$49285 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F(9) \right) \right)^2 \right) - F \left(F(8) \right) \right) \times - \left(5 \right) \right)$$

$$49436 := \sqrt{4} \times F(9) \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + 3^6 \right)$$

$$49450 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) \right) \right) \times 50 \right)$$

$$49569 := -F(4) + \sqrt{9^5} \times 6 \times F(9)$$

$$49596 := \left(4 + \sqrt{9^5} \times F(9) \right) \times 6$$

$$49650 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) + 6 \right) \times 50 \right)$$

$$49664 := \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + 96 \right) \times F(6)^{F(4)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49674 &:= \left((F(4) \times F(9)) \times \left(F(F(6)) - \left(F(F(7)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49729 &:= \left((-\sqrt{4} + F(9)) \times 7 - F(2) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 49734 &:= \left(\left(4 + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(3^4 \right) \right) \\
 49771 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\sqrt{9} \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \times 71 \right) \\
 49785 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F((9+7)) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 49795 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) - F((7+9)) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 49896 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + F(9) \right) \times F(8) \times 9 \times F(6) \\
 49965 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - F(9) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (5) \right) \\
 49982 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(9) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 49994 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((F(9) - F((F(9) - 9))) / - (F(4)) \right) \right) \\
 51529 &:= \left(-((5+1)) + F(F((5+2))) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 51984 &:= \left(- (5) + F \left(\left(F((1 \times 9)) - F(8) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 52439 &:= \left(\left((F(F((5+2))) - 4)^{F(3)} \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 52442 &:= \left(\left((F(F((5+2))) - 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 52443 &:= \left(\left((F(F((5+2))) - 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(3) \right) \\
 52444 &:= \left(\left((F(F((5+2))) - 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(4) \right) \\
 52489 &:= \left(\left(F((5+F(2))) \times \left(F(4)^8 \right) \right) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 52496 &:= \left(F((5+F(2))) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + \left(\sqrt{9}^{F(6)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 53134 &:= \left((F((F((5+3)) + 1)) \times 3) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 53139 &:= \left((F((F((5+3)) + 1)) + F(3)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 53298 &:= \left((53 + F(2)) \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 53361 &:= \left((F(F((5+F(3)))) - F(3))^{F(\sqrt{F(6)+1})} \right) \\
 53374 &:= \left(F((5+F(3))) + \left((-F(3) + F(F(7)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 53564 &:= \left((- (5) \times (F(F((F(3) + 5)))) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53679 &:= -F(5 \times 3) + F(6 + 7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 53696 &:= \left((-53) + F\left(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))\right) \right) \times F(6) \\
 53798 &:= \left(-5 + \left(-\left(F(F(3)) - F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(8) \right) \right) \\
 53799 &:= \left(-\left(5^{F(3)} \right) + \left(F(F(7)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 53819 &:= \left(-5 + \left(-\left(F(F(3)) - F(F((8-1))) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 53824 &:= \left(F(F(((5 \times 3) - 8))) - F(2) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 53829 &:= \left(5 + \left(-F(F(3)) + F(F((8 - F(2)))) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 54096 &:= \left(F(5 \times 4) - \sqrt{09} \right) \times F(6) \\
 54164 &:= \left(-\left(5^{F(4)} \right) + \left(F(F((1+6))) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 54264 &:= F((5+4) \times 2) \times F(\sqrt{64}) \\
 54268 &:= \left(\left(F(F((5 + \sqrt{4})) \right)^2 \right) - F\left(\sqrt{F(6) \times 8}\right) \right) \\
 54269 &:= 5 + F(4 \times 2) \times F(6 \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 54274 &:= \left(-5 \times F(4) + \left(F(F(2) \times F(7)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 54276 &:= \left(\left(F(F((5 + \sqrt{4})) \right)^2 \right) - (7 + 6) \right) \\
 54279 &:= \left(-5 \times \sqrt{4} + \left(F(F(2) \times F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 54281 &:= \left(\left(F(F((5 + \sqrt{4})) \right)^2 \right) - (8 \times 1) \right) \\
 54282 &:= \left(\left(F(F((5 + \sqrt{4})) \right)^2 \right) - (8 - F(2)) \right) \\
 54283 &:= F(5 \times \sqrt{4}) \times F(2 \times 8) - F(3) \\
 54284 &:= F(5 \times \sqrt{4}) \times F(2 \times 8) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 54285 &:= \left(F(5 \times \sqrt{4}) \times F(((F(2) \times F(8)) - 5)) \right) \\
 54286 &:= \left(\left(F(F((5 + \sqrt{4})) \right)^2 \right) - F\left(\sqrt{8 + F(6)}\right) \right) \\
 54289 &:= F(5 + 4^2 - 8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 54344 &:= \left(F(5 \times \sqrt{4}) + \left(F(F((3+4))) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54353 &:= \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times F \left(\left(F \left((3 + 5) \right) - F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54367 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)^{F(3)} - \left(- (6) \times F(7) \right) \right) \\
 54379 &:= \left(\left(F \left((5 \times F(4)) \right) + F \left(F(3) \right) \right) \times F \left(\left(F(7) - F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54459 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + \left(5 \times F(9) \right) \right) \\
 54465 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (54) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 54487 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\left(4 - \sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F(8) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F(7) \right) \right) \\
 54497 &:= \left(\left(5 \times F \left(\left(F(4) \times \sqrt{49} \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F(7) \right) \right) \\
 54517 &:= \left(- (5) - \left(F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- (1) - F \left(F(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54522 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left((5 + 2) \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 54527 &:= \left(5 + \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left((5 + 2) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(F(7) \right) \right) \\
 54565 &:= \left(- (5) - \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4^5} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times - (5) \right) \\
 54569 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{4^5} - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 54605 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{5^4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 05 \right) \\
 54615 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F \left(F(6) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left((1 + 5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54620 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) + (20) \right) \right) \\
 54626 &:= \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(F \left(F(6) \right) + F \left(\left(- (2) + F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54635 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F(6) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left((3 + 5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54636 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left((3 + F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 54644 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(F(4)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 54646 &:= \left(\left(5 \times F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(4 \times F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54654 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (5) \times F(4) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 54655 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (5) \times F(4) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) \\
 54660 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - (60) \right) \\
 54663 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + (6) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F(3) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$54664 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + (6) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$54665 := \left(\left(5 \times F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - (65) \right)$$

$$54666 := \left(\left(5 \times F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(6 \right) \times F \left(6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54669 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(9 \right) \right)$$

$$54670 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 0$$

$$54671 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 1$$

$$54672 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 2$$

$$54673 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 3$$

$$54674 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 4$$

$$54675 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 5$$

$$54676 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 6$$

$$54677 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 7$$

$$54678 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 8$$

$$54679 := 5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) + 9$$

$$54684 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\left(F \left(4 \right) + (6) \right) - F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$54690 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) + (9 + 0) \right) \right)$$

$$54691 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left((9 \times 1) \right) \right)$$

$$54693 := \left(\left(5 \times F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(9 \right) + 3 \right) \right)$$

$$54694 := \left(\left(5 \times F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - (9 \times 4) \right)$$

$$54695 := \left(\left(F \left(F \left((5 + F \left(4 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54697 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(4 - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54699 := \left(\left(5 \times F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(9 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$$

$$54714 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F \left(4 \right) - F \left(F \left((7 + 1) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$54727 := \left(\left(5 \times F \left(\left(F \left(4 \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{2 + 7} \right)$$

$$54728 := \left((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - \sqrt{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right)$$

$$54730 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 0$$

$$54731 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 1$$

$$54732 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 2$$

$$54733 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 3$$

$$54734 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 4$$

$$54735 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 5$$

$$54736 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 6$$

$$54737 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 7$$

$$54738 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 8$$

$$54739 := \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(7 \times 3) + 9$$

$$54740 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left((7 \times F \left((4 + 0) \right)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54741 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left((7 \times F \left(4 \right)) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$54742 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left((7 \times F \left(4 \right)) \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right)$$

$$54744 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left((7 \times F \left(4 \right)) \right) \right) \right) + 4 \right)$$

$$54746 := \left((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right)$$

$$54749 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54754 := \left(\left((5 + F((F(4) \times 7))) \times 5 \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$54755 := \left((5 + F((F(4) \times 7))) \times \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right)$$

$$54765 := \left(\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left((F \left(7 \right) + F \left(6 \right)) \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54769 := \left(\left(5 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left((F \left(7 \right) + F \left(6 \right)) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(9 \right) \right)$$

$$54779 := \left((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + \left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right)$$

$$54786 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times - (7) \right) - F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54789 := \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (7) \right) - F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(9 \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54820 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(8)) \right) - (20) \right) \right) \\
 54829 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) + (F((2+9))) \right) \\
 54845 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} + F(F(8)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 54853 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) - F(3) \right) \\
 54854 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 54855 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) \\
 54864 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(8)) \right) \right) + F((F(6) + (4))) \right) \\
 54865 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 54866 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) - \left(- (6) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 54867 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(8)) \right) \right) + (F(F(6)) \times 7) \right) \\
 54869 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(8)) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) + F(9) \right) \\
 54874 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times F(F(8)) \right) + F\left(\left(F(7) - F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54879 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times (4 - F(F(8))) \right) + \left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 54884 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) + F((8+4)) \right) \\
 54885 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 54887 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) + (F(8) \times 7) \right) \\
 54888 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(8)) \right) \right) - \left(- (8) \times F(8) \right) \right) \\
 54889 &:= \left(\left(5^4 \right) + \left(F(8) \times F\left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54890 &:= 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 0 \\
 54891 &:= 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 1 \\
 54892 &:= 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 2 \\
 54893 &:= 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 3 \\
 54896 &:= 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 4 \\
 54897 &:= 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$54898 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 6$$

$$54898 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 8$$

$$54899 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 7$$

$$54899 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) + F(9) \right) + 9$$

$$54925 := F\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 25$$

$$54963 := \left(\left(5 \times F\left(F\left(\sqrt{4\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \right) + F\left(F\left(F(6) - F(F(3))\right)\right) \right)$$

$$54965 := \left(\left(F\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right) + F(9) \right) + F\left(F(F(6))\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54979 := \left(F\left(F\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + F(F(7))\right) \right) - 9$$

$$54985 := \left(\left(54 - \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54988 := \left(F\left(F\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + F\left(-8 + F(8)\right)\right) \right)$$

$$54990 := \left(F\left(5 \times F(4)\right) + F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \times 90$$

$$54997 := \left(5 \times F\left(F\left(\sqrt{4\sqrt{9}}\right)\right) \right) - \left(-F(9) - F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$55447 := \left(\left(F\left(\left(5 + 5\right) + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 7$$

$$55454 := \left(5 + F\left(F\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times F\left(F\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right)$$

$$55895 := \left(-5 \times \left(-F\left(5 + 8\right) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} + 5\right)\right) \right) \right)$$

$$55896 := \left(55 + F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 6$$

$$55945 := \left(5 \times \left(F\left(F\left(5 + \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + \left(F(4)^5\right) \right) \right)$$

$$55984 := \left(\left(-5 \times F\left(5 \times \sqrt{9}\right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times -4$$

$$56169 := \left(F\left(5 + F(6)\right) + \sqrt{16} \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$56268 := \left(\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}\right) - F(2) \right) \times -6 \right) / -8 \right)$$

$$56642 := \left(\left(5 + F\left(-F(6) + F(F(6))\right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 2 \right)$$

$$56643 := \left(\left(5 + F\left(-F(6) + F(F(6))\right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - F(F(3)) \right)$$

$$56689 := \left(\left(-\left(\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}\right) + F\left(F(F(6))\right) \right) + \left(F\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 56778 &:= \left(\sqrt{5^{F(6)}} + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) + 8)) \right) \\
 56848 &:= \left(F(((5 - F(6)) + F(8))) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 56917 &:= \left((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left(\sqrt{9^{1 \times 7}} \right) \right) \\
 56935 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F(F((3 + 5))) \right) \right) \\
 56937 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) + (F((9 \times F(3))) \times - (7)) \right) \\
 56969 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) + F(9) \\
 57246 &:= \left((57 + F(2)) \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 57296 &:= \left(- (5) - F(7) \right) + \left(2 \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 57304 &:= (-5 + F(-7 + 30)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 57309 &:= -5 + F(-7 + 30) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 57314 &:= F(-5 + 7 \times (3 + 1)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 57324 &:= (5 + F(7 \times 3 + 2)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 57384 &:= \left(((5 \times 7) + F((F(3) + F(8)))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 57494 &:= \left((F((5 + F(7))) / 4) \times F \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 57547 &:= \left(\left(F(((5 + F(7)) + (5))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 57779 &:= \left(- (5) - \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(- (F(7)) - F(F(7)) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 57972 &:= 5 + 7^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(7)^2 \\
 58375 &:= 5 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{3^{7+5}} \right) \\
 58564 &:= \sqrt{-5 + F(8)} \times (5 + 6)^4 \\
 58647 &:= F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) + 6 - 4^7 \\
 58674 &:= \left((F((5 + 8)) + F(F(6))) \times \left(F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 58699 &:= \left((5 \times F(F(8))) - \left(\left(F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times - (9) \right) \right) \\
 58746 &:= \left(\left(5 - \left((F(8) \times F(F(7))) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 58775 &:= -\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(7) + 5)) \\
 58926 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F((-2) + F(F(6))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58944 &:= -5 \times F(8) + 9^{\sqrt{4+F(4)}} \\
 59044 &:= -5 + 9^{\sqrt{04+F(4)}} \\
 59287 &:= \left(\left(5 + \left(\sqrt{9^{2+8}} \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 59298 &:= ((5 + F(9)) \times F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} - F(8) \\
 59316 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 - F(\sqrt{16}) \\
 59346 &:= (5 + F(9))^3 + \sqrt{F(4)^6} \\
 59447 &:= (5 + F(9))^{F(4)} + \sqrt{4^7} \\
 59566 &:= 5 + 9^5 + \sqrt{F(6)^6} \\
 59643 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) \times F(F((4+3))) \right) \right) \\
 59648 &:= F(-5 + \sqrt{9} \times 6) \times \sqrt{4^8} \\
 59653 &:= \left(5 - \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) \right) \times F(F((5+F(3)))) \right) \right) \\
 59663 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) - F(3) \right) \\
 59664 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 59665 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F(6) + F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 59686 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) + \left(F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 59762 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) - \left(F(F(F(6))) / - (2) \right) \\
 59845 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - \left(F(F(8)) + (4^5) \right) \right) \\
 59898 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \\
 59997 &:= \left(F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - \left((F(9) \times F(9)) \times F(7) \right) \right) \\
 61194 &:= \left((61 + 1) \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 61485 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - 1 \right) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 61495 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + 1 \right) \right) + \left(4 \times F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 61498 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + 1 \right) \times F(4) \right) + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 61599 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(-((1-5))) + F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 61696 &:= \left(\left(F(6) + F(F((1+6))) \right) \right) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 61745 &:= \left(F(F((6+1))) \times \left(F(F(7)) + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \\
 62496 &:= \left(62 \times \left(F\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 62749 &:= \left(\left(F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \times \left(F(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(9) \right) \\
 62874 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left((F(2) - F(F(8))) - \left(F(F(7)) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 63169 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(6)^{F(3)} \right) \times F(16) \right) + F\left(F(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 63368 &:= \left(\left(F((F(6) + 3))^{F(3)} \right) \times \sqrt{F(6) \times 8} \right) \\
 63369 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((F(6) + 3))^{F(3)} \right) \times F(6) \right) + F\left(F(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) \\
 63374 &:= \left(\left((F(6) \times F((3 \times 3))) \times F(F(7)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 63379 &:= \left(\left((F(6) \times F((3 \times 3))) \times F(F(7)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 63384 &:= F(6) \times \left(F(3) + F(3+8)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 63469 &:= \left(F((6 \times 3)) + \left(F\left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 63479 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(3) + (4))) - \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 63496 &:= (63 \times 4)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(6) \\
 63497 &:= (63 \times 4)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 7 \\
 63524 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \left(F((F(3) \times 5))^2 \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 63654 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(- (F(3)) - (F(F(6)) \times - (5)) \right) \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 63888 &:= \left(6 \times \left((F(F(3)) + F(8))^{F(\sqrt{8+8})} \right) \right) \\
 63894 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((F(F(3)) + F(8))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 63896 &:= \left(F(6) - \left(\left((F(F(3)) + F(8))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times - (6) \right) \right) \\
 63948 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(F((3+9)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 63966 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((F(6) + F(3)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 63979 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(6)) - \left(\left((3 \times 9) + F(7) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 63984 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(- (F(3)) + \left(- \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(8) \right) \right)^{F(4)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 63987 &:= \left(\left(\left((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 8 \right) - F(7) \right) \\
 63995 &:= (F(6) - F(3) + F(9))^{\sqrt{9}} - 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 63999 &:= \left(\left(\left((F(6) - F(3)) + F(9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 64155 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(15) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 64266 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{4} \right) - F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 64276 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4} + (27)) \right) \right) / - (F(6)) \\
 64279 &:= \left((6 \times (F(F((4 \times 2)))) - F(F(7))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 64366 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - \left(F(F(3)) - (6^6) \right) \right) \\
 64488 &:= \left(\left(\left(6^4 + F \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 64516 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}} \right) \\
 64587 &:= F(6 \times F(4)) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} - F(7) \\
 64595 &:= \left(\left(F((6 \times F(4))) \times \left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 64597 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times - (5) \right) - F(9) \right) \times - (F(7)) \right) \\
 64599 &:= \left(\left(F((6 \times F(4))) \times \left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 64638 &:= 6 \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(6)^3 \right) \times F(8) \\
 64654 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - \left(F(6)^5 \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 64668 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 64674 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(F(6))) \right) - \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 64675 &:= \left(\left(F(6) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times (F(7) \times 5) \right) \\
 64679 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^{F(4)} \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \times 7 \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 64683 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - (6 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \right) \\
 64686 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (6) \right) \\
 64689 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(6) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(8 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64744 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times - (F(4)) \right) - \left(F(F(7)) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 64746 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^{F(4)} \right) \times 7 \right) - \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} \right) \\
 64749 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^4 \right) - F(F(7)) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$64769 := \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((\sqrt{4} - F(F(7))) \times F \left(F \left((F(F(6)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$64779 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - (7) \right) \times 7 \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$64788 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + (7 \times F(8)) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$64793 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7 \right) - \sqrt{F(9)^{F(3)}} \right) \right)$$

$$64794 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7 \right) - F(9) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$64795 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7 \right) - \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$64812 := \left(6 \times \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) - (F(12)) \right) \right)$$

$$64827 := F \left(\sqrt{64} \right) \times F(8)^2 \times 7$$

$$64829 := \left(\left((F(F(6))^4) + (8 - 2) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$64834 := \left(F(6) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(F(8)^3 + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$64843 := F(6) \times \sqrt{4} + F(8)^4 / 3$$

$$64847 := 6 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(8)^{F(4)} \right) \times 7$$

$$64848 := \left(F(6) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times F(8)^{F(4)} + F(8)$$

$$64849 := \left(F(F(6)) + \left(\left((F(4) + (F(8)^4)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$64869 := \left(\left((F(F(6))^4) - (F(8) \times - (6)) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$64878 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left((\sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times - (7) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$64883 := \left(F(6) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(8 + F(8)^3 \right)$$

$$64896 := \left(\left(\left(F \left((F(6) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right)) \right) \times 8 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$64897 := \left(6 + 4 + F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 7$$

$$64967 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + (F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$64971 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(6))^4) / \sqrt{9} \right) + F((F(7) - 1)) \right) \right)$$

$$64974 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times - ((F(9) \times F(7))) \right) / - (F(4)) \right) \right)$$

$$65066 := \left(\left(F(6) \times F \left(\sqrt{50 \times F(6)} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$$

$$65234 := \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left((F(F((5+2)))^{F(3)}) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65436 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - (5 \times \sqrt{4^3}) \right) \times 6 \right) \\ 65447 &:= F(6)^5 \times \sqrt{4} - F(4+7) \\ 65448 &:= -F(6+5) + F(\sqrt{4}) + 4^8 \\ 65463 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(F(6)^5 \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (3) \right) \\ 65464 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6)) + (5)) - F(\sqrt{F(4)^6}) \right) / - (F(4)) \right) \\ 65467 &:= \left(\left((F(F(F(6))) + (5 - F(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \times 6 - F(F(7)) \right) \\ 65468 &:= F(6)^5 \times \sqrt{4} - 68 \\ 65469 &:= -65 + 4^{F(6)} - F(\sqrt{9}) \\ 65484 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left((F((5+4)) - F(F(8))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\ 65494 &:= \left(F(6)^5 - F(\sqrt{4\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 65496 &:= F(6)^5 \times \sqrt{4} - F(9) - 6 \\ 65497 &:= F(6)^5 \times \sqrt{4} - \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \\ 65499 &:= F(6)^5 \times \sqrt{4} - F(9) - \sqrt{9} \\ 65524 &:= \left(F(6)^5 - 5 \right) \times 2 - \sqrt{4} \\ 65526 &:= \left(F(6)^5 - 5 \right) \times \sqrt{-2+6} \\ 65529 &:= \left(F(6)^5 - 5 \right) \times 2 + \sqrt{9} \\ 65534 &:= F(6)^5 \times (5-3) - \sqrt{4} \\ 65539 &:= F(6)^5 \times (5-3) + \sqrt{9} \\ 65542 &:= \left(F(6)^5 + \sqrt{5+4} \right) \times 2 \\ 65543 &:= \left(F(6)^5 + 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} - 3 \\ 65544 &:= \left(F(6)^{\sqrt{5 \times 5}} + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 65549 &:= \left(F(6)^5 + 5 \right) \times \sqrt{4} + \sqrt{9} \\ 65566 &:= \left((6 \times 5) + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6))^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \\ 65583 &:= F(F(6)) \times \left(5 \times \sqrt{5^8} - F(3) \right) \\ 65594 &:= \left(F(6)^5 - 5 + F(9) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 65596 &:= \left(- (F(6)) + \left(\left((5^5) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65597 &:= \left(\left(- (F(F(6))) \times \left(- \left((5^5) \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 7 \right) \\
 65598 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left((5 + 5) + \sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 65624 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \left(5^{6-F(2)} \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 65635 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) + F(3) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 65640 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(- (5) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - F(\sqrt{4+0}) \right) \right) \\
 65643 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - (5) \right) \times 6 \right) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 65644 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - (5) \right) \times 6 \right) - \left(4 - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 65645 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) + 4 \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 65647 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - (5) \right) \times 6 \right) + \left(F(\sqrt{4})^{F(F(7))} \right) \right) \\
 65648 &:= \left(\left(F(6) \times - (5) \right) + \left(- (6) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 65656 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{-5 + F(F(6))} \right) \times 5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 65661 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - (5) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times \sqrt{F(6) + 1} \right) \\
 65664 &:= \left(F(6)^5 + F(6) \times F(6) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 65665 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) + F(6) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 65669 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times 5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - \left(F(F(6)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 65674 &:= \left(\left(6 \times F(F((56/7))) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 65676 &:= 6 \times F \left(-5 + \sqrt{676} \right) \\
 65679 &:= F(6) - 5 + 6 \times F \left(7 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 65680 &:= \left(\sqrt{F(F(6)) - 5} + (6 \times F(F((8+0))) \right) \\
 65684 &:= \left(F(6) + \left(\left(- (5) + F(6) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 65685 &:= \left(\sqrt{F(F(6)) - 5} + \left((6 \times F(F(8))) + (5) \right) \right) \\
 65689 &:= \left((6 + 5) + \left((6 \times F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 65691 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + (5) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times \sqrt{9 \times 1} \right) \\
 65692 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + (5) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(2) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$65696 := \left(((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) \times 6) - (F(\sqrt{9}) + F(6)) \right)$$

$$65698 := \left((F(6) \times 5) + \left(- (6) \times (\sqrt{9} - F(F(8))) \right) \right)$$

$$65699 := \left(((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) \times 6) - \left(9 - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$$

$$65736 := \left((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times \sqrt{7-3})) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65739 := \left((F(F(6)) - (F(F((-5) + F(7)))) \times - (F(3))) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$65754 := \left(6 \times (F(F((-5) + F(7))) + F((5 + \sqrt{4}))) \right)$$

$$65784 := \left(- (6) \times \left(((-5) - F(7)) - F(F(8)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$65793 := \left((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times (F(7)^{\sqrt{9}}))) \times 3 \right)$$

$$65796 := \left((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times \sqrt{7+9})) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65835 := F(F(6)) \times (\sqrt{5^8} + F(3)) \times 5$$

$$65856 := \left(F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5} \right) \times 6$$

$$74758 := -F(F(7)) + F(-4 + F(7)) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$65879 := \left(\left(\sqrt{F(F(6)) - 5^8} \right) + \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$65928 := \left(- (6) \times \left((F((5 + \sqrt{9})) \times - (2)) - F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$65946 := \left((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times 9)) \times - \left((\sqrt{4} - F(6)) \right) \right)$$

$$65976 := \left((F(F(F(6))) + (-5) \times (\sqrt{9} - F(7))) \right) \times 6$$

$$65987 := \left((6 \times (F((5 + F(\sqrt{9}))) + F(F(8)))) + F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$66036 := \left((F(F(F(6))) + (60)) \times \sqrt{36} \right)$$

$$66048 := \sqrt{F(6)^6} + 04^8$$

$$66189 := \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (1 + (8^{\sqrt{9}})) \right)$$

$$66274 := \left((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 2)) + F((F(7) + \sqrt{4})) \right)$$

$$66374 := \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + \left((3 \times F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$$

$$66399 := \left((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3)))) + \left((9^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)$$

$$66426 := \left(6 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{(F(4) + 2)^6} \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66468 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times - (6) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 66492 &:= \left(6 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(9) \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 66494 &:= \left((6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + (4 \times F(9))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 66564 &:= ((F(6) \times 6 - 5) \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 66568 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times - \left(\sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 66569 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(6^5 \right) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \\
 66664 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + \left(F((F(6) + F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 66669 &:= \left(((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + 6) + F\left(\left(F(6) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \right) \\
 66684 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left((-F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 66692 &:= \sqrt{(F(6) + F(6))^{F(6)} + F(9)^2} \\
 66696 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left((F(6) \times F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 66744 &:= \left(6 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F((7 + 4)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 66784 &:= \left((F(6) + F(6)) \times \left(- (7) + F\left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 66893 &:= \left(\left((F(6) + F(6)) \times F\left(\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \right) - 3 \right) \\
 66894 &:= \left(\left((F(6) + F(6)) \times F\left(\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 66899 &:= \left(\left((F(6) + F(6)) \times F\left(\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 66912 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) + 1 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 66928 &:= \left((F(6) + F(6)) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F((-2) + F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 66944 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) + F(4) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 66948 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(- \left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (4) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \\
 66966 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) - 6 \right) \\
 66969 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 66984 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- \left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 66997 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) / 9 \right) \times F(7) \right) \right) \\
 67184 &:= (6 + 7) \times F(18) \times \sqrt{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$67468 := - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(- (7) \times \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{F(6)} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$67590 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 0$$

$$67591 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 1$$

$$67592 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 2$$

$$67593 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 3$$

$$67594 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 4$$

$$67595 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 5$$

$$67596 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6$$

$$67597 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 7$$

$$67598 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 8$$

$$67599 := F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) + 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 9$$

$$67686 := \left(\left(- \left(\left(F(6) - \sqrt{76} \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$67769 := \left((F(F(F(6))) \times F(7)) - \left((F(7) \times F(F(6)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right)$$

$$67798 := \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$67847 := \left(\left((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) + \left(F(F(8)) / - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times - (F(7)) \right)$$

$$67849 := \left(\left((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times \left(F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$67914 := \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times 14 \right) \right)$$

$$67926 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F \left(\left(7 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - 2 \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$67967 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) + F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$67968 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times - ((6 \times 8)) \right) \right)$$

$$68239 := - \left(\left((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) + \left(- (F(23)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$68247 := \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\left(F((F(8) + 2)) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(7) \right) \right)$$

$$68254 := \left((- (6) - F((F(8) - F(2)))) + F(\sqrt{54}) \right)$$

$$68274 := \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((F((F(8) + 2)) + (7)) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$68467 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times F \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right)$$

$$68471 := \left(\left(6 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68472 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 68473 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(- (\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) + F(F(3)) \right) \\
 68474 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(- (\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 68546 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 8) \times 5 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 68672 &:= \sqrt{(6 + F(F(8)))} \times F(6) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)) \\
 68921 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6)) + (F(8))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right)^{2+1} \\
 68929 &:= F(6) + (8 + F(9) - F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 68973 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(F(F(F(8) / \sqrt{9})) \right) \times (7^3) \right) \right) \\
 69169 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) - 1 - F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 69192 &:= F(6) \times \left(91 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^2 \\
 69277 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(-((F(2) - F(7)))) \right) \times F(7) \right) \\
 69360 &:= F(6 + \sqrt{9})^{F(3)} \times 60 \\
 69489 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) + (F(8)) \right) \times - (\sqrt{9}) \\
 69546 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left((F(\sqrt{54}) - (6)) \right) \right) \\
 69549 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left((F(\sqrt{54}) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 69551 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + ((F((5 \times 5)) - 1)) \right) \\
 69552 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + ((F((5 \times 5)) \times F(2))) \right) \\
 69553 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - (- (F((5 \times 5))) - F(F(3))) \right) \\
 69554 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left((F((5 \times 5)) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 69579 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) + \left(- (\sqrt{9}) \times F((5 + F(7))) \right) \right) \times - (9) \right) \\
 69647 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - \left(6 \times (4^7) \right) \right) \\
 69649 &:= \left((F(6) + 9) \times \left((F(6)^4) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 69664 &:= \left(F(6) + F(9) \times \sqrt{F(6)^6} \right) \times 4 \\
 69679 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (7) - F(9) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69693 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) - F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 3 \\
 69694 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) - F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} - \sqrt{4} \\
 69698 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F(6) \right) \times F(9) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 69699 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) - F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + \sqrt{9} \\
 69768 &:= F(6 \times \sqrt{9}) \times (F(7) + 6 + 8) \\
 69769 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - \left(7^6 \right) \right) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 69789 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + \left((F(9) - 7) \times F(F(8) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 69792 &:= \left(-6 + \sqrt{9^7} \right) \times (F(9) - 2) \\
 69839 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - \left((F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 69867 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(6)) - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^8 \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \times F(7) \right) \right) \\
 69869 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 69878 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) - \left((F(F(8)) \times 7) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 69879 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^8 \right) \times F(7) \right) \right) - 9 \right) \\
 69881 &:= \left(\left(F(6) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + F(F(8)) \right) \right) - F(F(8) + 1) \right) \\
 69888 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^8 \right) \times (-8) + F(8) \right) \right) \\
 69896 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times - (F(6)) \right) \\
 69959 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(- \left((F(9) - 9^5) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 69965 &:= F(6) + 9 \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + 6^5 \right) \\
 69966 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + (F(9) \times F(F(6))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 69974 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) - 7 \right) \times F(4) \right) \right) \\
 69992 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(9^{\sqrt{9}+2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 69993 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - F(3) \right) \right) \\
 69994 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 69995 &:= F(6 \times \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{9}) + 9^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69996 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - \left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 69997 &:= 6\sqrt{F(9)-9} \times 9 + F(7) \\
 69998 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 70844 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left((7 \times 0) + 8 \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 71084 &:= \left(- (F(7)) \times \left((10 - F(F(8))) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 71149 &:= \left((F(7) \times F(F((1+1) \times 4))) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 71289 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F \left(\left((1^2) + 8 \right) \right) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 71442 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((F(7)+1)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) / 2 \right) \\
 71824 &:= \left((F(F(7)) + (F((1+8)) + F(2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 71997 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{1 \times 9}} \right) - F(9) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 71998 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) + F((1+9)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \\
 72384 &:= F(7 \times 2) \times 3 \times \sqrt{8^4} \\
 72936 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) + 2)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) \right) \\
 73389 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times - (3)) + \left((F(3) \times F(8))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 73395 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times F(F((3+3)))) \times \left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 73674 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(- (F(3)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 73696 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(7^{F(3)} \right) \right) + \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 73719 &:= \left(\sqrt{(7-3)^{F(7)} - 1} \right) \times 9 \\
 73728 &:= \sqrt{(7-3)^{F(7)}} \times (F(2) + 8) \\
 73749 &:= \left(7 + F(3)^{F(7)} \times F(4) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 73969 &:= -F(7) - F(3) + (F(9) \times F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 73972 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7))^{F(3)} \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9^{7+2}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 73976 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(- (F(F(3))) - F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 73979 &:= \left(\left(7 + \left(3^9 \right) \right) + \left(F(F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 73982 &:= -\sqrt{7-3} + (F(9) \times 8)^2 \\
 73983 &:= -F(\sqrt{7-3}) + (F(9) \times 8)^{F(3)} \\
 73989 &:= 7 - F(3) + (F(9) \times 8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 73997 &:= \left((F(F(7)) + 39)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + (F(7)) \right) \\
 74296 &:= F\left((7 - \sqrt{4})^2 \right) - \sqrt{96} \\
 74426 &:= \left((7 + 4) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F((-F(2)) + F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 74439 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}))^{\sqrt{4}} + ((3^9)) \right) \right) \\
 74448 &:= \left((7 + 4) \times \left(F(4) + F\left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74458 &:= -7 \times F(4)^4 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} \right) \\
 74480 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times 4) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 80 \\
 74487 &:= \left(\left(F\left((F(7) + \sqrt{4}) \right) / \sqrt{4} - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (7) \right) \\
 74493 &:= (7^4 + \sqrt{4}) \times (F(9) - 3) \\
 74529 &:= \left(F(7) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) \right)^2 \times 9 \\
 74538 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) + F(5^{F(3)}) \right) - (F(8)) \right) \\
 74554 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) - (5) + F(\sqrt{5^4}) \right) \right) \\
 74557 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(7)) + (\sqrt{4} - F((5 \times 5))) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 74559 &:= \left(F(F(7)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) + F(5^{5-\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 74564 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) + (5) + F((F(F(6)) + 4)) \right) \right) \\
 74584 &:= F(-7 + \sqrt{4^5}) - F(8)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 74644 &:= \left(- \left(F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) + F((F(F(6)) + 4)) \right) - 4 \\
 74646 &:= \left((7 + 4) \times \left(F\left((F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4})) \right) + (F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 74648 &:= - \left(F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - F(((F(6) - 4) + F(8))) \right) \\
 74649 &:= \left(- \left(F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) + F((F(F(6)) + 4)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 74654 &:= -F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) + 6 + F(\sqrt{5^4})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74656 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F(6) \right) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) \right) \\
 74659 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(\left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) / 5 \right) \times F(9) \right) \\
 74665 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4^6} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 74673 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(7) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times F(7) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \\
 74676 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) + (7) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 74694 &:= F(7)^{F(4)} \times F(6 + \sqrt{9}) - 4 \\
 74699 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7)^{F(4)} \right) \times F(6 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 74739 &:= 7 + \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(7)^3 \right) \times F(9) \\
 74762 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(7) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 74763 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F(7) \times F(F(6)) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \\
 74764 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(\left(F(7) \times F(F(6)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 74774 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(7^{F(4)} \right) \\
 74784 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (7) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) + F((F(8) + (4))) \\
 74788 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(7) \times F(8)) \right) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \\
 74789 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(4) \right) - F \left(\left((7 + F(8)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74793 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F \left((F(7) + (9 + 3)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74794 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4} \right) - F \left((F(7) + 9) + F(4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74796 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - 4 \right) - F \left(\left(7 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74798 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right) - 9 \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 74799 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} - F(F(7)) \right) \right) + F((F(9) - 9)) \right) \\
 74844 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(\left(F(8) - F(4) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 74848 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + 8 \right) \right) \right) + F((4 + F(8))) \\
 74856 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{F(8) - 5 + F(F(6))} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74864 &:= \left((-7) \times (\sqrt{4} + F(8)) \right) + F((F(F(6)) + 4)) \\
 74865 &:= \left(7 \times \left(-(\sqrt{4^8}) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + (5) \right) \\
 74867 &:= \left(-F(7) \times \left((\sqrt{4} + (F(8) \times F(F(6)))) \times -F(7) \right) \right) \\
 74874 &:= \left((-7) + F((4 + F(8))) \right) - F\left((F(7) - F(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 74897 &:= F(-7 + 4 \times 8) - F(\sqrt{9})^7 \\
 74925 &:= -F(7) - F(4)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(25) \\
 74929 &:= -7 + F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) \times 29 \\
 74945 &:= F(7) \times \left(-F(4) + F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \\
 74946 &:= \left((F(F(7)) + 4) / -(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F((4 + F(F(6)))) \\
 74948 &:= \left(-(74) - \sqrt{9} \right) + F((4 + F(8))) \\
 74953 &:= \left((7 + F(\sqrt{4})) \times -9 \right) + F(5^{F(3)}) \\
 74954 &:= -74 + \sqrt{9} + F(\sqrt{5^4}) \\
 74955 &:= -7 \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + 9 \right) + F(5 \times 5) \\
 74976 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{7^4}) + F(\sqrt{9+7} + F(F(6))) \right) \\
 74977 &:= \left((F((7 \times F(4))) - F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7)) \right) \times 7 \\
 74978 &:= \left(-F(7) - (\sqrt{49} \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(8)))) \right) \\
 74984 &:= \left((-7) - F(F(4) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) + F((F(8) + (4))) \\
 74989 &:= \left((-7) \times (F((4 + 9)) - F(F(8))) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 74993 &:= \left(F(7)^4 + F(9 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) / 3 \\
 74998 &:= \left((-7) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F((F(9) - 9)) - F(8) \\
 74999 &:= \left(-\left(F(7) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F((F(9) - \sqrt{9 \times 9})) \\
 75029 &:= 7 + F(5^{02}) - \sqrt{9} \\
 75034 &:= \left(7 + F(5^{F(03)}) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 75039 &:= \left(F(7) + F(5^{F(03)}) \right) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 75046 &:= F(7) + F(\sqrt{5^{04}}) + F(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75245 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(5^2) \right) - F(\sqrt{4} + 5) \right) \\
 75248 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(F(5^2) - \sqrt{4} - 8 \right) \right) \\
 75249 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(F(5^2) - (F(4) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 75253 &:= \left((F(F(7)) - 5) + F(\sqrt{25}^{F(3)}) \right) \\
 75254 &:= \left((F(F(7)) - (5 - F(2))) + F(\sqrt{5^4}) \right) \\
 75259 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(5^2) \right) + F(5 - \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 75261 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(5^2) \right) + \sqrt{F(6) + 1} \right) \\
 75264 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(F(5^2) + F(6) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 75266 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(5^2) \right) + F(\sqrt{6 \times 6}) \right) \\
 75269 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(F(5^2) + F(6) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 75297 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(F(5^2) + (\sqrt{9} \times F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 75546 &:= \left(\left(F((F(7) + 5)) \times \sqrt{5^4} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 75645 &:= \left(\left((F((7 + 5)) - F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 75725 &:= \left(F(F(7)) \times \left((5 \times F(7)) \times \sqrt{25} \right) \right) \\
 75867 &:= \left(F(7) \times F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + F(F(F(6)))) \right) / F(7) \\
 75868 &:= F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} + F(-6 + F(8))) \\
 75889 &:= \left((-7) \times ((5 \times F(8)) - F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 75957 &:= \left((-F(F(7))) + F(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}) \right) + (5 \times F(F(7))) \\
 75999 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(5 + \sqrt{9})) - F(9 + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 76146 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(F((F(6) + 1)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 76174 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{(1 + 7)^4} \right) \right) \\
 76195 &:= \left(7 \times \left(-(61) + F(F(\sqrt{9} + 5)) \right) \right) \\
 76245 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(F(2 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76247 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(-(2) + F\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7\right) \right) \right) \\
 76249 &:= \left(\left(-(F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + \left(2^{4^{F(\sqrt{9})}} \right) \right) \\
 76278 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{76} + F(2) \right) \right) - \left(-(7) \times F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 76279 &:= \left((7 \times F(F((6+2)))) - \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 76364 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(\left(F(3)^{F(6)} \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 76366 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \sqrt{F(3)^{F(6)+F(6)}} \right) \\
 76369 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(\left(F(3)^{F(6)} \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 76374 &:= \left(-(F(F(7))) + \left(\left((F(F(F(6))) - F(3) \right) \times 7 - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76384 &:= \left(-(7) \times \left((F((6+3)) - F(F(8))) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 76389 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(7)) - \left((F((6+F(3))) \times F(F(8))) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 76396 &:= \left(-(F(F(7))) + \left(\left((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3))) / -(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times -(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 76397 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(- \left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76423 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F\left(\sqrt{4} + (23)\right) \right) \\
 76425 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times 6) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(25) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76426 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + (26) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76433 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(F(4)^{\sqrt{3 \times 3}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 76434 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(F(4)^3 \right) \right) \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 76453 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5)\right)^{F(3)}\right) \right) \right) \\
 76459 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (5 \times F(9)) \right) \\
 76462 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 76463 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) + F(3) \right) \\
 76469 &:= \left(\left(-(F(7)) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{F(6)} \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 76471 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - F((F(7) - 1)) \right) \\
 76474 &:= \left(\left(-(7) \times \left(F(F(6)) - F((F(4) \times 7)) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76476 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (7 \times F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 76479 &:= \left(\left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F\left(F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 76482 &:= \left(F((F(7) + F(6))) + \left(\sqrt{4}^{8 \times 2} \right) \right) \\
 76484 &:= \left(F((F(7) + F(6))) + \left((4^8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 76493 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - (\sqrt{4} \times 9) \right) \right) - 3 \right) \\
 76494 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(\sqrt{4^9} / 4 \right) \right) \\
 76495 &:= \left((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) + \left(4^{\sqrt{9}+5} \right) \right) \\
 76497 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(- (F(4)) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 76499 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(F\left((\sqrt{4} + 9) \right) + F(9) \right) \right) \\
 76529 &:= \left(\left((- (F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (5 + 2) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 76536 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(5 + \sqrt{3^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \\
 76545 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((5 + F(\sqrt{4})) + (5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76546 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(- (5) + \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \\
 76547 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(5 \times (\sqrt{4} + F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76549 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(5 + (\sqrt{4} \times F(9)) \right) \right) \\
 76552 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{(5+5)^2} \right) \right) \\
 76554 &:= \left((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5+5))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 76557 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(\sqrt{5 \times 5} \times F(7) \right) \right) \\
 76564 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(56 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 76569 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(56 - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 76573 &:= \left((- (7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{7-3} \right) \right) \\
 76579 &:= \left(- (7) + \left((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 7 - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 76582 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \sqrt{(5 \times 8)^2} \right) \\
 76589 &:= \left(((F(7) - (6)) \times (- (5) + F(F(8)))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76590 &:= \left((7 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) + \sqrt{9+0} \right) \\76591 &:= \left((7 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) + (\sqrt{9} + 1) \right) \\76592 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left((5 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 2 \right) \right) \\76593 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \sqrt{(-5 + F(9))^{F(3)}} \right) \\76595 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \left(- \left((6^5) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times - (5) \right) \\76596 &:= \left(\left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5) \right) - F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (6) \right) \right) \right) \\76609 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F \left(\left(F(F(6)) / \sqrt{09} \right) \right) \right) \\76618 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \sqrt{F(6) + 1 \times 8} \right) \\76619 &:= \left((7 \times F((F(6) + F((6+1)))) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\76624 &:= \left(\left((F(7) - (6)) \times F(F((6+2))) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\76633 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left(F(6) + \sqrt{3 \times 3} \right) \right) \\76646 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left((6/\sqrt{4}) \times F(6) \right) \right) \\76649 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left((6/\sqrt{4}) \times 9 \right) \right) \\76650 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{F(F(6)) - 5 + 0} \right) \right) \\76652 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \sqrt{(6 \times 5)^2} \right) \\76654 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left((6 \times 5) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\76661 &:= \left((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6)) - \sqrt{F(6) + 1} \right) \\76668 &:= \left((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6)) + \sqrt{F(6) + 8} \right) \\76681 &:= \left((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(6))) + \sqrt{8+1} \right) \\76684 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left((F(6) \times 8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\76686 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(\sqrt{6 \times 6}) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) + F(6) \right) \\76694 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left((6 \times \sqrt{9}) \times 4 \right) \right) \\76696 &:= \left((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(6))) + (\sqrt{9} \times 6) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76698 &:= \left(76 + \left(\left(F(F(6)) / \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(F(8))\right)\right) \\
 76699 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(6 / \sqrt{9}\right) + 9\right)\right)\right) \\
 76715 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7) + F(F(F(6)))\right) \times 7\right) + \left(\sqrt{-1+5}\right)\right) \\
 76716 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7) + F(F(F(6)))\right) \times 7\right) + F\left(\sqrt{16}\right)\right) \\
 76719 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(7) + 1\right)\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \\
 76729 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(6 \times 7\right) + 2\right)\right)^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) \\
 76739 &:= \left(\left(7 \times F(F(F(6)))\right) + \left(\left(F(7) \times 3\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 76745 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7) + F(F(F(6)))\right) \times 7\right) + \sqrt{4^5}\right) \\
 76764 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(7)\right) \times \left(F(6) - F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 76779 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 \times F(F(F(6)))\right) + F(7)\right) + F\left(\left(F(7) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 76791 &:= \left(\left(7 \times F(F(F(6)))\right) + \left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{9}-1}\right)\right)\right) \\
 76792 &:= \left(\left(7 \times F(F(F(6)))\right) + \left(\left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) + F(2)\right)\right) \\
 76793 &:= \left(\left(7 \times F(F(F(6)))\right) + \left(\left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) + F(3)\right)\right) \\
 76794 &:= \left(\left(7 \times F(F(F(6)))\right) + \left(\left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) + F(4)\right)\right) \\
 76796 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(7) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) - F(6)\right) \\
 76844 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(8 \times 4\right)\right)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) \\
 76847 &:= \left(-F(7) + \left(\left(6 \times F(8)\right) \times F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 76848 &:= \left(-7 + \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times F\left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) - F(F(8))\right)\right) \\
 76849 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - 6\right) + \left(F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{49}\right)\right) \\
 76854 &:= \left(\left(7 \times F(F(F(6)))\right) + \left(F((8+5)) - F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \\
 76879 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(F(6))\right) + \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times 7\right) + \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \\
 76895 &:= 7 \times \left(-F(6) + F(8)\right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 5 \\
 76945 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times 6\right) + F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \times F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5\right)\right)\right) \\
 76949 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + F(9)\right)\right) + \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 9\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 76956 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7) \times F\left(\left(F(6) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) - 5\right) \times 6\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76958 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(- (6) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (5) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 76962 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 76967 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(\left(- (F(6)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (7) \right) \right) \\
 76972 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + (7^2) \right) \\
 76979 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (7^{F(\sqrt{9})}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76983 &:= \left(\left((F(7) \times 6) \times F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8) \right) - 3 \right) \\
 76984 &:= \left(\left((F(7) \times 6) \times F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 76986 &:= F(7) \times F(6/\sqrt{9} \times 8) \times 6 \\
 76989 &:= \left(\left((F(7) \times 6) \times F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 76993 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(9 + F(F(3))) \right) \right) \\
 76996 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) \times (\sqrt{9} + F(6))) \right) \\
 76997 &:= \left(\left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7) \right) \\
 76998 &:= \left(\left(F(7) \times F(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) - \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 76999 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(9 + \sqrt{F(9) - 9}) \right) \\
 77098 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(- (70) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 77448 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left((F(F(7)) + F(4)) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 77679 &:= \left(7 \times \left((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \\
 77744 &:= \left((7 - F(F(7))) \times \left(- \left((7^{F(4)}) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 77798 &:= \left(- (7) + \left(7 \times \left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 77834 &:= \left(- (7) + \left(- \left((F(F(7)) - (8^3)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 77847 &:= \left((F(F(7)) - (F(7) \times - (8))) \times \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77957 &:= \left(\left(- ((F(7) \times F(7))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + (5^7) \right) \\
 77973 &:= \left((77 + F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F(7) + 3) \right) \\
 77987 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (F(7)) \times \left(- (F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 7 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78246 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) \times - (8)) + F(2) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times F(F(6)) \\
 78254 &:= \left((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times (2 + 5) \right) + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \\
 78289 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times (F(8) \times (2 \times 8))) + F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \\
 78296 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) \times (F(8) \times 2)) + F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 78357 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F\left(\sqrt{8/F(3)}\right) \right) + \left(5^7 \right) \right) \\
 78428 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + \left(2^8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78478 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(8))) - \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - F(F(7)) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 78487 &:= \left(\left((7 \times F(F(8))) + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \right) + (8 \times F(F(7))) \right) \\
 78499 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \left(- \left((8 - 4) \times \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78624 &:= F(7) \times F(8) \times F(6 \times 2) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 78798 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - F(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78819 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left(F((8 - 1))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 78876 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left((F(8) - F(F(8))) - \left(\sqrt{7^6} \right) \right) \right) \\
 78894 &:= (-F(7) + F(8 + 8)) \times \sqrt{9^4} \\
 78934 &:= \left((7 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left(F(9)^{F(3)} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 78957 &:= F(7) \times 8^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 5^7 \\
 79092 &:= F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times (F(09) + 2) \\
 79233 &:= 7^{\sqrt{9} + F(2)} \times 33 \\
 79454 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(\left(F(7) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + (5) \right) / 4 \right) \right) \\
 79478 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(F(9) \times \left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - (F(7)) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 79492 &:= \left(F(7) + F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times F(9) \times 2 \\
 79494 &:= -F(7) + \left(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{4}} + F(9) \right)^{F(4)} \\
 79524 &:= \left((F(7) + F(9)) \times (5 + F(2)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 79576 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F\left(\sqrt{9 - 5}\right) \right) \times \sqrt{7^6} \right) \\
 79646 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F((F(6) + (4))) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 79669 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (F((7+9))) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times F(6) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right. \\
 79688 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((F(F(6)) \times - (F(8))) - F(F(8))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79693 &:= \left(\left(- (F(7)) + \left(9 \times F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) / F(3) \right) \\
 79695 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times (69 \times 5) \right) \\
 79696 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (F((7+9))) + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(6) \right) \right) \\
 79775 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) - F((7+5)) \right) \\
 79794 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times \left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 79850 &:= \left(F \left(\left(\left(- (7) + \sqrt{9} \right) + F(8) \right) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 79855 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(8) \right) + (F((5 \times 5))) \right) \\
 79876 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 7 \right) - F(6) \right) \\
 79877 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 7 \right) - (7) \right) \\
 79884 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times (F(8) / F(4)) \right) \\
 79898 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F \left(F \left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - (F(8)) \right) \\
 79919 &:= 7^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(\sqrt{9} + 1 + 9) \\
 79944 &:= F(7+9) \times \sqrt{9^4} - F(4) \\
 79949 &:= F(7+9) \times \sqrt{9^4} + F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 80934 &:= \left(\left(80 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F \left(\left(F(3)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 81179 &:= \left(F \left((F(8) - 1) \times (- (1) + F(7)) \right) - F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 81648 &:= \sqrt{8+1} \times 6^4 \times F(8) \\
 81793 &:= ((F(8) + 1) \times F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 3 \\
 81794 &:= ((F(8) + 1) \times F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} - \sqrt{4} \\
 81799 &:= ((F(8) + 1) \times F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + \sqrt{9} \\
 81976 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(\sqrt{1 \times 9} \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 82095 &:= \left((F(F(8)) / - (2)) \times \left(\sqrt{09} \times - (5) \right) \right) \\
 82568 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{\sqrt{25^{F(6)}}} \right) \times 8 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 82942 &:= (8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{\sqrt{4}} - 2 \\
 82943 &:= \left(\left((8 \times (2 + F(9)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - F(F(3)) \right) \\
 82946 &:= \left(\left(F(F((8 - F(2))))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(6))\right)\right) \right) \\
 82979 &:= \left(-F(8) + 2^9 \right) \times F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 83343 &:= \left(F(8)^3 \times 3 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 \\
 83488 &:= \left(\left(-\left(8^3\right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 8 \\
 83496 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(3 - \sqrt{4^9}\right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 83598 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) / F(3) \right) + \left(5^{-\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - 8 \right)} \right) \right) \\
 83619 &:= \left(\left(F((F(8) - F(3))) \times (F(F(6)) - 1) \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 83620 &:= F\left(-8 + \sqrt{3^6}\right) \times 20 \\
 83664 &:= \left(83 \times \left(F(F(6)) + F\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\
 83696 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(F(3)) + F(F(6)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 83764 &:= \left(\left(F((F(8) - F(F(3)))) \times F(7) \right) - F\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 83957 &:= (F(8) - 3)^{\sqrt{9}} + 5^7 \\
 83959 &:= F(8)^3 \times 9 + F(5 \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 84368 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 8 \\
 84374 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \times 3 \right) - F((F(7) + (4))) \\
 84474 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 84568 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(4) \times \sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \\
 84664 &:= \left(- (8) - \left(- (F(4)) \times \left(F(6) \times F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 84679 &:= \left(F((8 \times F(4))) - \left(F(F(F(6))) \times 7 \right) / - \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 84777 &:= \left(- (F(8)) \times \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7)\right) \right) \times - (7) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 84872 &:= 8 \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - 8 \times F(7) \right)^2 \\
 84882 &:= F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times (88 - 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84936 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(F \left(\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) / - (3) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 84968 &:= \left(- (F((F(8) - F(4)))) - \left(\left(- (F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (8) \right) \right) \\
 84985 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (F(9) \times F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 84986 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F((F(8) - F(4))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (F(F(8)) \times - (F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 85664 &:= \left(8 \times \left((- (5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F \left(F \left(\left(F(6) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 85683 &:= (8 + 5) \sqrt{F(6)+8} \times 3 \\
 85792 &:= \left(F(8) + (5 \times 7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 2 \\
 85827 &:= F(F(8)) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) - F(-F(2) + F(7)) \\
 85867 &:= F(F(8)) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) - F(6) \times F(7) \\
 85869 &:= \left(F((F(8) - (5))) \times \left((F(8) + F(6)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 85893 &:= \left(\left((F(8) + (5)) - F \left(\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \times - (3) \right) \\
 85937 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) - F((F(3) + (7))) \right) \\
 85939 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) + ((F(3) - F(9))) \right) \\
 85944 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) - \left(F(4)^{F(4)} \right) \right) \\
 85946 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) + F((4 + F(F(6)))) \right) \\
 85948 &:= \left(\left(- (F(8)) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) + \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 85956 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (5 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) \right) \\
 85962 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) - (F(6) + F(2)) \right) \\
 85963 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(F \left(\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(6) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 85964 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) - (5)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F((F(F(6)) + 4)) \right) \\
 85958 &:= F(F(8)) - F \left(5 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \\
 85969 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F \left(\left(5^{F(9-6)} \right) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 85976 &:= \left((F(F(8)) + (5)) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{9+7} + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 85979 &:= \left(\left((- (8) + F((5 + 9))) \times F(F(7)) \right) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 85983 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{F(8) - 5} \right) - F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times - (3) \\
 85984 &:= \left((8 + 5) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times F \left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 85986 &:= \left(\left(F(8) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) + (F(F(8)) - (6)) \right) \\
 85989 &:= \left(\left(F(8) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 85992 &:= \left(\left(F(8) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) + F(F((9 - F(2)))) \right) \\
 85997 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(7) \right) \right) \\
 85998 &:= \left((8 - 5) \times \left(9 + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86016 &:= F(8) \times F(6)^{\sqrt{016}} \\
 86348 &:= \left(F((8 + 6)) - \left(- (3) \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86483 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^6} - \left(- (F(4)) \times F \left(\left(F(8) + F(3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86564 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 86568 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + \left(\sqrt{5^6} \times - (8) \right) \right) \\
 86569 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 86839 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - \left((8 + F(F(3)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 86849 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(8^6 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F(8) - (4) \right) \right) \right) / - \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 86869 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - \left(F \left(\left(F(8) - F(6) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 86872 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{87^2} \right) \right) \\
 86874 &:= \left((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (87))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 86896 &:= \left(\left((86 - F(F(8))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times - (F(6)) \right) \\
 86936 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - \sqrt{3^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86954 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right) \right) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 86958 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(8) + (6) \right) \right) - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5 \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 86959 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86974 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 86975 &:= \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times F(9) - F(7) \right) \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$86976 := \left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (76) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$86984 := \left(8 \times \left((F(6) \times - (9)) + F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$$

$$86989 := \left((F(F(8)) + (F(6) \times - (9))) \times 8 - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$86995 := \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times F(9) - 9 \right) \times 5$$

$$87263 := \left(- (F(F(8))) - \left(F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{(7+2)^6}} \right) / (-F(3)) \right) \right)$$

$$87294 := \left((8 \times (F(F((7+F(2)))) - F(9))) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$87299 := \left((8 \times (F(F((7+F(2)))) - F(9))) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$87374 := \left(((F((F(8) - (7))) - F(3)) \times F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$87379 := \left(\left(\left(8^{7-F(F(3))} \right) - (7) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$87384 := 8 \times \left(F(7 \times 3) - F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$87454 := \left((((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times 4) - (5)) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$87462 := \left(\left((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times (\sqrt{4} + (6)) \right) - 2 \right)$$

$$87463 := \left(\left((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times (\sqrt{4} + (6)) \right) - F(F(3)) \right)$$

$$87466 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(6) \right) - (6) \right)$$

$$87469 := \left(\left(\left((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(6) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$87472 := \left(\left((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (7 + F(2)) \right)$$

$$87479 := \left((8 \times F((7 \times F(4)))) - F \left((F(7) - F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right)$$

$$87488 := \left((F(F(8)) - (F(7) - F(4))) \times \sqrt{8 \times 8} \right)$$

$$87494 := \left((((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times 4) - 9) \times \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$87498 := \left(F(F(8)) + \left(- (7) \times \left((F(\sqrt{4}) + 9) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$87499 := \left((8 \times (F((7 \times F(4)))) - 9) + \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$87514 := \left(((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times F((5+1))) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$87546 := \left(\left((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(6)) \right)$$

$$87549 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87562 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - \sqrt{6^2} \right) \\
 87569 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + F\left(\left(6/\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \\
 87574 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + (7) \right) - F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 87579 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + (F(7)) \right) - F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) \\
 87584 &:= 8 \times \left(F(-7 \times (5 - 8)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 87589 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + \left(- (7) \times \left((- (5) - F(F(8))) + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87591 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F(F((F(7) - (5)))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 87592 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F((F(7) - (5)))) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times F(2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87593 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F(F((F(7) - (5)))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F(F(3)) \right) \\
 87594 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F(F((F(7) - (5)))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 87599 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + \left(F(9) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 87614 &:= \left((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) - 1)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 87619 &:= \left((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) - 1)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 87622 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) - \sqrt{2+2} \right) \\
 87626 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + \sqrt{-2+6} \right) \\
 87627 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + \sqrt{2+7} \right) \\
 87628 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + \sqrt{2 \times 8} \right) \\
 87629 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + \left(2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 87634 &:= \left((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 \\
 87640 &:= 8 \times \left(7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 0 \\
 87641 &:= 8 \times \left(7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 1 \\
 87642 &:= 8 \times \left(7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 2 \\
 87643 &:= 8 \times \left(7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 3 \\
 87644 &:= 8 \times \left(7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 4 \\
 87646 &:= 8 \times \left(7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$87646 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4}) + 8$$

$$87647 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4}) + 6$$

$$87647 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4}) + 9$$

$$87649 := 8 \times (7 + F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4}) + 7$$

$$87654 := F(8) \times (-7 + F(-6 + \sqrt{5^4}))$$

$$87659 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - F((5 + F(\sqrt{9}))))$$

$$87664 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - \sqrt{64})$$

$$87666 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - \sqrt{6 \times 6})$$

$$87668 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) - \sqrt{F(6) + 8})$$

$$87679 := (((F(F(8)) + (7)) \times F(6)) + F((F(7) - \sqrt{9})))$$

$$87688 := ((F(F(8)) + (7 + F(6))) \times \sqrt{8 \times 8})$$

$$87694 := ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + 9)) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$87696 := (((F(8) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(6))) \times (\sqrt{9} \times 6))$$

$$87697 := (((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) \times (6 + F(\sqrt{9}))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$87699 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times F(6)) + (9 \times \sqrt{9}))$$

$$87759 := F(8) \times (F(7 + 7 + 5) - F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$87784 := (8 \times (((F(7) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$87798 := (((F(F(8)) \times 7) + F(F(7))) - \sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)))$$

$$87799 := ((F(8) \times F((-7) + (F(7) \times F(\sqrt{9})))) - F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$87839 := ((F((F(8) - (7))) \times F(F((F(8) / 3)))) - F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$87894 := ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(8))) + F(9))) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$87899 := ((8 \times ((7 + F(F(8))) + F(9))) + \sqrt{9})$$

$$87924 := (F(8) + F(7)) \times (F(9 \times 2) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$87948 := F(8) \times (7 + F(9 + \sqrt{4} + 8))$$

$$87953 := \left(8 + \left(F(7) \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times (5 \times F(3)) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$87960 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 0$$

$$87961 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 1$$

$$87962 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 2$$

$$87963 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 3$$

$$87964 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 4$$

$$87965 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 5$$

$$87966 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 6$$

$$87967 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 7$$

$$87968 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 8$$

$$87969 := \left(F(F(8)) + 7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) + 9$$

$$87984 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) + F(4) \right)$$

$$87985 := \left(F(8) + F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 8 \right) \times 5$$

$$88179 := \left(\left((8 \times F(F(8))) + 1 \right) + F \left(\left(F(7) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$88279 := - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(8) \times (2 + F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right)$$

$$88284 := \left(- (F(8)) \times \left(- \left((F(8) + 2) \right) - F \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$88296 := \left((8 \times F(F(8))) - \left(F(2) - \sqrt{96} \right) \right)$$

$$88299 := \left((8 \times F(F(8))) + \left(2 + \left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$88347 := \left(F(8) \times \left(F \left((F(8) - F(3)) \right) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(7) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$88384 := \left(8 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(3 \times F \left(\left(8 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$88435 := \left(\left(\left(- (F(8)) + F \left(\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) - 3 \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$88445 := \left(\left(\left(- (F(8)) + F \left(\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$88448 := \left(8 \times \left(\left(F \left(\left(8 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$88450 := \left(-F(8) + F \left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times 5 + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88451 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 1 \\
 88452 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 2 \\
 88453 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 3 \\
 88454 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 4 \\
 88455 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 5 \\
 88456 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 6 \\
 88457 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 7 \\
 88458 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 8 \\
 88459 &:= \left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \times 5 + 9 \\
 \\
 88494 &:= \left(F(8) \times \left(\left(F\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4}\right) + F(9)\right) - F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \\
 88495 &:= \left(\left(\left(-F(8) + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right)\right) + 9\right) \times 5 \\
 88515 &:= \left(\left(-8 + F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{5-1})\right)\right)\right) \times 5 \\
 88545 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(8) + F(F(8-5))\right)\right) - \sqrt{4}\right) \times 5 \\
 88554 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(8) + F(F(8-5))\right)\right) \times 5\right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 88563 &:= \left(\sqrt{8 \times 8} + (5 \times F(F(F(6)) + F(F(3))))\right) \\
 88564 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{5^6}\right)\right)\right) - 4 \\
 88568 &:= \left(8 \times F(F(8))\right) - \left(\sqrt{5^6} \times -8\right) \\
 88569 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{5^6}\right)\right)\right) + F\left(F(\sqrt{9})\right) \\
 88584 &:= \left(8 + F(8)\right) + \left(5 \times F\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})\right)\right) \\
 88699 &:= \left(-F(8) + \left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + F\left(9 + \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 88719 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(8)) + F(F(7) - 1)\right)\right) - F\left(F(\sqrt{9})\right) \\
 88724 &:= \left(8 \times F(F(8))\right) + \left(\left(F((7+2)^{\sqrt{4}})\right)\right) \\
 88848 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{4})\right) \times 8\right)\right) \\
 88864 &:= \left(F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{8 \times 8}\right) + \left(6^4\right) \\
 88896 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (-8 \times F(8))\right) - F(\sqrt{9})\right) \times F(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88899 &:= \left((8 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left((8 + \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 88972 &:= \left(\left(F((-8) + F(8)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times F((7 \times 2)) \right) \\
 88992 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((9 + 2)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89167 &:= \left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^{F(\sqrt{16})} \times F(7) \\
 89275 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(- \left(F(2) - F(7) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \\
 89296 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left((\sqrt{9} \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 89346 &:= \left(\left((8 \times (F(9) + F(F(3))))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 89349 &:= \left(-8 + (F(9) - 3)^{F(4)} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 89394 &:= F(8) + (F(9) - 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(4) \\
 89448 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(F((9 + 4) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 89456 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left((\sqrt{4} + (5)) \right) \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 89457 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(- \left(F(4)^5 \right) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 89528 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{9^5} + 2 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 89536 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{9^5} + 3 \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 89542 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) + \left(F \left((4^2) \right) \right) \\
 89568 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{5^6} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 89616 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) \right) \times F((1 \times 6)) \right) \\
 89635 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + (6^3) \right) \times 5 \\
 89647 &:= \left(- \left(F(F(8)) \right) - \left(- (9) \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89648 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) + 4 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 89649 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F \left(F(6) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 89656 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) + (5) \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 89715 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(F(7)) - 1 \right) \right) \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$89725 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(F(7)) + F(2) \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$89735 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(8) + F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(F(7)) + 3 \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$89747 := F(8) + F(9) \times 7 \times F(\sqrt{4} \times 7)$$

$$89775 := \left(-F(8) \times \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \times -7 \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$89946 := \left(F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(9) - F(4) \right) \times 6$$

$$89962 := F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(9) \times 6 - 2$$

$$89963 := \left(\left(\left(F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times \left(F(9) \times 6 \right) \right) - F(F(3)) \right)$$

$$91916 := \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F(19) \right) \right) \times \left(1 + F(F(6)) \right) \right)$$

$$91938 := - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(19) \right) \right) \times \left(F(F(3)) + F(8) \right) \right)$$

$$91948 := \left(-F(9) + \left(F(19) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$91948 := -F(9) + F(19) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8) \right)$$

$$91979 := -\sqrt{9} + F(19) \times \left(F(7) + 9 \right)$$

$$91981 := - \left(\left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(F(19) \times \left(F(8) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$91983 := \left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(-F(19) \times \left(-F(8) - F(F(3)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$91984 := F(\sqrt{9}) + F(19) \times \left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$92448 := F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(F(24) - F(4 + 8) \right)$$

$$92449 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(9 + F \left(\left(2 \times 4 \right) \right) \right) \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) / 9 \right)$$

$$92477 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(F(24) - F(7) \right) \right) - F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$92487 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(F(24) - 8 \right) \right) - F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$92497 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(F(24) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - F(F(7)) \right)$$

$$92568 := \left(\left(9 - F(2) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{5^{F(6)}} + F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$92644 := -92 + F(6 \times 4) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$92694 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(9 - F(2) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$$

$$92696 := \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(\left(F(2) - F(F(6)) \right) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$92698 := \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(\left(2 - F(F(6)) \right) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$92699 := \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(- (2) \times F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + F(9) \right) \right)$$

$$92724 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 2 \times (-7 + F(24))$$

$$92728 := \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F \left((2 \times F(7)) - 2 \right) \right) - 8 \right)$$

$$92732 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times (F(27 - 3) - 2)$$

$$92733 := -\sqrt{9} + 2 \times F(7 \times 3 + 3)$$

$$92734 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F(27 - 3) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$92736 := \left(\sqrt{9} - F(2) \right) \times F((7 - 3) \times 6)$$

$$92737 := \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + (2 \times F(((F(7) - F(3)) + F(7)))) \right)$$

$$92738 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(F(2)^{F(7)} + F(3 \times 8) \right)$$

$$92739 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F(27 - 3) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$92742 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F(((F(2) + (7)) \times F(4))) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$92744 := \left(F(((9 + 2) + F(7))) + 4 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$92746 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times (-2 + 7 + F(4 \times 6))$$

$$92748 := \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(-((F(2) - (7))) + F((F(4) \times 8)) \right) \right)$$

$$92754 := (9 + F(2 \times (7 + 5))) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$92763 := \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - (2 \times (-F(7) - F((F(6) \times 3)))) \right)$$

$$92764 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 2 \times (F(7) + F(6 \times 4))$$

$$92778 := \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times (F(((- (2) + F(7)) + F(7))) + F(8)) \right)$$

$$92796 := \left(F(9) - \left(2 \times \left(-F(7) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$92846 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times (F(2 + 8) + F(4 \times 6))$$

$$92889 := \left(\left(\sqrt{\left(\sqrt{9} + 2 \right)^8} - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right)$$

$$92969 := \left(F(F((9 - 2))) + \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$93059 := F(9) + 305^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$93314 := \left((F(9) + F(3))^3 + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$93366 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(3^3 + 6^6 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 93593 &:= \left(\left(F(9)^3 \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \\
 93634 &:= (9 \times F(3+6))^{F(3)} - \sqrt{4} \\
 93636 &:= F(9)^{F(3)} \times \sqrt{(6-3)^{F(6)}} \\
 93639 &:= (9 \times F(3+6))^{F(3)} + \sqrt{9} \\
 93696 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F(3) \right)^6 - 9 \right) \times 6 \\
 93892 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(3 \times 8) + F(9)^2 \\
 94249 &:= \left(F(9) \times F(4)^2 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 94365 &:= F(9+4) \times \sqrt{3^{F(6)}} \times 5 \\
 94459 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + 4 \right) \times 59 \right) \\
 94464 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - F(4) \right) \\
 94467 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) + F((F(6) + F(7))) \right) \\
 94469 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 94488 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right)^4 \right) + F(8) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 94647 &:= \left(\left(- (9) - \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 94668 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times -((6+8)) \right) \\
 94676 &:= \left(- (F(9)) - \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \times (7 - F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 94699 &:= \left(- (9) + F \left((4 + F(F(6))) \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \\
 94716 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times (F(4) + (7 \times F((-1) + F(F(6)))) \right) \\
 94718 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times (4 + (7 \times F((-1) + F(8)))) \right) \\
 94792 &:= F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (-7 + F(9+2)) \\
 94874 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(8)) \right) \times F(7) \right) / F(4) \right) \right) \\
 95489 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - (F(F(8)) \times 9) \right) \right) \\
 95779 &:= \left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(\left(F \left((5 + F(7)) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times - (F(9)) \right) \right) \\
 96163 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6)) \right) \times F((16+3)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 96327 &:= 9 \times F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{3^{2 \times 7}} \\
 96399 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - F(F(-((F(3) - 9))) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 96417 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - 1 \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 96426 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \right) \right) \\
 96435 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \right) - F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \right) \right) \\
 96466 &:= \left(\left(9 \times F(F(F(6))) \right) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{F(6)} \right) \times F(6) \right) \right) \\
 96498 &:= \left(- (9) \times \left(F \left(F \left(\left(F(6) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) - (9 + F(F(8))) \right) \right) \\
 96646 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6)) \right) \times \left(F(F(6)) + F \left(\left(- (\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 96687 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(- (\sqrt{6^6}) + F(F(8)) \right) + (F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 96696 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \left(F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) - F(6) \right) \right) \\
 96759 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((F(7) \times 5) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 96899 &:= - \left(\left(F((9 + F(6))) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 96916 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 96918 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - \left(- (1) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 96926 &:= \left((9 + F(F(F(6)))) - \left(- (\sqrt{9}) \times F((2 + F(F(6)))) \right) \right) \\
 96993 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(F \left(\left(9 - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 96995 &:= \left(\left(F(9) + F \left(\left(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \times 95 \right) \\
 97242 &:= \left(\left(- (\sqrt{9}) - \left(F((7 + F(2)))^4 \right) \right) / - (2) \right) \\
 97334 &:= (-9 + F(7 + 3))^3 - \sqrt{4} \\
 97336 &:= (-9 + F(7 + 3))^{\sqrt{3+6}} \\
 97339 &:= (-9 + F(7 + 3))^3 + \sqrt{9} \\
 97344 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(3) \times 4 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 97383 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{9}) \times \left(F((7 \times F(3))) + \left(F(F(8)) \times - (3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97389 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^7 \right) - 3 \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) \\
 97417 &:= \left(9 \times 7 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(17)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97464 &:= F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^7 + 46^{F(4)} \\
 97605 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) - \left(F\left(6\right)^{05}\right)\right)\right) \\
 97815 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) - \left(F\left(F\left(8\right)\right) \times F\left(-\left(\left(1-5\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 97818 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) \times \left(F\left(8\right) - 1\right)\right)\right) \times -\left(F\left(8\right)\right) \\
 97820 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) \times F\left(8\right)\right)\right) \times -\left(20\right) \\
 97824 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(8\right)\right) + F\left(2\right)\right) \times F\left(4\right)\right)\right) \\
 97833 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(8\right)\right) + F\left(3\right)\right) \times 3\right)\right) \\
 97836 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) + \left(F\left(F\left(8\right)\right) \times -\left(3\right)\right)\right)\right) + F\left(F\left(6\right)\right) \\
 97845 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + \left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) \times -\left(84\right)\right)\right) \times -\left(5\right) \\
 97848 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(7 + F\left(F\left(8\right)\right)\right) - \sqrt{F\left(4\right)^8}\right)\right) \\
 97849 &:= \left(F\left(9\right) - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) - \left(F\left(F\left(8\right)\right) \times F\left(4\right)\right)\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) \\
 97861 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) \times -\left(F\left(8\right)\right)\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(6\right)\right) - 1\right)\right) \\
 97862 &:= \left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) \times -\left(F\left(8\right)\right)\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(6\right)\right) - F\left(2\right)\right)\right) \\
 97863 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) \times -\left(F\left(8\right)\right)\right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(6\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(3\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 97869 &:= -\sqrt{9} \times F\left(F\left(7\right)\right) + \left(F\left(F\left(8\right)\right) + 6\right) \times 9 \\
 97920 &:= \left(\left(F\left(9\right) \times F\left(\left(F\left(7\right) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \times 20 \\
 97938 &:= \left(9 \times \left(-\left(\sqrt{\left(7+9\right)^3}\right) + F\left(F\left(8\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 97956 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(-\left(7\right) - F\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times 5\right)\right)\right) + F\left(F\left(F\left(6\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 97969 &:= \left(F\left(9\right) + 7 + F\left(9\right) \times F\left(6\right)\right)^{F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)} \\
 97973 &:= \left(\left(\left(F\left(\left(F\left(9\right) - \left(7\right)\right)\right) / F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(7\right)\right)\right) - 3 \\
 97974 &:= \left(\left(\left(F\left(\left(F\left(9\right) - \left(7\right)\right)\right) / F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(7\right)\right)\right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 97976 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(F\left(9\right) - \left(7\right)\right)\right) / F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - \left(F\left(\left(7+6\right)\right)\right) \\
 97979 &:= \left(\left(\left(F\left(\left(F\left(9\right) - \left(7\right)\right)\right) / F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(7\right)\right)\right) + \sqrt{9} \\
 98209 &:= \left(F\left(\left(9 \times F\left(\left(8/2\right)\right)\right)\right) / F\left(\sqrt{09}\right)\right) \\
 98265 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times \left(F\left(\left(8 - F\left(2\right)\right)\right) - \left(F\left(6\right)^5\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98272 &:= \sqrt{9} \times F(8) + F(27) / 2 \\
 98274 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(2))) - (F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 98279 &:= \left((((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(2)) - F(F(7))) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98296 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2+\sqrt{9}} - F(6) \\
 98298 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left((F(2) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 98299 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 2)) - F\left(F\left(9 - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \right) \\
 98304 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8^{F(3)+F(04)} \\
 98324 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F((3 \times 2)))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 98349 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((F(F(8)) \times 3) - F\left(F(\sqrt{4} + 9)\right) \right) \right) \\
 98366 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \sqrt{F(3) \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6)} \right) \\
 98367 &:= \sqrt{9} \times \left(F(8) + F(3)^{F(6)+7} \right) \\
 98374 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(F(8)) \right) + \left((3 + F(7))^4 \right) \right) \\
 98389 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left(-((3 - 8))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 98394 &:= \left(\left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(8))) \times - (3) \right) - F(9) \right) \times F(4) \right) \\
 98395 &:= \left(\sqrt{F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8 + 3^9} \right) \times 5 \\
 98397 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9} + 8) - F(3) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(7) \\
 98399 &:= \left(\left((-9) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \left(3 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - F(9) \\
 98406 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times 06 \right) \right) \right) \\
 98425 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^8} \times F(4) + 2 \right) \times 5 \\
 98427 &:= \left(\left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \sqrt{4} \right) - F((-2) + F(7)) \right) \\
 98434 &:= \left(\left((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left((3^4) \right) \right) \\
 98438 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times 38 \right) \right) \\
 98439 &:= \left(\left((-9) + F(F(8)) \right) \times F(4) + F(3) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 98442 &:= \left(\left((-9) + F(F(8)) \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times \left(F(4)^2 \right) \\
 98444 &:= \left(-F(9) + \left((F(F(8)) - 4) \times \left(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}98445 &:= (\sqrt{9^8} + \sqrt{4}) \times F(4) \times 5 \\98446 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 + \sqrt{4^6}) \\98447 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{4} + (4)))) - (F(7))) \\98451 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times ((F(F(8)) \times F(4)) - F(F((5+1)))) \\98452 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{4} + (5)))) + F(2)) \\98456 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{4} + (56)) \\98457 &:= (((-\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8))) \times -(F(4))) - (57) \\98458 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - ((\sqrt{4} + (5)) \times 8) \\98460 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((\sqrt{4} - F((6+0)))))) \\98461 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((\sqrt{4} - F(6)))))) + 1 \\98468 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) + ((\sqrt{4} - ((6 \times 8)))) \\98479 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - ((\sqrt{4} \times F(7)) + 9) \\98480 &:= (-F(9)) - ((-8) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times F(F((8+0))) \\98482 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - \sqrt{(4 \times 8)^2} \\98484 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - ((\sqrt{4} + 8) \times F(4)) \\98486 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{4} \times (8+6)) \\98487 &:= ((\sqrt{9} - F(F(8))) \times (-((4-8)) - F(7))) \\98488 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{4} \times (-8) + F(8)) \\98489 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - ((\sqrt{4} \times 8) + 9) \\98490 &:= (\sqrt{9} + ((F(F(8)) - F(4)) \times (9+0))) \\98491 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{4} + F((9-1))) \\98493 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{49} \times 3) \\98495 &:= (F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8 + F(4)^9) \times 5 \\98496 &:= ((F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(8))) \times (F(4) \times -(9-6))) \\98498 &:= (9 \times F(F(8))) - ((\sqrt{4^{\sqrt{9}}}) + 8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98499 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left(-((4-9)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\ 98501 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(\sqrt{50-1}) \right) \\ 98504 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left(5 \times \sqrt{04} \right) \right) \\ 98516 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \sqrt{5-1^6} \right) \\ 98524 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \sqrt{5^2 \times 4} \right) \\ 98529 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \sqrt{5^2 \times 9} \right) \\ 98532 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \left((5 + F(3)) + 2 \right) \right) \\ 98534 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left((5 \times F(3)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\ 98536 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(- (5) + \sqrt{3^6} \right) \right) \\ 98539 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(5 \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\ 98541 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - \left((5+4) \times 1 \right) \right) \\ 98542 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - \left((5+4) \right) \right) + F(2) \right) \\ 98544 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(4) \right) \right) \\ 98545 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) + (5) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (5) \right) \\ 98546 &:= \left(\left((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5) \right) + \sqrt{F(4)^6} \right) \\ 98549 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(5 \times \sqrt{49} \right) \right) \\ 98559 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\sqrt{5 \times 5 \times 9} \right) \right) \\ 98561 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + \left(\left(F(F(8)) + (5) \right) \times \left(F(6) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\ 98562 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(F(F(8)) + (5) \right) \times \left(F(6) + F(2) \right) \right) \right) \\ 98579 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + \sqrt{(5 \times F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})}} \\ 98589 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} \times 9} \\ 98593 &:= \left(F(9) + \left(\left(F(F(8)) + (5) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{F(3)}} \right) \right) \right) \\ 98594 &:= \left(F(9) + \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) + (5) \right) \times 9 \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\ 98596 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(5 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - F(6) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98597 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (5))) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^7 \right) \right) \\
 98599 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left((5 \times F(9)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98622 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{(6 \times 2)^2} \right) \right) \\
 98624 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(F((F(6) + 2)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 98639 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left((F(6) - 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\
 98646 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 98647 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 98648 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) - F(\sqrt{4} + 8) \right) \\
 98649 &:= \left(((9 + F(F(8))) + (6)) \times (F(4) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98658 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times F(F(6)) \right) \times 58 \right) \\
 98659 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 9) \right) \\
 98662 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \sqrt{(6 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 2} \right) \\
 98667 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{6^6}) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 98669 &:= \left(- (F(9)) + \left((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times (6 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98674 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(6))) + \left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 98679 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) + F\left(F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 98684 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left((F(6) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 98695 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{9}) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 9) - (5)) \right) \\
 98696 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 9) - F(6)) \right) \\
 98697 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 9) - (7)) \right) \\
 98698 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 9) - 8) \right) \\
 98699 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) - \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98724 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left((7 \times 2)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 98738 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98739 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 98743 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (\sqrt{4} + F(3)) \right) \\
 98744 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4 \times 4}) \right) \\
 98745 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4+5}) \right) \\
 98747 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + F\left(\left(F(7) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - F(7)\right) \right) \\
 98749 &:= \left(\left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98752 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + \sqrt{5^2} \right) \\
 98754 &:= \left(((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 98756 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7)))) + (\sqrt{5^6}) \right) \\
 98769 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (((F(F(8)) + (7)) + F(F(6))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98774 &:= \left((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(7)))) + F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 98776 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times (((-F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)) - F(6)) \right) \\
 98792 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times ((-F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F((9-2))) \right) \\
 98819 &:= \left((((-F(9)) - F(F(8))) \times -(8+1)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 98829 &:= \left(((F(9) + F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{8/2})) \times 9 \right) \\
 98843 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 98874 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F(F(8)) + (8 \times (7 - \sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 98889 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{9}) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) + F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98894 &:= \left((((F(9) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 98937 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{F(9)^{F(3)}} \right) + F(7) \right) \right) \\
 98946 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(\sqrt{4} \times 6) \right) \right) \\
 98973 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (7^{F(3)}) \right) \right) \\
 98975 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(7)) \right) - (5) \right) \right) \\
 98977 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 98979 &:= \left(\left((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98982 &:= \left(\left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) + \left(F(8)^2 \right) \right) \\
 98989 &:= \left(\left((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(9) \right) + \left(F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 98991 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F((9+1)) \right) \right) \\
 98998 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(8) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + (9 \times F(F(8))) \right) \\
 98999 &:= \left(\left(\left((\sqrt{9} - F(F(8))) \times - (9) \right) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 99224 &:= (9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^2 - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 99243 &:= \left(9 \times \left((9^2) + F(F(\sqrt{4^3})) \right) \right) \\
 99246 &:= \left(\left((9 \times (F(9) + F(2)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \\
 99288 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((F((F(9)/2)) - F(8)) \times F(8) \right) \right) \\
 99369 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + 93 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99498 &:= \left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) + F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4\right)\right) \right) + (9 \times F(F(8))) \right) \\
 99646 &:= \left(\left(\left((9 - \sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right)^{F(4)} \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 99666 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((9 + \sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times F(6) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 99669 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9\right)\right) \times F(F(6)) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 9) \right) \\
 99765 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F\left(-\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(7)\right)\right)\right) + (F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \right) \right) \\
 99767 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{F(7)-F(6)} \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 99783 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F\left(-\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(7)\right)\right)\right) + (F(F(8)) - 3) \right) \right) \\
 99812 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(12))) \right) \\
 99819 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((9 + \sqrt{9})) + F(F(8)) \right) + 1 \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99837 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + F(F(8))) + F(-((F(F(3)) - F(7)))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 99858 &:= \left(-\left(\left(F(9) \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times (8 - F((-5) + F(8))) \right) \\
 99878 &:= \left(\left(9 \times F\left(-\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F(8)\right)\right)\right) \right) - (-7 \times F(F(8))) \right) \\
 99945 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9\right)\right) - \left(\left(9 + F(\sqrt{4})\right)^5\right)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99957 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times (F(9) + (5)) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 99958 &:= \left(- (F(9)) + \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^5 - 8 \right) \right) \\
 99964 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(9) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 99965 &:= \left(\left(- (F(9)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(6) \right)^5 \right) \right) \\
 99975 &:= 9 - F(9) + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^5 \\
 99987 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)} \right) - F(7) \right) \\
 99995 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} \right) - (5) \right) \\
 99997 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{9}) + \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{- \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (7) \right)} \right) \right) \\
 99998 &:= \left(- (F(\sqrt{9})) + \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)} \right) \right) \\
 99999 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Selfie Numbers With Fibonacci Values: Reverse Order of Digits

This subsection brings **Fibonacci type selfie numbers** with basic operations. The results are in reverse order of digits. The work is up to 5 digits. This section is divided in three parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and consecutive in blocks of 10. The second part is with symmetrical and non consecutive results. The third part is for general values.

3.1 Two Digits

$$89 := F(\sqrt{9} + 8)$$

3.2 Three Digits

$$256 := \sqrt{F(6)^5 \times 2}$$

$$374 := F(\sqrt{4} \times 7) - 3$$

$$379 := (F(\sqrt{9}) + F((7 \times F(3))))$$

$$466 := (F((-F(6)) + F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$474 := ((-4) - F(F(7))) \times -(\sqrt{4})$$

$$484 := (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$597 := -F(7) + F(\sqrt{9} \times 5)$$

$$648 := 8 \times \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}}$$

$$659 := F(9) + \sqrt{5^{F(6)}}$$

$$699 := (\sqrt{9} \times F((F(9) - F(F(6)))))$$

$$966 := (-F(F(6))) + F((F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$984 := F(\sqrt{4} \times 8) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$985 := (F((-5) + F(8)) - F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$987 := F((-((F(7) - F(8))) \times F(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$988 := (F((8 + 8)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$989 := (F(\sqrt{9}) + F((8 \times F(\sqrt{9}))))$$

$$996 := (F((F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}))) + 9)$$

3.3 Four Digits

$$0142 := -2 + F(\sqrt{4} + 10)$$

$$0179 := F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(7)) - F(10)$$

$$0199 := F(9) + \sqrt{9} \times F(10)$$

$$0247 := -F(7) \times (F(\sqrt{4}) - 20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0347 &:= F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - 30 \\ 1596 &:= (F((F(6) + 9)) - F(\sqrt{5-1})) \\ 1598 &:= F(8 + 9) + F(\sqrt{5-1}) \\ 1599 &:= (F(\sqrt{9}) + F((9 + F((5 + 1)))))) \\ 1684 &:= ((\sqrt{4} \times F(F(8))) / F((6 + 1))) \\ 1847 &:= (((F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 8) - 1) \\ 1864 &:= ((\sqrt{4} + (6)) \times F(F((8 - 1)))) \\ 1867 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times F(6)) + \sqrt{8+1}) \\ 1869 &:= (F((\sqrt{9} + F(6))) \times F((8 \times 1))) \\ 1879 &:= (((F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7))) \times 8) - 1) \\ 1974 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(7 + 9 \times 1) \\ 2579 &:= ((-\sqrt{9}) + F((F(7) + (5)))) - 2) \\ 2589 &:= (F(-((\sqrt{9} - F(8)))) + \sqrt{5^2}) \\ 2594 &:= F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) + 5 \times 2 \\ 2645 &:= (5 \times ((\sqrt{4} + F(F(6)))^2)) \\ 2646 &:= 6 \times F(\sqrt{4} + 6)^2 \\ 2648 &:= F(8)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 6 + 2 \\ 2797 &:= (((F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times F(F(7))) + F(2)) \\ 2889 &:= -((F(-((\sqrt{9} - F(8)))) + (F(F(8)) / -(2)))) \\ 2898 &:= F(8 \times \sqrt{9}) / (8 \times 2) \\ 2961 &:= ((F(16) \times \sqrt{9}) \times F(2)) \\ 2962 &:= ((F((2 \times F(6))) \times \sqrt{9}) + F(2)) \\ 2963 &:= ((F((F(3) \times F(6))) \times \sqrt{9}) + 2) \\ 2964 &:= (F(4) \times (F((F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}))) + F(2))) \\ 2977 &:= (F(7) \times (F(F(7)) - (\sqrt{9} + F(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3194 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times F((F(9)/F((1 \times 3)))))) \\ 3249 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(9 + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right)^{F(3)} \right) \\ 3374 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(7) + F(3))^3 \\ 3644 &:= \left(- (4) - \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) / - (3) \right) \right) \\ 3646 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) / 3 \right) \\ 3647 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (7) + \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) / 3 \right) \\ 3648 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4} \right) / (6 - 3) \right) \\ 3649 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \right) / 3 \right) \\ 3659 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) - F(F(3)) \right) \\ 3669 &:= \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F(6)^3 \right) \right) \\ 3844 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + F(4) \times F(8) \right)^{F(3)} \\ 3948 &:= F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(3) \\ 3993 &:= (F(3) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 3 \\ 4179 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F \left(\left(F((7+1)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ 4182 &:= \left(F(2) + F \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{1 \times 4} \right) \right) \right) \\ 4183 &:= \left(F(3) + F \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{1 \times 4} \right) \right) \right) \\ 4184 &:= \left(F(4) + F \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{1 \times 4} \right) \right) \right) \\ 4277 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F \left((F(7) + 2) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\ 4356 &:= \left((65 + F(F(3)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\ 4373 &:= 3^7 \times F(3) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 4378 &:= \left(-8 + F(7)^3 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 4397 &:= F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(3) + F(4) \\ 4428 &:= \left(\left(F \left((F(8) + F(2)) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) / 4 \right) \\ 4647 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F(7) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\ 4693 &:= \left(\left(F(3)^9 \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$4766 := \left((F(F(6)) \times (-6) + F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4768 := \left((-F(8)) \times (6 - F(F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4776 := \left(F(6) \times (-F(7)) + F(F(7) + \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4792 := \left(F(2) + (\sqrt{9} \times F(F(7) + 4)) \right)$$

$$4793 := \left(F(3) + (\sqrt{9} \times F(F(7) + 4)) \right)$$

$$4794 := \left(F(4) + (\sqrt{9} \times F(F(7) + 4)) \right)$$

$$4796 := -6 + F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7^4$$

$$4799 := -\sqrt{9} + F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7^4$$

$$4847 := \left((F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4}) \times F(8) - 4 \right)$$

$$4864 := \sqrt{4}^{F(6)} \times (F(8) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$4871 := \left(((1 - F(F(7))) \times -F(8)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4872 := \left((-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{F(8)^{\sqrt{4}}} \right)$$

$$4873 := \left((F(F(3)) - F(F(7))) \times -F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4874 := \left((F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(7))) \times -F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$4878 := 8 \times F(7 + 8) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$4879 := \left((F(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7))) \times 8 - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$4887 := (F(F(7)) \times F(8)) - (8 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$4892 := (F(F(-(2-9))) \times F(8)) - F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$4894 := -\sqrt{4} + F(9) \times F(8 + 4)$$

$$4895 := (F(5 \times F(\sqrt{9}))) \times F(8 + F(4))$$

$$4897 := \left((\sqrt{F(F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})}} \times F(8)) + 4 \right)$$

$$4899 := \sqrt{9} + F(9) \times F(8 + 4)$$

$$4925 := \left(-5 \times \left(2 - F(F(\sqrt{9})^4) \right) \right)$$

$$4945 := \left(-5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} - F(F(\sqrt{9})^4) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}4964 &:= \left(\left(F(4)^{F(6)} \right) - F \left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\4965 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- (6) - F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\4998 &:= F(8) \times F(9) \times \left(9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \\5346 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times \left(3^5 \right) \right) \\5464 &:= \left(- (4) - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) + (5) \right) \right) \\5469 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(F(6))) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) - (5) \right) \\5486 &:= \left(F(6) + \left(\left(F(F(8)) / \sqrt{4} \right) + (5) \right) \right) \\5696 &:= F(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(6+5) \\5796 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) / (F(7) - (5)) \right) \\6408 &:= 80^{\sqrt{4}} + F(6) \\6498 &:= -F(8) \times \sqrt{9} + F(4)^{F(6)} \\6569 &:= \left(\left(9\sqrt{F(F(6))-5} \right) + F(6) \right) \\6656 &:= (F(6) + 5) \times \sqrt{F(6)^6} \\6746 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (F(7) + (6)) \right) \\6759 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (- (5) - F(7)) \right) \right) - 6 \right) \\6774 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F((F(7) + (7))) \right) + F(6) \right) \\6799 &:= \left(F(9) + F \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right) + (6) \right) \right) \right) \\6969 &:= \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - (F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) + (F(9) \times 6) \right) \\6997 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + F \left(- \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - (F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\6998 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(8) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \right) \\7168 &:= \sqrt{8^6} \times (1 + F(7)) \\7448 &:= \left(- (8) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (4 \times F(F(7))) \right) \right) \\7456 &:= \left(\left((6 \times 5) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\7458 &:= \left(\left(85^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\7463 &:= -3^6 + \sqrt{4^{F(7)}}\end{aligned}$$

$$7464 := \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(4 \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7696 := \left(F \left(6 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^6} + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7759 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F \left(\left(5 + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(7 \right) \right)$$

$$7889 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \times 8 \right) - 7 \right)$$

$$7919 := \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(- \left(1 \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7924 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(- \left(\left(F \left(2 \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7954 := \left(\sqrt{4^5} - \left(- \left(F \left(9 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7959 := \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F \left(5 + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right)} \right) - F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7964 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - \left(- \left(F \left(9 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7967 := - \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) - F \left(6 \right) \right) - \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F \left(7 \right)} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7969 := \left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(6 + 9 \right) \right) \times F \left(7 \right)$$

$$7985 := \left(5 \times F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) - \sqrt{9 + 7} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7990 := 0 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7991 := 1 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7992 := 2 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7993 := 3 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7994 := 4 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7995 := 5 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7996 := 6 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7997 := 7 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7998 := 8 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$7999 := 9 + F \left(9 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$8174 := \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} - 18$$

$$8179 := F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F(7)} - F \left(-1 + 8 \right)$$

$$8184 := \sqrt{4^{F(8-1)}} - 8$$

$$8191 := -1 + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^{F(-1+8)}$$

$$8193 := \left(F(F(3)) + \left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^{F(-1+8)}\right)\right)$$

$$8194 := \sqrt{4} + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^{F(-1+8)}$$

$$8294 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times (-F(9)) + F((-2) + F(8))\right)$$

$$8364 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F((6 \times 3))\right) + F(F(8))\right)$$

$$8849 := \left(\left(-9\right) \times F\left(F\left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - 8\right)\right)\right)\right) + F(F(8))$$

$$8883 := \sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}} \times F(8 + 8)$$

$$8898 := \left(F(F(8)) - \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^8\right) \times 8\right)\right)$$

$$9216 := (F(6) \times 12)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$9218 := \left(F(F(8)) - \left(12^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)$$

$$9258 := F(8)^{5-2} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$9259 := \left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) + \left(F\left(F\left(5 + F(2)\right)\right)\right)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)$$

$$9261 := F(16/2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9262 := F(2) + F(6 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9263 := F(3) + F(6 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9264 := F(4) + F(6 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9296 := \left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + (F(2) + F(9))\right)$$

$$9349 := \left(-\left(F\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) + F\left(F\left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right)\right)\right)$$

$$9375 := 5^{7-F(3)} \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9477 := F(7) \times (F(7) - 4)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9576 := \left(F(F(6)) \times \left((F(F(7)) - 5) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$9726 := \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\left(F((2 + F(7))) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right)$$

$$9782 := \left(2 \times \left((F(8) \times F(F(7))) - F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$9783 := \left(\left((F(3) \times F(8)) \times F(F(7))\right) - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$9784 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(8)\right) \times F(F(7))\right) - F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}9786 &:= \left(((6 \times F(8)) \times F(F(7))) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\9788 &:= \left(((F(8) + F(8)) \times F(F(7))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\9789 &:= \left(((F(9) + 8) \times F(F(7))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\9946 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((F(\sqrt{4}) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\9968 &:= \left((F(F(8)) - F(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}))) + 9 \right)\end{aligned}$$

3.4 Five Digits

$$\begin{aligned}00174 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (-F(7) + 100) \\00195 &:= -5 + F(\sqrt{9}) \times 100 \\00247 &:= F(F(7)) + \sqrt{-4 + 200} \\00987 &:= F(7 - F(8) + \sqrt{900}) \\01134 &:= F(\sqrt{4^3}) \times (-1 + F(10)) \\01154 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(5 + 1)) \times F(10) \\01157 &:= F(7) \times F(F(\sqrt{5 - 1}) + 10) \\01294 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 9 \times F(2 + 10) \\01296 &:= (6 + \sqrt{9}) \times F(2 + 10) \\01299 &:= \sqrt{9} + 9 \times F(2 + 10) \\01367 &:= \sqrt{7^6} + F(3)^{10} \\01375 &:= \sqrt{5^{7-3}} \times F(10) \\01398 &:= (8 - F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(3 + 10) \\01399 &:= F(9) \times F(9) + \sqrt{3^{10}} \\01424 &:= 4^2 \times F(F(\sqrt{4}) + 10) \\01425 &:= 5^2 \times (\sqrt{4} + F(10)) \\01428 &:= F(8) \times 2 \times F(-F(\sqrt{4}) + 10) \\01439 &:= -F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3 \times 4) \times 10\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01446 &:= 6 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{F(4)^{10}} \right) \\01456 &:= (F(F(6)) + 5) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(10) \right) \\01466 &:= F(6) + 6 \times \sqrt{F(4)^{10}} \\01587 &:= F \left(F(7) + \sqrt{F(8) - 5} \right) - 10 \\01645 &:= 5 \times \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + 6 \times F(10) \right) \\01646 &:= F(F(6)) \times \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} - F(10) \\01649 &:= -\sqrt{9} + F(-4 + F(F(6))) + F(10) \\01696 &:= F(6) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6)) \times 10 \right) \\01764 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(F(6)) \times (-F(7) + F(10)) \\01784 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times 8 \times (F(F(7)) - 10) \\01847 &:= 7 \times \sqrt{4^8} + F(10) \\01854 &:= F \left(F(\sqrt{4} + 5) \right) \times 8 - 10 \\01924 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(10) \\01936 &:= F(6) \times \left(-F(F(3)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9}^{10}} \right) \\01938 &:= F(8 + F(F(3))) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(10) \right) \\01946 &:= F(F(6)) + \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(9) \right) \times F(10) \\01964 &:= F \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) - 10 \\01967 &:= -F(7) + 6^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(10) \\01984 &:= F \left(\sqrt{4} \times 8 \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) + 10 \\01993 &:= F(3)^{9+F(\sqrt{9})} - F(10) \\01995 &:= 5^{\sqrt{9}} + F(9) \times F(10) \\02498 &:= F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{4} - F(20) \\02564 &:= F \left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(6)) - 5 \right) - 20 \\02569 &:= F \left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right) + 5 - 20 \\02589 &:= F \left(-\sqrt{9} + F(8) \right) + 5 + 2 \times 0\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02595 &:= 5 \times \left(-F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 520 \right) \\02647 &:= -F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \times 20 \\02669 &:= -F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{6+6} + F \left(20 \right) \\02961 &:= F \left(16 \right) \times \sqrt{9} + 2 \times 0 \\03448 &:= 8 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + 430 \right) \\03948 &:= F \left(8 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times \left(F \left(9 \right) - 30 \right) \\03956 &:= F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(5 + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 30 \\04467 &:= F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \times \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) + 40 \\04474 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(F \left(7 \right)^{F(4)} + 40 \right) \\04874 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(8 \right) - 40 \\04998 &:= F \left(8 \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \times \sqrt{9+40} \\05126 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) + F \left(2 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(\sqrt{-1+50} \right) \right) \\05423 &:= F \left(F \left(F \left(3 \times 2 \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} - 50 \\05473 &:= F \left(3 \times 7 \right) / \sqrt{4} + 5 \times 0 \\05489 &:= -F \left(9 \right) + F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} + 50 \\06499 &:= -F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 9^4 - 60 \\06684 &:= F \left(-F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(8 \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - 60 \\06824 &:= -F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(-F \left(2 \right) + F \left(8 \right) \right) + 60 \\06825 &:= F \left(5 \times \sqrt{2 \times 8} \right) + 60 \\06846 &:= F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F \left(8 \right) + 60 \\06896 &:= F \left(6 \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 860 \right) \\06945 &:= F \left(5 \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{9} \times 60 \\07846 &:= 6\sqrt{4+F(8)} + 70 \\07847 &:= F \left(7 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times F \left(8 \right) - 70 \\07966 &:= F \left(6 \right) \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 70 \\08274 &:= \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} + 2 + 80 \\08679 &:= -\sqrt{9^7} + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 80\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 09869 &:= -F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times F(6)\right) + F(F(8)) - 90 \\
 09879 &:= F\left(-F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(7)\right) \times (F(8) + 90) \\
 10648 &:= \left(F(8) + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right)^{\sqrt{F(6)+01}} \\
 10689 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^8\right)\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right) - 01\right) \\
 10864 &:= -\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} - F(F(8))\right) + 01\right)\right) \\
 10866 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{6 \times 6}\right)\right)\right) - ((80 \times 1))\right) \\
 10869 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right) - ((80 - 1))\right) \\
 10897 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) - F(F(8))\right) \times (0 - 1)\right) \\
 10916 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{-1 + 901}\right) \\
 10942 &:= \left(F(F((2 \times 4))) - \left(\sqrt{9} + 01\right)\right) \\
 10944 &:= \left(F(F((4 + 4))) - \left(\sqrt{9} - 01\right)\right) \\
 10945 &:= F\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times \sqrt{9}\right) - 01 \\
 10956 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(5 \times \left(\sqrt{9} - 01\right)\right)\right) \\
 10958 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F\left(\left(5 + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) - 01\right) \\
 10959 &:= \left(F\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + (5)\right)\right) + \left(F(F((9 - 01)))\right)\right) \\
 10969 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(F(6))\right) + F(F((9 - 01)))\right) \\
 10979 &:= F(9) + F\left(7 \times \sqrt{9}\right) - 01 \\
 10998 &:= \left(F(F(8)) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F((9 + 01))\right)\right)\right) \\
 11466 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(6 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F(11)\right)\right)\right) \\
 11468 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + \left(- (6) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - F(11)\right)\right)\right) \\
 12269 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(F(F(6))^2\right)\right) + F(21)\right) \\
 12579 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F((5 \times 2)) - 1\right)\right)\right) \\
 12749 &:= \left(F(9) \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times 2)\right)\right) - 1 \\
 12759 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times 5\right)\right) \times \left(F(F(7)) - F(2)\right)\right) - 1\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12784 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + 8 \right) \right) \times \left(F \left((7 \times 2) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \\12789 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(F \left(8 \right) \times \left(F \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) + 2 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \\12794 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + 9 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - \left(21 \right) \right) \\12957 &:= \left(7 + F \left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 21 \\12978 &:= \left(\left(8 + F \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 21 \right) \\12979 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(\left(9 + F \left(2 \right) \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\12994 &:= \sqrt{4^{9+F(\sqrt{9})}} + F(21) \\12997 &:= \left(F \left(7 \right) \times 9 - \sqrt{9} \right)^2 + 1 \\13297 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) - \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F \left(\left(F \left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\13488 &:= \left(\left(- \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(3 - 1 \right) \right) \\13529 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F \left(\left(\left(2 \times 5 \right) \times F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\13534 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(F \left(3 \right) + F \left(5 \times \left(3 + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\13569 &:= F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F(6)} \times 53 + 1 \\13669 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(31 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\13795 &:= \left(\left(5 \times F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 31 \right) \\13869 &:= \sqrt{9} \times \left(68^{F(3)} - 1 \right) \\14325 &:= \left(-5 + F \left(23 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} - 1 \\14326 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) + 2 \right) \right) - 3 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) - 1 \right) \\14329 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(23 \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} - 1 \\14374 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(4 + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{3^4} \right) + 1 \right) \\14447 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(4^{F(4)} - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\14639 &:= -\sqrt{9} + \left(3 + F \left(6 \right) \right)^4 + 1 \\14644 &:= \sqrt{4} + \left(F \left(4 \right) + F \left(6 \right) \right)^4 + 1 \\14679 &:= \left(\left(9 \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\left(F \left(6 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) + 1 \right) \right) \\14847 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{8^4} \right) - 1 \right) \\14848 &:= 8^{F(4)} \times \sqrt{841}\end{aligned}$$

$$14879 := \left(- (F(9)) - \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times - (\sqrt{84}) \right) - 1 \right) \right)$$

$$14989 := F(9) \times F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 4 - 1$$

$$14996 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(9) \right) + F((4-1)) \right)$$

$$14998 := F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(9) + 4 \times 1$$

$$15174 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(7) \right) \right) - 1 \right) / F((5+1)) \right)$$

$$15377 := 7 \times F(7)^3 - \sqrt{5-1}$$

$$15456 := \left(F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{5+4} \right) \right) / F((5-1)) \right)$$

$$15492 := \left(F(2 \times 9) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times (5+1)$$

$$15496 := 6 \times F(9 \times \sqrt{4}) - F(5+1)$$

$$15497 := -7 + F(9 \times \sqrt{4}) \times (5+1)$$

$$15552 := (F(2) + 5)^5 \times \sqrt{5-1}$$

$$15624 := (F(4) + 2)^6 - F(\sqrt{5-1})$$

$$15626 := (6 - F(2))^6 + F(\sqrt{5-1})$$

$$15659 := F(9) + 5\sqrt{6 \times (5+1)}$$

$$15748 := \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times (7^{5-1}) \right) \right)$$

$$15769 := - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(F(6)) \times - (751)) \right) \right)$$

$$15774 := \left((4^7) - F \left(\left(F(7) + \sqrt{5-1} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$15842 := \left(2 \times \left(F((F(4) + 8))^{\sqrt{5-1}} \right) \right)$$

$$15859 := F(\sqrt{9} \times 5) \times (F(8) + 5) - 1$$

$$15868 := -8 + (6 \times F(8))^{\sqrt{5-1}}$$

$$15876 := (6 \times (F(7) + 8))^{\sqrt{5-1}}$$

$$15969 := \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((F(6) + 9)) \right) \times 5 \right) - 1 \right)$$

$$15971 := F(17) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5 + 1$$

$$16379 := F(\sqrt{9})^{7 \times F(3)} - 6 + 1$$

$$16385 := \sqrt{(-5 + F(8))^{F(F(3))+6}} + 1$$

$$16397 := F(7) + F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(3)^{F(6+1)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 16398 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) \times -(\sqrt{9}) \right) / - (F(3)) \right) - F(F((6 \times 1))) \right) \\
 16469 &:= F(9+6) \times \sqrt{F(4)^6 - 1} \\
 16483 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) / \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 16546 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - (5 \times F(F((6+1)))) \right) \\
 16574 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times (7^5) \right) - F(F((6+1))) \right) \\
 16577 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - (7^5) \right) - \sqrt{F(6)+1} \right) \right) \\
 16617 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + (\sqrt{16^{6+1}}) \right) \\
 16644 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) - (F(F(6)) - 1) \right) \right) \\
 16694 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} - F(F(6)) \right) \times F((F(6)+1)) \right) \\
 16697 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times - (6) \right) + F((F(F(6))+1)) \right) \\
 16764 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - 1) \right) \\
 16779 &:= \left(\left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(7)) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) + F((F(F(6))+1)) \right) \\
 16784 &:= -\sqrt{4} - F(8) + 7^{6-1} \\
 16786 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{F(6) \times 8} \right) - \left((7^{6-1}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 16789 &:= \sqrt{9} - F(8) + 7^{6-1} \\
 16796 &:= -F(6) - \sqrt{9} + 7^{6-1} \\
 16799 &:= -F(9 - \sqrt{9}) + 7^{6-1} \\
 16869 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) - (F(F(8)) / F((6+1))) \right) \\
 16875 &:= 5 \times (7+8) \sqrt{F(6)+1} \\
 16981 &:= \left(F((1+F(8))) - (\sqrt{9^6} + 1) \right) \\
 16982 &:= \left(F((F(2)+F(8))) - \sqrt{9^6 \times 1} \right) \\
 16983 &:= \left(F((F(F(3))+F(8))) - (\sqrt{9^6} - 1) \right) \\
 16996 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times - (F(9)) \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + F((F(F(6))+1)) \right) \\
 16998 &:= \left(\left(-((F(8) \times F(9))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + F((F(F(6))+1)) \right) \\
 17246 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + ((-2) \times F(F(7))) + 1 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17334 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left((3+3) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17469 &:= \left(\left(- (9) + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \times - (1) \right) \right) \\
 17475 &:= \left(\left(5 \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F \left((7 \times 1) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17477 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(\left(F \left(7 \right) + (7) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 17479 &:= \left(\left(F \left((9 + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F \left(F \left((7 \times 1) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17489 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(8 \times \left(\left(F \left(4 \right)^7 \right) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 17495 &:= \left(5 + \sqrt{9} \right) \times F \left(4 \right)^7 - 1 \\
 17497 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(F \left(4 \right)^7 \right) \right) + 1 \\
 17589 &:= \left(\left(F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) / - (5) \right) \times \left(F \left(7 \right) \times - (1) \right) \right) \\
 17639 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + (71) \right) \right) \\
 17640 &:= 0 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17641 &:= 1 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17642 &:= 2 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17643 &:= 3 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17644 &:= 4 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17645 &:= 5 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17646 &:= 6 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17647 &:= 7 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17648 &:= 8 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17649 &:= 9 + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - 71 \\
 17679 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(- (7) \times F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) / - \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 17684 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) / F \left(7 \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 17689 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(- \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(\left(F \left(6 \right) + F \left(7 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17691 &:= \left(\left(1 + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left((7 + 1) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17692 &:= \left(\left(2 + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left((7 + 1) \right) \right) \\
 17694 &:= \left(\left(- (4) + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left((7 \times 1) \right) \right) \\
 17695 &:= \left(\left(5 + F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left((7 + 1) \right) \right) \\
 17699 &:= \left(\left(- (9) - \sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(\left(\left(F \left(6 \right) + F \left(7 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 17709 &:= \left(- \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(0 - 7 \right) + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 17718 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + 1 \right) \right) + \sqrt{7 \times 7 \times 1} \right) \\
 17769 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) - 71 \right) \right) \right) \\
 17784 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) / \left(7 + 1 \right) \right) \\
 17789 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(7 + 71 \right) \right) \\
 17945 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 17946 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left((7 \times 1) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 17948 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(9 \right) \times 7 \right) - 1 \right) \right) \\
 17963 &:= \left(F \left(3 \right)^{F(6)} - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 71 \\
 18179 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) + 1 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 18397 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F \left(3 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 18407 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \times \left(\left(0 - \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(81 \right) \right) \right) \\
 18439 &:= \left(\left(\left(9^3 \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 18493 &:= -3 + \left(F \left(9 \right) \times 4 \right)^{F(\sqrt{8+1})} \\
 18494 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F \left(9 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 - 1 \\
 18496 &:= F \left(6 \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \times F \left(8 + 1 \right) \\
 18499 &:= \sqrt{9} + \left(F \left(9 \right) \times 4 \right)^{F(\sqrt{8+1})} \\
 18522 &:= \left(2 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\left(F \left(2 \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) \right) \\
 18694 &:= \left(\left(- (4) + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + 1 \right) \right) \right) \\
 18698 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) - F \left(\left(9 + F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{8+1} \right) \right) \\
 18699 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18764 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} \times F(7) \right) + F((F(8) + 1)) \right) \\
 18769 &:= \left((-96) + F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{8+1})} \\
 18779 &:= \left(F \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(7) \right) \right) \right) \times (F(F(7)) - (F(8) + 1)) \\
 18791 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7)) \right) \times - (81) \right) \\
 18792 &:= \left(\left((2 - \sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)) \right) \times 81 \right) \\
 18793 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7)) \right) \times - (81) \right) \\
 18794 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F(7)) \right) \times - (81) \right) \\
 18799 &:= \left((-F(9)) \times (F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(7))) \right) + (F(F(8)) - 1) \\
 18839 &:= \left(- (F(9)) + \left(\sqrt{3^8} \times F(F((8 - 1))) \right) \right) \\
 18932 &:= \left((23^{\sqrt{9}}) + F((F(8) - 1)) \right) \\
 18945 &:= \left(\left((5 \times 4)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(F(8)) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 18946 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(F((8 \times 1))) \right) \\
 18969 &:= \left((-F(9)) \times F(F(6)) + \left(\sqrt{9}^{8+1} \right) \right) \\
 19396 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} - F((F(3) + F((9 - 1)))) \right) \right) \\
 19448 &:= \left(F(8)^4 - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) / (9 + 1) \\
 19466 &:= -\sqrt{6^6} + F(4)^9 - 1 \\
 19494 &:= (4 + F(9)) \times \left(\sqrt{4^9} + 1 \right) \\
 19552 &:= 2^5 \times \left(F(5 \times \sqrt{9}) + 1 \right) \\
 19594 &:= \left(F(4)^9 - F \left(\left(5 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \\
 19642 &:= \left(\left(- (2) - F \left(\sqrt{F(4)^6} \right) \right) / - ((9 + 1)) \right) \\
 19649 &:= \sqrt{9^{F(4)+6}} - F(9 \times 1) \\
 19664 &:= \left(F(4)^{F(6)} - 6 \right) \times \sqrt{9} - 1 \\
 19681 &:= -1 + (F(8) + 6)^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \\
 19694 &:= F(4)^9 + F(6) + \sqrt{9 \times 1} \\
 19764 &:= (F(4) + 6) \times \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19772 &:= (2 + 7) \times F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} - 1 \\
 19773 &:= (F(3) + 7) \times F(7)^{\sqrt{9 \times 1}} \\
 19774 &:= (-4 + F(7)) \times F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} + 1 \\
 19782 &:= (F(2) + 8) \times (F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} + 1) \\
 19796 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times F(\sqrt{9})) - ((F(F(7)) \times 9) - 1) \right) \\
 19799 &:= \sqrt{9^9} + F(7) \times 9 - 1 \\
 19845 &:= 5 \times (F(4) \times F(8))^{\sqrt{9}-1} \\
 19916 &:= \left(F(F((6+1))) + (\sqrt{9^{9 \times 1}}) \right) \\
 19917 &:= \left(F(F(7)) - \left(- (1) - (\sqrt{9^{9 \times 1}}) \right) \right) \\
 19967 &:= F(7) \times F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9} - 1 \\
 19976 &:= \left((6 - F(F(7))) \times (\sqrt{9} - (91)) \right) \\
 20269 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (-F(6) + F(20)) - 2 \\
 20289 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \times (F(20) - 2) \\
 20291 &:= -1 + \sqrt{9} \times (F(20) - F(2)) \\
 20292 &:= -2 + \sqrt{9} \times F(20) - F(2) \\
 20293 &:= -3 + \sqrt{9} \times F(20) + F(2) \\
 20294 &:= -4 + \sqrt{9} \times (F(20) + F(2)) \\
 20297 &:= F(\sqrt{7+9}) \times F(20) + 2 \\
 20298 &:= \left(F\left(\left(\frac{8}{F(\sqrt{9})}\right)\right) \times (F(20) + F(2)) \right) \\
 20299 &:= \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{9} \times F(20) + F(2) \\
 20449 &:= \left((F((9 + F(4))) - F(\sqrt{4}))^{02} \right) \\
 20734 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{4}) + \left(F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(7)))) \right)^{02} \right) \\
 20746 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - (\sqrt{4} \times -((70^2))) \right) \\
 20868 &:= \left((-\sqrt{8^6} + F(F(8))) \times 02 \right) \\
 20895 &:= \left(-(5) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F((F(8) - 02)) \right) \right) \\
 20970 &:= 0 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$20971 := 1 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20972 := 2 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20973 := 3 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20974 := 4 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20975 := 5 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20976 := 6 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20977 := 7 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20978 := 8 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$20979 := 9 + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{90^2}$$

$$21296 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)^{2+1} \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$21604 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times (F(F(F(06))) - (F(12))) \right)$$

$$21647 := \left(- (F(F(7))) - \left(- (\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(F(6))) \right) + 12 \right)$$

$$21648 := \left((F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{4} \times 61)) \times 2 \right)$$

$$21659 := - \left(\left(F(F(F(\sqrt{9} + 5))) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times -((1 \times 2))) \right)$$

$$21746 := \left((F(F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{4}) - (F((F(7) - 1) + 2)) \right)$$

$$21748 := \left((F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{4}) - F(((7 - 1) \times 2)) \right)$$

$$21764 := \left(\left(- (\sqrt{4^6}) + F(F((7 + 1))) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$21846 := \left(\left((F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4}) - F(F(8)) \right) \times -((1 \times 2)) \right)$$

$$21863 := \left(- (\sqrt{36}) - ((F(F(8)) - 1) \times - (2)) \right)$$

$$21864 := \left((\sqrt{4} \times (- (F(6)) + F(F(8)))) - 12 \right)$$

$$21865 := - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} + ((F(F(8)) - 1) \times - (2)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$21878 := \left((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times \sqrt{8 \times 1/2} \right)$$

$$21879 := \left(\sqrt{9} + (((- (7) + F(F(8))) - 1) \times 2) \right)$$

$$21884 := \left((4 - F(F(8))) \times - (\sqrt{8 \times 1/2}) \right)$$

$$21889 := \left((F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8))) - F(((8 \times 1) / 2)) \right)$$

$$21891 := \left(\left((- (1) + \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8)) \right) - (1^2) \right)$$

$$21893 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(3)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + (1^2) \right)$$

$$21895 := \left(\left((5 - \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8)) \right) + (1 + 2) \right)$$

$$21896 := \left(\left((6/\sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)) \right) \times (1 \times 2) \right)$$

$$21897 := \left(-(7) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8)) \right) + 12 \right) \right)$$

$$21898 := \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + ((8 \times 1) - 2) \right)$$

$$21899 := \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)) \right) \times -((1 \times 2)) \right) \right)$$

$$21934 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4^3}) + F(F((9-1))) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$21946 := \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (F((9+1)) - F(2)) \right)$$

$$21948 := \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + (F((9+1)) + F(2)) \right)$$

$$21964 := \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \times \left(F(9)^{1 \times 2} \right) \right)$$

$$21966 := \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left((6^{F(\sqrt{9})}) + 1 \right) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$21983 := \left(F(3) \times F(F(8)) + \sqrt{91^2} \right)$$

$$21984 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(F(8)) \right) + (91 + F(2)) \right)$$

$$21996 := \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((\sqrt{9} - F((9+1))) \right) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$21998 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F((9+1)) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$22184 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) + F(12) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$22646 := \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6 \times 2)\right)\right) \right) \times 2 \right)$$

$$22647 := \left(\left(\left(F\left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 2 \right) + F(2) \right)$$

$$22784 := \sqrt{4^8} \times F(7 + 2 + 2)$$

$$23185 := \left(F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} - 1}\right) \right) / F(3) + F(2)$$

$$23186 := \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{8+1}\right)\right) \right) / F(3) \right) + 2$$

$$23488 := \left(F(F(8)) - \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times - (3) \right) + F(2) \right) \right)$$

$$23489 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8)) \right) + F\left(\left(\left(4^{F(3)}\right) + F(2)\right)\right) \right)$$

$$23679 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (7 \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \right) / 2$$

$$23688 := F(8 + 8) \times F(6) \times \sqrt{3^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23689 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right) \times F \left(F(6) \times F(3) \right) \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 23696 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F \left(F(6) \times F(3) \right) \right) + F(2) \right) \right) \\
 23766 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{F(6) + F(6)} \right) \times \left(F(F(7)) \times F \left((3^2) \right) \right) \right) \\
 23864 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) - F(F(3)) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 23869 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(F(F(F(6))) + F((8 \times F(3))) \right) \right) \times - (2) \\
 23997 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \left(\left(F(9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(3)) \right) \right) - 2 \right) \\
 23998 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(8) - F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 3 \right) - 2 \right) \\
 23999 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\left(9 - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(F(9) \times 3 + F(2) \right) \right) \\
 24198 &:= 8 \times F(9+1)^{\sqrt{4}} - 2 \\
 24278 &:= F(8) \times F(7+2)^{\sqrt{4}} + 2 \\
 24279 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7) \times 2) \right) / (F(4) + 2) \right) \\
 24296 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \left(\left(F(9)^2 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) - F(2) \right) \\
 24298 &:= F(8) \times \left(F(9)^2 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F(2) \\
 24338 &:= \left((F(8) + F(3))^3 + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 2 \\
 24467 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F(4) \right) \right) + 2 \\
 24468 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) - 4 \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 24476 &:= - \left(\left(F((6 + F(7))) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F((4 \times 2)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 24574 &:= \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \times \sqrt{5+4} - 2 \\
 24576 &:= 6 \times (F(7) - 5)^{\sqrt{4^2}} \\
 24625 &:= \left((5^2) \times \left(F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 2 \right) \right) \\
 24647 &:= \left(F(7) + F(\sqrt{4} \times 6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 2 \\
 24698 &:= F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(6) / F(4) + 2 \\
 24768 &:= \left(\left(86 \times F \left(\left(F(7) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 24843 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F((8 + F(4))) \right) \right)^2 \right) \\
 24977 &:= F(7) + \left(79 \times \sqrt{4} \right)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24989 &:= F(9) \times F(8) \times \left(F(9) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(2) \\
 24991 &:= \left(\left((-1) + F(9) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(F((4 \times 2))) \right) \\
 24995 &:= \left(\left(F(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - F(9) \right) / F(4) \right) - 2 \\
 25595 &:= -5 + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^5 \times 5 \right)^2 \\
 25599 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^5 \times 5 \right)^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 25664 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4} \times F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + (5)) \right) + 2 \\
 25746 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (7 \times 5)^2 \right) \right) \\
 25839 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((-3) + F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) - F(2) \\
 25844 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((F(-(F(4) - F(8)))) \times 5) + 2 \right) \\
 25998 &:= F(8) \times \left(9 + F(\sqrt{9} \times 5) \right) \times 2 \\
 26364 &:= \left(\left(F((F(\sqrt{4}) + (6)))^3 \right) \times (6 \times 2) \right) \\
 26447 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) - F(4))^{\sqrt{4}} - (6) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 26448 &:= \left(F(F(8) - F(\sqrt{4})) \right) + \left(F(4)^{F(6)+F(2)} \right) \\
 26484 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8) - F(\sqrt{4})) \right) - F((6 \times 2)) \right) \\
 26496 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times - (4) \right) / (- (6) - F(2)) \\
 26571 &:= \left(F(F((1+7))) + \left(5^{\sqrt{6^2}} \right) \right) \\
 26586 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(\left(8 + \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 26625 &:= 52 \times \sqrt{F(6)^6} + F(2) \\
 26645 &:= 5 \times \left(\sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} - F(6) \right)^2 \\
 26648 &:= \left(\left(F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \times (F(F(6)) + (6)) \right) - F(2) \\
 26749 &:= \left(\left(F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} + (7) \right) \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \right) \\
 26767 &:= F(7) \times \left(6 \times \sqrt{7^6} + F(2) \right) \\
 26784 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(F(8)) \right) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) - F(2)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26793 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + F((F(F(6)) + 2)) \right) \\
 26795 &:= \left(\sqrt{5^{F(\sqrt{9})}} \times (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 2)) \right) \\
 26846 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - 8 \right) \times 62 \right) \\
 26964 &:= \left(4 \times \left(- \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2))) \right) \right) \\
 26966 &:= \left(\left(- (6) + \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + F((F(F(6)) + F(2))) \right) \\
 26969 &:= \left(\left(- (\sqrt{9}) + \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) + F((F(F(6)) + F(2))) \right) \\
 26972 &:= \left(\left(F((F(2) + (7)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F((F(F(6)) + F(2))) \right) \\
 26984 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(- (F(8)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2))) \right) \right) \\
 26985 &:= 5 \times F(8) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} + F(2) \right) \\
 26994 &:= (-4 + F(9))^{\sqrt{9}} - \sqrt{6^2} \\
 26996 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6)) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (6 - 2) \right) \\
 26998 &:= (F(8) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(6/2) \\
 27149 &:= F(9) / \sqrt{4} \times F(17) \times F(2) \\
 27358 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) \times - (5)) / - (F(3)) \right) - \sqrt{7^2} \right) \\
 27364 &:= \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left((F(F(F(6))) / - (F(3))) \times (7 - 2) \right) \right) \\
 27459 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(5 \times F(\sqrt{4} + F(7)) \right) \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 27495 &:= \left(\left(\left(59 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 27497 &:= \left(\left((F(7) \times - (9)) \times \left(- (\sqrt{4}) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 27596 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times - (5) \right) + ((F(F(7)) - 2)) \right) \\
 27598 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times 5 \right) + F((F(7) \times F(2))) \right) \\
 27644 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4} \times F(6)) \right) \times 7 \right) + 2 \right) \\
 27796 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 27846 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^{F(4)} \right) + (F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{7+2} \right) \\
 27889 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times F(8) + 8 \times F(7) \right)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27928 &:= \left(F \left((F(8) + 2) \right) - \left(9^{\sqrt{7+2}} \right) \right) \\
 27958 &:= \left(\left((8 \times 5) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(F(7)) - 2 \right) \\
 27965 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left((F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(F(7)) - F(2) \right) \right) \\
 27966 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left((F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \times F(F(7)) + F(2) \right) \right) \\
 27976 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left((F(7) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times F(F(7)) + 2 \right) \right) \\
 27984 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F \left((F(8) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) + (F(F(7)) - 2) \right) \right) \\
 28047 &:= - \left(\left(F \left((F(7) + \sqrt{4}) \right) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 28279 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F((7 \times 2)) - F((F(8) + 2))) \right) \right) \\
 28296 &:= - \left(\left(\left((F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9}))^2 \right) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 28425 &:= - \left(\left((F(F((5 + 2))) - F(\sqrt{4})) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 28426 &:= \left(\left(F((F(F(6)) + 2) + \sqrt{4}) - F(F((8 - F(2)))) \right) \right) \\
 28449 &:= \left((9^4) - \left((\sqrt{4} - F(F(8))) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 28459 &:= (F(9) \times 5)^{\sqrt{4}} - F(8)^2 \\
 28469 &:= \left(\left((-9) \times F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28479 &:= \left(\left(-9 - (F(7)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28488 &:= \left(- \left((-8 + F(8))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28497 &:= \left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - 8^2 \\
 28529 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{2+5} \right) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 28532 &:= F(23) - \sqrt{5^{8-2}} \\
 28559 &:= \left(\left(F \left((F(\sqrt{9}) + 5) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{-5+F(8)}} - 2 \right) \\
 28567 &:= \left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{F(F(6))-5}} \right) + (8 - 2) \right) \\
 28569 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (-F((6 + 5))) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28579 &:= \left(- \left((\sqrt{9} + 75) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28589 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (8^5) \right) - F((F(8) - 2)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28594 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(9) \right) - (5) \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28596 &:= \left(\left(- (6) - F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5 \right) \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28597 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(F(7) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + (5) \right) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 28598 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\left(8^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - (5) \right) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 28599 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times - \left((F(9) - (5)) \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28615 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{5-1} \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28619 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(9) + \sqrt{16} \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 \\
 28630 &:= 0 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28631 &:= 1 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28632 &:= 2 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28633 &:= 3 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28634 &:= 4 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28635 &:= 5 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28636 &:= 6 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28637 &:= 7 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28638 &:= 8 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28639 &:= 9 - \sqrt{3^6} + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 \\
 28642 &:= \left(\left(F(2) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28646 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (6) / \sqrt{4} \right) - F(6) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28648 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - (6 + F((8/2))) \right) \\
 28649 &:= \left(F \left(\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) + (6) \right) \right) - \sqrt{8^2} \right) \\
 28659 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) + F(-5 + (6 + 8) \times 2) \\
 28661 &:= \sqrt{F(1 \times 6) + F(6) + F(F(8) + 2)} \\
 28662 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(2) - \sqrt{6 \times 6} \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28664 &:= \left(\sqrt{F(4 + 6) - 6 + F((F(8) + 2))} \right) \\
 28668 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{8 + F(6)} \right) - \left(- (F(6)) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28674 &:= \sqrt{4} + 7 \times F(6)^{8/2} \\
 28684 &:= \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right) \right) + \left((6 + F(8)) \times F(2) \right) \right) \\
 28686 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) + \sqrt{8 \times F(6)} \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28696 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28697 &:= \left(\left(F(7) + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28698 &:= \left(\left(F(8) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F(F(6)) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \right) \\
 28699 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + (F(9) + (6)) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28744 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F((4 + 7)) \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28748 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + (F(7) \times (8 - F(2))) \right) \\
 28749 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F((4 + 7)) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28765 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{5^6} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28767 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} - F(F(7)) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28784 &:= \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right) \right) + \left((F(F(7)) + F(8)) / 2 \right) \right) \\
 28795 &:= \left(\left(\left(5^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(7) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28797 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(F(7)^{8/2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 28798 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(8 \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) / 7 \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28799 &:= \left(\left(- \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - F(7) \right) \right) \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28847 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F(8) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28877 &:= \left((F(F(7)) - F(7)) + F \left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{8/2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 28879 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) - 8 \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28887 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F \left(\sqrt{8+8} \right) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28889 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(8) \right) \right) + \left(F((-8) + F(8)) - F(2) \right) \right) \\
 28895 &:= -5 + \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 8 \times F(8) \right)^2 \\
 28946 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) - 4 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F((F(8) + 2)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28948 &:= \left(\left(84^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + (F(F(8)) \times 2) \right) \\
 28981 &:= \left(\left(18^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28985 &:= 5 \times \left(F(8 \times \sqrt{9}) / 8 + F(2) \right) \\
 28986 &:= \left(\left(F((F(6) + 8)) / \sqrt{9} \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28997 &:= \left(\left((F(7) - \sqrt{9}) \times F(9) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 29188 &:= \left(\left(((8 \times F(F(8))) - 1) / \sqrt{9} \right) - F(2) \right) \\
 29266 &:= \left(\left((-F(F(6))) \times F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \right) / -(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(2) \\
 29268 &:= \left(\left((-F(8)) \times F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \right) / -(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(2) \\
 29269 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \times -((9 - 2))) \right) \\
 29287 &:= \left(\left(7 \times (F((F(8) - 2)) + \sqrt{9}) \right) - F(2) \right) \\
 29357 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \left((5^3) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - F(2) \right) \\
 29376 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) + 3 \right) \times (\sqrt{9} \times 2) \\
 29466 &:= \left(6 \times \left((F(F(6)) - 4)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 \right) \right) \\
 29468 &:= \left(F(F(8)) - \left((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times -(\sqrt{9} - F(2)) \right) \right) \\
 29476 &:= 6 \times (F(7) + 4)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 \\
 29524 &:= \left(\left((F(4)^{2 \times 5}) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 29526 &:= \left((F(6) + F(2))^5 + \sqrt{9} \right) / 2 \\
 29577 &:= 7 \times (F(7) \times 5)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 2 \\
 29597 &:= F(7) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + 5 \times F(9) \right)^2 \\
 29642 &:= \left(\left(F(2^4) \right) + F\left((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - 2 \\
 29643 &:= \left(\left(F(F(3)^4) \right) + F\left((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - F(2) \\
 29644 &:= \left(F((4 \times 4)) + F\left((F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) - F(2) \right) \right) \\
 29646 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) + F\left((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + 2 \\
 29664 &:= F(\sqrt{4} \times 6) \times (6 \times F(9) + 2) \\
 29668 &:= \left((F(F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) + \left((6^{\sqrt{9}+2}) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29744 &:= 44 \times \left(F(7) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^2 \\
 29768 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(6 + F\left(\left(F(7) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) \\
 29792 &:= (2 \times 9 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(2) \\
 29793 &:= (F(3) \times 9 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} + 2 \\
 29879 &:= \left(\left(F((9+7)) - F(F(8)) \right) \times -(\sqrt{9}) \right) + 2 \\
 29883 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) - F\left(\left(8 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 29984 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(9) - 2 \right) \\
 31848 &:= - \left(\left(F\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(F(F(8)) - 1 \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 31944 &:= F(4) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(9-1) \right)^3 \\
 32397 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + \left(-F(3) \times F\left(F\left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32649 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(-F(4) \times F(F(6)) \right) + F\left(F\left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32669 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(F(F(6))) \right) - \left(F\left(\left(F(6) - F(2) \right) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \right) \\
 32679 &:= \left(\left(\left(-F\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + 2 \right) \times 3 \\
 32744 &:= 4 \times \left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} - 2 \times 3 \right) \\
 32766 &:= F(6)^{F(6)-\sqrt{7+2}} - F(3) \\
 32769 &:= \sqrt{9} + F(6)^{7-2} - F(3) \\
 32774 &:= \left(4^7 + \sqrt{7+2} \right) \times F(3) \\
 32789 &:= F(\sqrt{9})^{8+7} + F(2^3) \\
 32793 &:= \left(-3 \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7) \right) - F\left(F\left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32795 &:= 5 \times \left(\sqrt{9^{7+F(2)}} - F(3) \right) \\
 32796 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(6)) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(-7 + F\left(F\left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32799 &:= F(9) + F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)+2} - 3 \\
 32824 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(2 - F(F(8)) \right) + 2 \right) \times -3 \right) \\
 32833 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{3 \times 3} \times F(F(8)) \right) - (2+3) \right) \\
 32834 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(3) \right) \right) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) - (F(2) + 3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32842 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(2) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + (F(2) + 3) \right) \\
 32843 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + (2 + 3) \right) \\
 32844 &:= \left(\left(\left(4 - \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times (F(2) + F(3)) \right) \\
 32846 &:= \left(\left(\left(6 / \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + \left(2^3 \right) \right) \\
 32854 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(- (5) - F(F(8)) \right) \times (F(2) \times - (3)) \right) \right) \\
 32861 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{16} \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + 23 \right) \\
 32864 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(- (F(6)) - F(F(8)) \right) \times (F(2) \times - (3)) \right) \right) \\
 32874 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - (F(7)) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times (F(2) \times - (3)) \right) \\
 32879 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(- (F(7)) - F(F(8)) \right) \times (F(2) \times - (3)) \right) \right) \\
 32895 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) - 2 \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 32927 &:= \left(F \left((F(7) - 2) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times F \left(F \left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32939 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(3 \times \left(F(9) + F \left(F \left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32943 &:= \left(3 \times \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(9) \right) + F \left(F \left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32949 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((F(4) + F(9)) + F \left(F \left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 32963 &:= \left(\left(3 \times F(F(F(6))) \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 2 \right)^3 \right) \right) \\
 32979 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((F(7) + F(9)) + F \left(F \left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33464 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times F((3 + 3)) \right) \\
 33466 &:= \left(\left(F(6) \times \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(3) \right) \right) + F(3) \right) \\
 33486 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(8 - \sqrt{4} \right)^3 \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 33488 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + (F(3) + 3) \right) \right) \\
 33489 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 \right)^{F(3)} \\
 33496 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \left(F \left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F(3) \right) \right) + F(F(3)) \right) \\
 33498 &:= \left(\left(F(8) \times \left(F \left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F(3) \right) \right) + 3 \right) \\
 33548 &:= F \left(8 + \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(5 \times 3) - F(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33594 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9 \right) \right) \times F \left(5 + F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(3 \right) \\
 33614 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(1 + 6 \right)^{F \left(3 \right) + 3} \\
 33657 &:= F \left(7 \right) \times \left(5 + F \left(6 \times \sqrt{3} \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 33694 &:= \left(\left(4 + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(3 \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 33697 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(6 \times F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \\
 33796 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F \left(6 \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \times F \left(3 \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 33825 &:= F \left(5 \times \sqrt{2} \times 8 \right) \times \left(F \left(3 \right) + 3 \right) \\
 33846 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) + \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(F \left(3 \right) + 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 33867 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{76} \right) - F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{3} \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 33964 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(9^3 \right) \right) \times F \left(3 \right) \right) \\
 33969 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(9 - F \left(3 \right) \right) \times F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33978 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + F \left(\left(7 \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 3 \right) \times 3 \\
 33996 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(\left(F \left(9 \right)^{F \left(3 \right)} + F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 33999 &:= \left(\left(F \left(9 \right) \times \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 9 \right)^3 \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 34368 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(6 \right)^3 - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 34398 &:= F \left(8 \right)^{F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)} \times \left(3^4 - 3 \right) \\
 34445 &:= 5 \times \left(F \left(4 \right)^4 + \sqrt{4} \right)^{F \left(3 \right)} \\
 34476 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(F \left(7 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times F \left(\left(F \left(4 \right)^{F \left(3 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 34659 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 5 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(4 \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 34669 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(9 + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) / F \left(6 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 34674 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 34848 &:= \left(8 + \sqrt{4^8} \right)^{\sqrt{4}} / F \left(3 \right) \\
 34876 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \times F \left(7 \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \\
 34969 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(6 \right) \right) \times F \left(9 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right)^{F \left(3 \right)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34986 &:= -6 + (F(8) - \sqrt{9})^4 / 3 \\
 34989 &:= (-9 + (F(8) - \sqrt{9})^4) / 3 \\
 35189 &:= ((F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((F(8) + 1))) - F(F((5 + F(3)))))) \\
 35369 &:= ((F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))))) - 53) \\
 35396 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})))))) - (F((F(3) + (5)))))) \times F(3) \\
 35412 &:= ((F((21 + F(\sqrt{4})))) - (5)) \times F(3) \\
 35416 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + 1)) \times \sqrt{4}) - (5 + F(F(3)))) \\
 35418 &:= ((F((F(8) + 1)) - \sqrt{4}) \times (5 - 3)) \\
 35419 &:= ((F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((1 + F((F(4) + (5))))))) - 3) \\
 35424 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(2 + 4 \times 5) + F(3) \\
 35426 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(2))) \times \sqrt{4}) + (5 - F(F(3)))) \\
 35436 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + (\sqrt{4} + (5))) \times F(3) \\
 35448 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})))) + F((\sqrt{4} + (5)))) \times F(3) \\
 35464 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (F(F(6)) + F(((4 \times 5) + F(3)))))) \\
 35649 &:= ((9 + F((\sqrt{4} \times 6))) \times F(F((5 + F(3)))))) \\
 35799 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (F((9 + 7)) + F(F((5 + 3)))))) \\
 35929 &:= (F(9) - F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 - 3 \\
 35933 &:= (((33^{\sqrt{9}}) - (5)) + F(F(3))) \\
 35934 &:= (-F(4) + ((F(F(3)) + (F(\sqrt{9})^5))^3)) \\
 35939 &:= ((F(9) - F(F(3)))^{\sqrt{9}} + (5 - 3)) \\
 35956 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F((5^{F(\sqrt{9})})) + (5)) / 3)) \\
 35992 &:= ((-((F(2) - F(9)))^{\sqrt{9}}) + F((5 \times F(3)))) \\
 36174 &:= -\sqrt{4} + (F(7) + 1) \times F(6 \times 3) \\
 36179 &:= \sqrt{9} + (F(7) + 1) \times F(6 \times 3) \\
 36246 &:= (F(F(6)) \times -((\sqrt{4} - ((2 \times 6)^3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36289 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F(8) \times \left((2 \times 6)^3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 36399 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(- \left(F(9) \right) + \left(\left(F(3) + F \left(F(6) \right) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 36446 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(F(6)^{F(4)} \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(F(3) \right) \right) \\
 36449 &:= \left(F(9) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)^{F(4)} + F(6)^3 \\
 36475 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(7 + \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) / 3 \right) \right) \\
 36478 &:= \left(- \left(F \left(F(8) \right) \right) + \left(F(7) \times \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) / 3 \right) \right) \right) \\
 36479 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\left(F \left(F(7) \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 36498 &:= \left(F \left(F(8) \right) - \left(F \left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times - \left(\left(F(6) \times F(3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36499 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F \left(F(6) \right) \right)^3 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36699 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - F \left(F(6) \right) \right) - F \left((6 \times 3) \right) \right) \\
 36749 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 7 \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) + F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36799 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(9) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times F \left(F(7) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 36849 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F \left(-F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + 8 \right)} \right) + \left(F \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) + F(3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36879 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9+7^8} \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) + F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36934 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{3+9}} \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \right) \\
 36949 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(9) - \sqrt{4} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) - F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36964 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + F \left(F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36978 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) - \left(\left(F \left(F(7) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times - (6) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 36989 &:= \left(F(9) \times 8 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 6 / F(3) \\
 36993 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(3) \times F(9) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F(6) \right) + F \left(F(3) \right) \\
 36996 &:= F(6) \times F(9)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(6) / F(3) \\
 37179 &:= \sqrt{9^7} \times (1 + F(7) + 3) \\
 37349 &:= \left(9 + \sqrt{4^3} \right) \times F(7)^3 \\
 37395 &:= \left(F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - \left(F(3) + F \left(F(7) \right) \right) \right) / F(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 37396 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(\left(F(6) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{F(3)} \right) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) / F(3) \right) \\
 37545 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{5^4} \right) + 5 \times F(7) \right) / F(3) \\
 37584 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^8} + (5) \right) \times F \left((F(7) - F(F(3))) \right) \right) \\
 37649 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F \left((6 + F(7)) \right) \right) \right) + F(3) \right) \\
 37674 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times - \left(\left(F(6) - \left(F(7)^{F(3)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37684 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(- \left(F(6) \right) \times F \left((F(7) + 3) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37689 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(F(8)) \right) + \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(F(F(7)) - F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37696 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times \left(F(F(6)) - F \left((F(7) + F(3)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37747 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - (7) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + F(F(3)) \right) \\
 37749 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(9) + \sqrt{4^7} \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + 3 \right) \\
 37794 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \times F(7) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 37845 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} \times 87^{F(3)} \\
 37926 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6))^2 \right) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left((F(7) - F(3)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 37964 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) - 3 \right) \right) \\
 37976 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (6) + \left(F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) - 3 \right) \\
 37984 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) + F(3) \right) \right) \\
 38274 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) - F(2) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - \left(F(3) \right) \right) \\
 38297 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F(2) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) / - \left(F(3) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38414 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 14^{8/F(3)} \\
 38419 &:= \sqrt{9} + 14^{8/F(3)} \\
 38437 &:= (7 \times F(3))^4 + \sqrt{F(8)^{F(3)}} \\
 38445 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times \left(F(4) \times F \left((8 + F(3)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 38447 &:= -F(7+4)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(8 \times 3) \\
 38478 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times - (8) \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 38479 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times 7 \right)^4 + F(8) \times 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38495 &:= (5 + F(9)) \times F(\sqrt{4} \times 8) + F(3) \\ 38592 &:= -(2 \times \sqrt{9})^5 + F(8 \times 3) \\ 38656 &:= \left((F(F(6)) - \sqrt{5^{F(6)}}) \times - \left((8^{F(3)}) \right) \right) \\ 38679 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F(F(7)) \times ((F(6) \times F(8)) - F(3))) \right) \\ 38745 &:= \left((5 + F(\sqrt{4} + F(7))) \times (F(8) \times 3) \right) \\ 38747 &:= \left(-(F(7)) + \left((\sqrt{4} + F(7)) \times F((F(8) - 3)) \right) \right) \\ 38799 &:= F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} + 7 - 8^3 \\ 38927 &:= -F(7 \times 2) + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right)^3 \\ 38976 &:= \left((F((F(6) + (7))) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times (8^{F(3)}) \right) \\ 38978 &:= \left((8 \times ((F(F(7)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times F(8))) + F(3) \right) \\ 38982 &:= \left((2^{8+\sqrt{9}} + F(F(8))) \times 3 \right) \\ 38997 &:= \left((F((F(7) + F(\sqrt{9}))) + 9) \times (F(8) \times 3) \right) \\ 39194 &:= -\sqrt{4} \times F(9 + 1) + F(9)^3 \\ 39199 &:= F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} - (1 + F(9)) \times 3 \\ 39246 &:= \left((F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \times F((2 + 9))) - 3 \right) \\ 39248 &:= -F(8 + \sqrt{4}) - F(2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39254 &:= -\sqrt{4} \times 5^2 + F(9)^3 \\ 39269 &:= -F(\sqrt{9} + 6) - F(2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39295 &:= -5 - \sqrt{9} - F(2) + F(9)^3 \\ 39299 &:= F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 2 - 9/3 \\ 39306 &:= F(6 + 03)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(3) \\ 39309 &:= F(9)^{03} + \sqrt{9} + F(3) \\ 39319 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) + 13 + F(9)^3 \\ 39328 &:= \sqrt{8^2} \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 39329 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 2)^{F(3)} + F(9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39347 &:= -F(7) + \sqrt{4} \times (3^9 - 3) \\
 39348 &:= F(8) \times \sqrt{4} + F(3) + F(9)^3 \\
 39354 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (-5 + 3^9) - F(3) \\
 39359 &:= \sqrt{9} + (-5 + 3^9) \times F(3) \\
 39372 &:= (\sqrt{2+7} + 3^9) \times F(3) \\
 39379 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) + 73 + F(9)^3 \\
 39383 &:= \sqrt{3^8} - F(3) + F(9)^3 \\
 39389 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) + 83 + F(9)^3 \\
 39399 &:= F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(3) + 93 \\
 39429 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 2)^{F(4)} + F(9)^3 \\
 39434 &:= (F(4)^{\sqrt{3^4}} + F(9)) \times F(3) \\
 39446 &:= (F((F(6) + (4))) - ((\sqrt{4} - (F(9)^3)))) \\
 39447 &:= (F((F(7) - F(\sqrt{4}))) - ((F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(9)^3)))) \\
 39448 &:= \sqrt{(8+4)^4} + F(9)^3 \\
 39449 &:= F(9)^{F(4)} + F(\sqrt{4}) + F(9+3) \\
 39456 &:= (F(6) \times ((5 \times F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}))) - 3) \\
 39465 &:= (-5 \times ((-F(6) \times F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}))) + 3) \\
 39467 &:= (((-7) \times F(F(F(6)))) / -(\sqrt{4})) + (F(9)^{F(3)}) \\
 39469 &:= \sqrt{9} \times F(6+4) + F(9)^3 \\
 39472 &:= -F(2) + F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(9)^3 \\
 39473 &:= (F(F(3)) \times ((F(7)^{\sqrt{4}}) + (F(9)^3))) \\
 39478 &:= 87 \times \sqrt{4} + F(9)^3 \\
 39485 &:= (-5 \times ((-8) \times F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}))) - F(F(3)) \\
 39488 &:= 8 \times (F(8) + \sqrt{4}) + F(9)^3 \\
 39494 &:= (4^{\sqrt{9}} + F(4)^9) \times F(3) \\
 39496 &:= 6 \times (F(9) - \sqrt{4}) + F(9)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$39539 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \right) + \left(F(9)^3 \right) \right)$$

$$39546 := 6 \times F(\sqrt{4} + 5)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 3$$

$$39549 := F(\sqrt{9}) + F(4)^5 + F(9)^3$$

$$39574 := \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(F(7)) \times 5) \right) \times - (F(9)) \right) - F(3) \right)$$

$$39579 := F(\sqrt{9} + 7) \times 5 + F(9)^3$$

$$39585 := 5 \times F(8) \times \sqrt{F(5+9)^{F(3)}}$$

$$39595 := \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (F(9)) \times F(F((5 + F(\sqrt{9})))) \right) + 3 \right) \right)$$

$$39599 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(9) - \sqrt{9}) \right) - (5) \right) / F(9) + 3 \right)$$

$$39602 := \left(\left(- (F(20)) + F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(3)) \right)$$

$$39605 := \left(5 \times \left(F(F(06) + \sqrt{9}) \right)^{F(3)} \right)$$

$$39606 := \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(06)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + 3 \right)$$

$$39647 := 7\sqrt{F(4)+6} + F(9)^3$$

$$39676 := - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((F(F(7)) - F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - 3 \right) \right)$$

$$39678 := - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left((F(F(7)) - F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - F(F(3)) \right) \right)$$

$$39679 := \left(\left(- (F(\sqrt{9})) + F((-7) + F(F(6))) \right) + (F(9)^3) \right)$$

$$39696 := \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6))) \right) + (93) \right)$$

$$39726 := \left(\left(F(F(F(6)) - 2) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9}^{F(3)} \right) \right)$$

$$39749 := \left(F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(7) \right) \times F(9) + 3$$

$$39762 := \left(\left(F(2 \times F(6)) / 7 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(3) \right)$$

$$39784 := \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left((F(7) - \sqrt{9})^3 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$39799 := 9 \times F(\sqrt{9} + 7) + F(9)^3$$

$$39816 := F(6)^{\sqrt{1+8}} + F(9)^3$$

$$39836 := \left(\left(F(F(6) \times F(3)) - F(F(8)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times - (F(3))$$

$$39959 := \left(F(9) + \left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(F(9) / F(3)) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39967 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(6 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times -((F(9)/F(3))) \right) \\
 39976 &:= \left(F((F(6) + (7))) + \left((\sqrt{9^9}) \times F(3) \right) \right) \\
 39984 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8) \right) \times F(9) + F(9)^3 \\
 39985 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left(\left(F(8) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right)^{9^9} - 3 \right) \right) \\
 39998 &:= (8 \times (F(9) - 9))^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(3) \\
 39999 &:= F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(9) + 9^3 \\
 40465 &:= \left(\left(F((5 + F(F(6)))) + \sqrt{4} \right) / F(04) \right) \\
 40566 &:= \left(6 \times \left(F\left(\sqrt{F(6) \times 50}\right) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 40586 &:= 6 \times F(\sqrt{8 \times 50}) - 4 \\
 40596 &:= \left(6 \times \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F((5 \times 04)) \right) \right) \\
 40775 &:= \left((5 \times F(F(7))) \times \left(70 / \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 40938 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times 3) + \left((90^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\
 41469 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(6) \right)^{F(4)} - 1 \right) \times F(4) \\
 41474 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(7) \right)^4 + 1 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 41496 &:= \left(- (F(F(6))) \times \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^4 \right) \right) + 1 \right) \times -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 41603 &:= \left((F(30) / (F(F(6)) - 1)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 41616 &:= \left((6 \times F((1 + F(6))))^{\sqrt{1 \times 4}} \right) \\
 42276 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) - (F((7 \times 2)))) \times \sqrt{2^4} \right) \\
 42437 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - (3^{F(4)}) \right)^2 \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 42546 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left((45^2) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 42632 &:= 2 \times (F(3) + F(6 \times 2))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 42647 &:= \left(F(7) \times F(4)^{F(6)} + F(2) \right) / \sqrt{4} \\
 42768 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{2^4} \right) \\
 42849 &:= \sqrt{9^4} \times (F(8) + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42874 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(7) + F(8) + F(2))^{F(4)} \\
 42876 &:= \left((6 - F(F(7))) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{2^4} \\
 42878 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{8/2}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 42896 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + \left(F(9) + F(\sqrt{8/2}) \right)^{F(4)} \right) \\
 42968 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + (-6 \times F(9)) \right) \times \sqrt{2^4} \\
 42984 &:= \left(\left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(8) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) / 2 \times F(4) \\
 42986 &:= \left(\left(6 \times F(F(8) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + 2 \right) / 4 \\
 43188 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + \left((F(8) + 1)^3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 43264 &:= \left(4 \times (F(F(6) + 2) - 3) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 43347 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} - F(F(F(3 + 3))) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 43428 &:= F(8 \times 2) \times \left(43 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 43464 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (3^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43467 &:= \left(-F(F(7)) + \left(F(F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{4^3}) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43488 &:= \left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{F(F(8)) / \sqrt{4} + 3} \right) * 4 \\
 43496 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times -F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(4 \times 3) \right) \times -(\sqrt{4}) \\
 43569 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{9}) - (F(F(F(6))) - 53) \times -4 \right) \\
 43644 &:= \left(\left(-F(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3)) \right) \times 4 \\
 43667 &:= \left(-F(F(7)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times -F(6)) + F(F(3)) \right) / \sqrt{4} \\
 43668 &:= \left((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) - F(6) \right) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 43674 &:= \left(-F(F(4) + 7) - (F(F(F(6))) \times -F(3)) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 43678 &:= \left(8 \times (-F(7) - F(F(F(6))) / -F(3)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 43679 &:= -F(\sqrt{9}) + (-7 + 6^3)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 43684 &:= \left(4 \times F(F(8)) - (F(6) + F(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 43687 &:= \left(-F(7) + \left(F(F(8)) - F(F(6)) \right) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43689 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(F(6)) \right) - F(3) \right) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 43692 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) - \left(F(F(6)) + F(3) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43696 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(F(F(6)) \right) \right) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43716 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - 17 \right) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43732 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(2^3 \right) \right) \right) - \left(F(7) \right) \right) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43748 &:= \left(-8 - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(7 \times 3) \right) \times 4 \\
 43749 &:= \left(\left(- \left(F(9) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(F(7 \times 3) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43749 &:= -F(9) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 43776 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(6) + F(7) \right) \right) - \sqrt{7-3} \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43777 &:= -\sqrt{7 \times 7} + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 43778 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(F(F(8)) \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(- (7) + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + 3 \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43779 &:= F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - 7 + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 43781 &:= -\sqrt{1+8} + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 43782 &:= \sqrt{2 \times 8} \times F(7 \times 3) - \sqrt{4} \\
 43783 &:= \left(-F(3) + 8 \times F(7 \times 3) \right) / \sqrt{4} \\
 43785 &:= \sqrt{-5 + F(8)} \times F(7 \times 3) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \\
 43789 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 8 + F(7 \times 3) \times 4 \\
 43791 &:= -1 + \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(7 \times 3) \right) \times 4 \\
 43793 &:= -3 + \left(\sqrt{9} + F(7 \times 3) \right) \times 4 \\
 43794 &:= 4 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + F(7 \times 3) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 43795 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9^7} \right) - F \left(F \left(\left(F(3)^{F(4)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43798 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + (7) \right) \times \sqrt{F(3) + \sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 43799 &:= \sqrt{9} + \left(\sqrt{9} + F(7 \times 3) \right) \times 4 \\
 43804 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(08)) \right) + 3 \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43819 &:= \left(\left(F(9) + 1 \right) + \left(F(F(8)) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43828 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) \times - (2) \right) - \left(F(8) \right) \right) - F(F(3)) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43839 &:= \left(F((9 + F(F(3)))) + \left(F(F(8)) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43846 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 4) + \left(\left(8^{F(3)} \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43849 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (F(9)) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(F(8)) \right) \right) \times - (F(3)) \right) - F(4) \right) \\
 43864 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6)) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - \left(\left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43873 &:= \left(F(-((F(3) - F(7)))) + \left(F(F(8)) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43877 &:= F(7) \times (7 + 8)^3 + \sqrt{4} \\
 43878 &:= \left((- (F(8)) - ((- (F(7)) - F(F(8))) \times - (F(3)))) \times - (\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 43884 &:= \left((4 \times F(F(8))) + \left((8 + F(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 43896 &:= \left(((- (6) + F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43916 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) + (- (1) + F(9))) \times \left(F(3) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43928 &:= (F(8) - 2) \times F(9)^{F(3)} \times \sqrt{4} \\
 43929 &:= (F(9) \times F(2 \times 9) + F(3)) / \sqrt{4} \\
 43946 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 4) + \left(\left(9^{F(3)} \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43962 &:= \left(((- (2) \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((9 + F(3)))) \times - (\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 43968 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(3) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43976 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 9) - 3)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44268 &:= \left((F(8) \times 62) \times F\left(\left(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 44276 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - F(4) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44278 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) + 2 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44279 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)) \right)^2 - F(F((4 + 4))) \right) \right) \\
 44285 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left((F((F(8) + F(2))) + F(4)) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 44296 &:= \left(\left(F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (F(F((2 \times 4))) \times - (4)) \right) \\
 44364 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + F((3 \times 4)) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44368 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) + F((6 \times F(3)))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44376 &:= \left(6 \times \left((F((F(7) - F(3))) - F(4))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44436 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left((F(3) + 44)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 44469 &:= \sqrt{96} \times \left(4^{F(4)} - F(4) \right) \\
 44476 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left((F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} + (4)) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44646 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(6^{F(4)} \right) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (4) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 44666 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + \left((F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 44679 &:= \left(\left(\left((-9) + F(F(7)) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 4 \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 44708 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) + F(F(07))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44712 &:= \left(\left((F(21) + F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44715 &:= \left(\left((F(F(F((5+1)))) + F(F(7))) \times 4 \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 44717 &:= 7 \times F(17) \times 4 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 44718 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) + F(F((1 \times 7)))) \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44724 &:= \left(\left((F(F((4 \times 2))) + F(F(7))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44726 &:= \left(\left((F(F(F(6))) + (2 + F(F(7)))) \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44734 &:= \left(\left(\left((4^3) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times F(4) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44738 &:= \left(\left(\left((8^{F(3)}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times F(4) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44739 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((3 \times F(F(7))) \times (4^{F(4)}) \right) \right) \\
 44746 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(4 - \left((F(F(7)) + F(4))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44767 &:= \left((-7) \times F(F(F(6))) + \left(F \left((F(7) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) - 4 \right) \right) \\
 44768 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left((-6) \times F(F(7)) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times - (4) \right) \\
 44769 &:= \left(\left(F \left((\sqrt{9} \times F(6)) \right) \right) - F((F(7) + (4))) \right) - \sqrt{4} \\
 44776 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(F(7)) + \left(F(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44876 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6)) \times F(7)) + F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{4 \times 4} \right) \\
 44878 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) + (F(7) \times F(8))) \times 4 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44936 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F((3+9)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44946 &:= \left(\left(- \left((F(F(6)) - (F((4+9)))) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$44947 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{4\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(4) \right)$$

$$44948 := (F(8) - F(4+9))^{\sqrt{4}} + 4$$

$$44967 := \left((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) \times 9) + 4) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$44978 := \left(\left((-F(8) + F(F(7)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F\left(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \right)$$

$$44988 := \left(F(8) \times F(8) \times F(9) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(4)$$

$$45148 := \left(F(8 \times F(4)) - (F(15) \times \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$45177 := \left(F(F(7)) + \left((F(F(7)) - F(F(1+5)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$45396 := \left(F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) - \left((3^5 \times 4) \right) \right)$$

$$45436 := \left(F(F(6) \times 3) - \left(4 \times F(F(5 + \sqrt{4})) \right) \right)$$

$$45468 := \left(F(F(8)) / F(F(6) - F(\sqrt{4})) \right) \times 54$$

$$45486 := \left(F(F(6)) \times - \left(F(8) - (F(4)^{5+\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right)$$

$$45568 := \left(\sqrt{8^6} \times F((5+5) + F(\sqrt{4})) \right)$$

$$45617 := \left(F((F(7) + 1)) \times \sqrt{(6+5)^4} \right)$$

$$45639 := \left(- \left(9^3 \right) + F(F(6) \times \sqrt{5+4}) \right)$$

$$45667 := \left(((F(F(7)) \times - (6)) \times F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{5^4}) \right)$$

$$45669 := \left(F(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)) - (F(F(6) + 5)) \times F(4) \right)$$

$$45698 := \left(- (F(F(8))) + \left((F(F(9) - F(F(6)))) + (5) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$45747 := \left(\left(F(F(7) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \times 75 - F(4) \right)$$

$$45751 := F(15) \times 75 + F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$45884 := \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times \sqrt{5^4}) \right) \right)$$

$$45886 := \left((((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times - (F(8))) / 5) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$45927 := 7 \times \left(F(2) + \sqrt{9} + 5 \right)^4$$

$$45948 := F(8) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + \sqrt{9^{5+\sqrt{4}}} \right)$$

$$45966 := \left(\left(- (F(F(6))) \times \left((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) / - (5) \right) \right) - F(4) \right)$$

$$45968 := \left(\left(- (F(8)) \times \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) / - (5) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$45989 := F(\sqrt{9} \times 8) - F(9 + 5) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$45998 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(8) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \times F(9) \right) / 5 - 4 \right)$$

$$46136 := \left((F((F(6) \times 3)) - F(F((1 + 6)))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$46176 := - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((F(7)^{\sqrt{16}} \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$46225 := \left((- (5) \times (- (22) - F(F(6))))^{\sqrt{4}} \right)$$

$$46284 := -\sqrt{4} \times F(8) \times 2 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46289 := \sqrt{9} - 82 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46332 := F(2^3 \times 3) - \sqrt{6^4}$$

$$46349 := -F(9) / \sqrt{4} - F(3) + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46353 := -3 \times 5 + F(3 \times \sqrt{64})$$

$$46370 := 0 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46371 := 1 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46372 := 2 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46373 := 3 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46374 := 4 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46375 := 5 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46376 := 6 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46377 := 7 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46378 := 8 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46379 := 9 + \sqrt{7-3} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46389 := \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 3 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46393 := \left(F(3) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{F(3)} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46398 := F(8) + \sqrt{9} \times 3 + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46408 := 80 / \sqrt{4} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46417 := \sqrt{(7 \times 1)^4} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$46424 := F(\sqrt{4}) + F(24) + F(6 + 4)$$

$$46425 := F(5 \times 2) + \sqrt{4} + F(6 \times 4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46429 &:= -\sqrt{9} + F(24) + 64 \\ 46432 &:= \sqrt{2^{3 \times 4}} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46434 &:= 4^3 + \sqrt{4} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46436 &:= F(6 + 3) \times \sqrt{4} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46446 &:= F(6 \times 4) + \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} - F(4) \\ 46449 &:= \sqrt{9\sqrt{4 \times 4}} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46456 &:= F(6 + 5) - F(\sqrt{4}) + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46475 &:= 5 \times (F(7)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times F(6 + 4) \\ 46485 &:= 5 \times (F(8)^{F(4)} + \sqrt{6^4}) \\ 46489 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 8)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46493 &:= (F(3) + \sqrt{9})^{F(4)} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46494 &:= (F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 6 \times F(4) \\ 46495 &:= 5^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{4} + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46496 &:= F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} / 4 + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46546 &:= F(6 \times 4) + F(5 + 6) \times \sqrt{4} \\ 46548 &:= (F((8 \times F(4))) + (5 \times \sqrt{6^4})) \\ 46576 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) - F(4) \right) \right) \\ 46584 &:= \left(F \left(- \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(8) \right) - (5) \right) \right) \right) + \left(6^{F(4)} \right) \right) \\ 46589 &:= F(\sqrt{9} \times 8) + 5 + 6^{F(4)} \\ 46592 &:= 2^9 \times (F(5 + 6) + \sqrt{4}) \\ 46596 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - (5 - F((6 \times 4))) \right) \\ 46598 &:= \left(\left(F \left((8 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) + F((5 + F(6))) \right) - F(4) \right) \\ 46599 &:= \left(\left(- \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F((6 \times 4)) \right) \right) \\ 46605 &:= -50 + 6^6 - F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46623 &:= -F(3^2) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46634 &:= -F(\sqrt{4^3}) + 6^6 - F(\sqrt{4}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46638 &:= -8 \times F(3) + 6^6 - \sqrt{4} \\ 46641 &:= -14 + 6^6 - F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46646 &:= (F(6) - \sqrt{4})^6 - 6 - 4 \\ 46670 &:= 0 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46671 &:= 1 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46672 &:= 2 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46673 &:= 3 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46674 &:= 4 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46675 &:= 5 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46676 &:= 6 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46677 &:= 7 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46678 &:= 8 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46679 &:= 9 + F(7) + 6^6 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46691 &:= -1 + F(9) + 6^6 + \sqrt{4} \\ 46696 &:= F(6) + F(9) + 6^6 - \sqrt{4} \\ 46697 &:= F(7) \times \sqrt{9} + 6^6 + \sqrt{4} \\ 46743 &:= -F(3) + F(\sqrt{4} \times 7) + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46744 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + F(\sqrt{4} \times 7) + F(6 \times 4) \\ 46746 &:= \left((F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (F(7) \times F(6) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \\ 46796 &:= \left((F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - (F(7) - F((6 \times 4))) \right) \\ 46809 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9} \times 08) \right) + \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\ 46834 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times F(F(-((F(F(3)) - 8)))) \right) + \left(F((6 \times 4)) \right) \\ 46873 &:= 3 \times (F(7) - 8)^6 - \sqrt{4} \\ 46874 &:= F(4) \times (F(7) - 8)^6 - F(\sqrt{4}) \\ 46879 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (F(7) - 8)^6 + 4 \\ 46883 &:= F(3 \times 8) + \sqrt{8^6} + F(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46884 &:= \left(F((F(4) \times 8)) + (\sqrt{8^6} + (4)) \right) \\
 46896 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + \left((-((\sqrt{9} - 8))^6) \times F(4) \right) \right) \\
 46899 &:= \sqrt{9^9} + F(8) \times 6^4 \\
 46938 &:= \left(F(8) + (F(3) + \sqrt{9})^6 \right) \times F(4) \\
 46974 &:= \left(\left(F((\sqrt{4} + F(7))) + F((\sqrt{9} \times F(6))) \right) - 4 \right) \\
 46976 &:= \left(\left(F((F(6) + (7))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (F((6 \times 4))) \right) \\
 46979 &:= \left(F((F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(7)))) + \left((F((\sqrt{9} \times F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \\
 47089 &:= \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) \times - (8)) + F(F(07)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 47125 &:= 5^{2+1} \times F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) \\
 47263 &:= \left(- \left((3^{F(6)}) \right) + \left((- (F(2)) + F(F(7)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 47298 &:= \left(\left(F((8 \times \sqrt{9})) - 2 \right) + (F(F(7)) \times 4) \right) \\
 47336 &:= \left(\left((F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) - 3) \times 7 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 47346 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}))) - F(F(3)) \right) \times 7 \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47348 &:= \left(\left(F((F(8) - F(\sqrt{4}))) - F(F(3)) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) \\
 47353 &:= \left((F(((F(3) \times 5) \times F(3))) \times 7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47354 &:= \left(\left(F(((\sqrt{4} \times 5) \times F(3))) \times 7 \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47355 &:= F(5 + 5 \times 3) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \\
 47356 &:= \left((F(((F(6) \times 5) / F(3))) \times 7) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47357 &:= 7 \times F(5 \times (-3 + 7)) + \sqrt{4} \\
 47359 &:= \left(\left(F((F(\sqrt{9}) \times (5 \times F(3)))) \right) \times 7 + 4 \right) \\
 47361 &:= \left(\left((1 + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \times 7 - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47362 &:= \left((F(2) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \\
 47363 &:= \left(\left((F(F(3)) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \times 7 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47364 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \times 7 + \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47367 &:= \left((7 \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) + (F(7) - F(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 47368 &:= \left(8 \times \left((6 \times F((3 + F(7)))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 47369 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) \\
 47374 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4} \times 7)^{F(3)} - 7 \right) / F(4) \\
 47377 &:= \left(((F((F(7) + (7))) + 3) \times 7) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47384 &:= \left(((- (4) - F((F(8) - F(F(3)))))) \times - (7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47395 &:= 5 \times \left(9^3 \times F(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47424 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(F((2 \times 4))) \right) \times - (F(7)) \right) / F(4) \right) \\
 47426 &:= \left((((F(F(F(6))) - 2) / F(4)) \times F(7)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47436 &:= \left((((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3))) / - (F(4))) \times - (F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47437 &:= \left(F(7 \times 3) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(7) / F(4) \\
 47438 &:= \left((((F(F(8)) + F(F(3))) / - (F(4))) \times - (F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47448 &:= \left((((F(F(8)) + 4) / - (F(4))) \times - (F(7))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47465 &:= \left(5 \times \left(\left((F(F(6))^{F(4)} + F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47487 &:= \left((((- (F(7)) - F(F(8))) / F(4)) \times - (F(7))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47499 &:= F(9)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} + F(4) \\
 47516 &:= \left(- (F(6)) + \left((- (15) + F(F(7)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 47517 &:= \left(- (7) + \left((- (15) + F(F(7)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 47524 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (\sqrt{4}) + F(F((2 + 5))) \right) - (F(7)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 47526 &:= \left(6 \times \left(F(- ((F(2) - (5 + 7))))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 47537 &:= \left(F(7) + \left((- ((3 \times 5)) + F(F(7)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 47538 &:= \left(F((8 \times 3)) - \left(- (5) \times \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47574 &:= \left(F(4) \times \left(F(F(7)) + \left(5^{7-F(\sqrt{4})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 47618 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left((1 + F(6)) + F(F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47697 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(F(9) \times \left((6 \times F(F(7))) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 47726 &:= \left((F((F(6) \times 2)) - F(7)) \times \sqrt{74} \right) \\
 47767 &:= \left((((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) - (7)) \times F(F(7))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47838 &:= F(8) \times \left(\sqrt{38} + F(7)^{F(4)} \right) \\
 47879 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right) \right) \times \left((-F(8) - F(F(7))) / -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 47946 &:= \left(6 \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + \left(F(9) \times \left(F(F(7)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47959 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - \left((-((5+9)) + F(F(7)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 47961 &:= \left((((1-6) - 9) + F(F(7)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 47963 &:= \left(\left(-F(3) + F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + F((F(7) + (4))) \right) \\
 47964 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - F((F(7) + (4))) \right) \right) \\
 47966 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - \left(\left(F((9 + F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47979 &:= \left(\left((-9) + F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - \left(F(7)^{F(4)} \right) \right) \\
 47985 &:= \left((-5) \times F(8) \right) \times \left(9 + \left(F(F(7)) \times -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 47986 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F \left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + F((F(7) + (4))) \right) \\
 47996 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 \times F(9)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47997 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - (9 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 48334 &:= F(4+3)^3 \times \left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 48342 &:= F(24) + F(3) \times F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \\
 48363 &:= \left(\left((F(F(3)) + (6))^{F(3)} \right) \times F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 48373 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times F(7))^3 \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 48374 &:= \left(\left(\left((F(4) \times F(7))^3 \right) - F(F(8)) \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 48377 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) - F(7))^{F(3)} \right) - \left(F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48384 &:= 4 \times F(8) \times \sqrt{(3 \times 8)^4} \\
 48386 &:= \left(\left(\left((6 \times 8)^{F(3)} \right) \times F(8) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 48426 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times \left(2 + \left(48^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48456 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left((5 - F((4 + F(8)))) / -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 48465 &:= \left((5^6) + \left((F(4) \times F(F(8))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 48477 &:= \left(- (F(7)) \times \left((F(F(7)) \times (\sqrt{4} \times - (8))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 48486 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F((F(8) - F(4))) \times - \left((F(8) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48664 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times F((- (6) + F(F(6)))) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 4 \\
 48679 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))) \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (4)) \right) \\
 48769 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)) + (7^{8-4}) \right) \\
 48776 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(F(7) + (78^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\
 48789 &:= \left(9 \times \left(((8 \times F(7)) - F(F(8))) / -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 48837 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7))^{F(3)}) + (F(8)) \right) + \left(F(F(8)) / -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 48864 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4} + F(F(6))) + \left(F(F(8)) + (F(8)^{F(4)}) \right) \right) \\
 48946 &:= \left((- (6) + F(\sqrt{4} \times 9)) + F((8 \times F(4))) \right) \\
 48948 &:= \left((F((F(8) - F(4))) + F(\sqrt{9} \times 8)) - 4 \right) \\
 48949 &:= F(9 \times \sqrt{4}) + F(\sqrt{9} \times 8) - F(4) \\
 48952 &:= \left(F((F(2) + (5)) \times \sqrt{9}) + F((8 \times F(4))) \right) \\
 48966 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(F(6)) \times (F(\sqrt{9})^8) \right) \right) \right) \times F(4) \\
 48968 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(6^{\sqrt{F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8}} \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 48969 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left((F(6)^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - F(F(8)) \right) / -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 48997 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(7)) + \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + (F(F(8)) / -(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49096 &:= \left((F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times F((09 \times \sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 49179 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)+1} + 9 \right) \times F(4) \\
 49238 &:= \left((((F(F(8)) / - (F(3))) + 2) \times - (9)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 49239 &:= \left(9 \times \left((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) / F(\sqrt{9})) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 49246 &:= \left(\left((F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{4}) / 2 \right) \times 9 \right) - \sqrt{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49248 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4} \right) / 2 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 49256 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (F((5-2))) \right) \times - (9) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 49257 &:= F(7 \times (5-2)) \times 9 / \sqrt{4} \\
 49258 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) / - (F((5-2))) \right) \times - (9) \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 49259 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9} + (5))) \right) / - (2) \right) \times - (9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 49263 &:= \left(\left(\left((3 \times F(F(F(6)))) / - (2) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times - (F(4)) \right) \\
 49264 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(F(6))) \right) / - (2) \right) \times - (9) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49276 &:= \left(- (F(6)) + \left((F(F(7)) - (2+9))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 49277 &:= \left(- (7) + \left((F(F(7)) - (2+9))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 49278 &:= \left(F(8) - \left(\left(F(F((7+F(2)))) \times 9 \right) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 49283 &:= \left(\left(- (3) + (F(F(8)) / - (2)) \right) \times - (9) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 49284 &:= \left(4 \times 8^2 - F(9) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 49285 &:= \left(5 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(- ((F(2) - F(9))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49286 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (6) - F(F(8)) \right) / 2 \right) \times - (9) \right) + \sqrt{4} \\
 49289 &:= \left(\left(- (9) \times F(F(8)) \right) / - (2) \right) + \left(F(9) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49387 &:= \left((F(F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) + 3) \times 9)) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49469 &:= (9+6)^4 - F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 49487 &:= \left(F(F(7)) - \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 9 \right) + F(4) \right) \right) \\
 49564 &:= \left((4 \times F(F(F(6)))) - \left(- (5) \times (F(9)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \\
 49596 &:= 6 \times \left(\sqrt{9^5} \times F(9) \right) + 4 \\
 49629 &:= \left(F(F((9-2))) \times \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) - F(4) \right) \right) \\
 49674 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(F(7)) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \times (F(9) \times F(4)) \right) \\
 49678 &:= \left((F(F(8)) / - (F(7))) \times \left((F(F(6)) \times - (\sqrt{9})) + 4 \right) \right) \\
 49679 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F(F(7)) \right) \times - \left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 49693 &:= \left(- (3) + F(9) \right) \times \left(6 + F \left((F(9) / \sqrt{4}) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49698 &:= \left((F(8))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 49725 &:= \left((-((5 \times 2)) + F(F(7)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - 4 \\
 49726 &:= \left((-((F(6) + 2)) + F(F(7)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - F(4) \\
 49728 &:= \left((-((8 + 2)) + F(F(7)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 49729 &:= \left(F(9) / 2 \times F(7) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 49734 &:= \left((4 + F((F(3) + F(7)))) \times \sqrt{9^4} \right) \\
 49746 &:= - \left((F(F(F(6))) + (F(\sqrt{4} \times F(7)) - 9) / -(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 49785 &:= \left(5 \times (F(F(8)) - (F((7 + 9)) + \sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 49795 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- (F((F(9) - F(7)))) + F \left((F(\sqrt{9})^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49867 &:= \left(F((7 + F(6))) + (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) / -(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 49896 &:= 6^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(8) \times (9 + \sqrt{4}) \\
 49965 &:= \left(5 \times \left((F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) - F \left((F(\sqrt{9})^4) \right) \right) \right) \\
 49977 &:= \left((- (7) - F \left((F(7) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times -(\sqrt{9^4}) \\
 49982 &:= \left(2 \times \left(- (F(F(8))) + \left((F(9) - F(F(\sqrt{9})))^{F(4)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 49994 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((F(9) - F((F(9) - 9))) / - (F(4))) \right) \\
 49995 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - \left((F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9)^4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 51695 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left((- (\sqrt{9}) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(15) \right) \right) \\
 52446 &:= \left(\left((F(F((F(6) - F(\sqrt{4})))) - 4 \right)^2 \right) + (5) \\
 52447 &:= \left((F(F(7)) - 4)^{\sqrt{4}} + (F(2) + (5)) \right) \\
 52488 &:= 8 \times \left(8 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{-F(2)+5} \\
 52489 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + \left(8 \times (F(4))^{F(F(2)+5)} \right) \right) \\
 52969 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} + F((- (6) + F(9))) \right) / (F(2) + (5)) \\
 53134 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (- (3) \times F((1 + F((3 + 5)))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53139 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times (F(3) + F((1 + F((3 + 5)))))) \right) \\
 53229 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (F(22) + F(3)^5) \\
 53298 &:= \left(F\left(\left(8 \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \times \left(-F(2) + F\left(F(3) \times 5\right)\right) \right) \\
 53374 &:= \left(\left(\left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + F\left(F(7)\right) \right)^{F(3)} \right) + F\left(F(3) + (5)\right) \right) \\
 53564 &:= \left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + \left(F\left(F\left(F(6)\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(5 + F(3)\right)\right)\right) \times 5 \right) \\
 53798 &:= \left(-F(8) + \left(\left(-\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F\left(F(7)\right)\right) \right)^{F(3)} - (5) \right) \right) \\
 53819 &:= \left(\left(-\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(-\left(1 - 8\right)\right)\right)\right) \right)^{F(3)} - (5) \right) \\
 53824 &:= \left(\left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) + F\left(F\left(-\left(F(2) - 8\right)\right)\right) \right)^{-} (3 - 5) \right) \\
 53829 &:= \left(\left(\left(-\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) + F\left(F\left(-\left(F(2) - 8\right)\right)\right) \right)^{F(3)} + (5) \right) \\
 54096 &:= F(6) \times \left(-\sqrt{9} + F(04 \times 5) \right) \\
 54234 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F\left((4 + 3)\right)\right) \right)^2 - F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5\right)\right) \right) \\
 54247 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - \left(2 \times F\left(F(4) + (5)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54257 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) \right)^{F(5-2)} - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \\
 54264 &:= F\left(\sqrt{4} + 6\right) \times F\left(2 \times (4 + 5)\right) \\
 54269 &:= F\left(\sqrt{9} \times 6\right) \times F\left(2 \times 4\right) + 5 \\
 54273 &:= \left(-(3) + \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) \right)^2 - F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54274 &:= \left(\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \times F\left(F(7)\right) \right) \right)^2 - \left(F(4) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54276 &:= F(6 + 7)^2 - F\left(\sqrt{4} + 5\right) \\
 54277 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) \times F\left(F(7)\right) \right) - \left(2 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 5\right) \right) \right) \\
 54278 &:= \left(-(8) + \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) \right)^2 - \sqrt{4 + 5} \right) \right) \\
 54279 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) \right)^2 - F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 54282 &:= \left(-(2) + \left(\left(F\left(F\left((8 - F(2))\right)\right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - (5) \right) \right) \\
 54283 &:= -F(3) + F(8 \times 2) \times F\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54284 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8 \times 2) \times F(\sqrt{4} \times 5) \\
 54285 &:= F(5 + 8)^2 + F(\sqrt{4}) - 5 \\
 54286 &:= \left((F(-((F(6) - F(8))))^2) - \sqrt{4+5} \right) \\
 54287 &:= \left((F(F(7))^{\sqrt{8/2}}) - F(\sqrt{4+5}) \right) \\
 54289 &:= F(9 + 8/2)^{F(\sqrt{4+5})} \\
 54296 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times F((9 \times 2))) + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \\
 54297 &:= \left((F(F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})}) + (2^{\sqrt{4+5}}) \right) \\
 54344 &:= \left((F(F((F(4) + (4))))^{F(3)}) + F((\sqrt{4} \times 5)) \right) \\
 54347 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7))^{\sqrt{4}}) + 3 \right) + F((\sqrt{4} \times 5)) \right) \\
 54348 &:= \left((F((F(8) - \sqrt{4})) \times F((3 + 4))) - (5) \right) \\
 54353 &:= \left((F((F((3 + 5)) - F(3))) \times F((\sqrt{4} + (5)))) \right) \\
 54379 &:= \left(F(-((F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(7)))) \right) \times (F(F(3)) + F((F(4) \times 5))) \\
 54465 &:= \left(5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (-\sqrt{4} + F((\sqrt{4} \times 5)))) \right) \\
 54467 &:= 7 \times (6^{\sqrt{4}+F(4)} + 5) \\
 54477 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F(F(7))^{\sqrt{4}}) - 45)) \\
 54485 &:= ((5 \times F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{4} + (F(4)^5))) \\
 54487 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((F(F(8)) - (4 - \sqrt{4})) \times 5))) \\
 54497 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F((9 \times \sqrt{4})) \times F((F(4) + (5)))))) \\
 54517 &:= ((F(F(7)) + 1) \times F(F((5 + \sqrt{4})))) - (5) \\
 54522 &:= ((F(2) + F(F((2 + 5)))) \times F(F((\sqrt{4} + (5)))))) \\
 54615 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - (F(F(6) + \sqrt{4}))) \times 5) \\
 54626 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \times F((\sqrt{4} + (5)))) \\
 54635 &:= ((F(F((5 + 3))) - F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4}) \times 5) \\
 54636 &:= (-F((F(6) + 3))) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times -5)) \\
 54639 &:= (-((9^{F(3)})) - ((F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{4}) \times -5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54644 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(4)^4 \right) \right) - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times - (5) \right) \right) \\
 54646 &:= \left(- (F((F(6) + F(4)))) + \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54649 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9^4} \right) - \left(F(F(F(6))) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times - (5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54654 &:= \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(4) \times 5))) \right) \\
 54657 &:= \left(- (F(F(7))) - \left(- (5) \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4^5} \right) \right) \right) \\
 54663 &:= \left(- (F(3)) + \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F\left(\left(F(6) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54664 &:= \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F\left(\left(F(6) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54665 &:= \left(\left((- (5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(6) \right) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54667 &:= \left(- (F(7)) + \left(\left((F(6) - F(F(F(6)))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times - (5) \right) \right) \\
 54669 &:= \left(F(9) + \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54671 &:= \left(1 + \left(\left((- (F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54672 &:= \left(2 + \left(\left((- (F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54674 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times \left(F(4)^5 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54675 &:= \left((5 \times F((F(7) + F(6)))) - F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right) \right) \right) \\
 54676 &:= \left(6 + \left(\left((- (F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54677 &:= \left(7 + \left(\left((- (F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \\
 54678 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + \left((- (F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54687 &:= \left(- (F(7)) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(6) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times - (5) \right) \right) \\
 54690 &:= 0 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \\
 54691 &:= 1 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \\
 54692 &:= 2 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \\
 54693 &:= 3 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \\
 54694 &:= 4 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \\
 54695 &:= 5 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \\
 54696 &:= 6 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$54697 := 7 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5$$

$$54698 := 8 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5$$

$$54699 := 9 + \left(-9 + F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5$$

$$54725 := \left(F((5-2) \times 7) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5$$

$$54728 := \left((F(F(8)) \times -((2-7))) - F(\sqrt{4+5}) \right)$$

$$54730 := 0 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54731 := 1 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54732 := 2 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54733 := 3 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54734 := 4 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54735 := 5 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54736 := 6 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54737 := 7 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54738 := 8 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54739 := 9 + F(3 \times 7) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54740 := 0 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54741 := 1 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54742 := 2 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54743 := 3 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54744 := 4 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54745 := 5 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54746 := 6 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54747 := 7 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54748 := 8 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54749 := 9 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7 \times F(4)) \right) \times 5$$

$$54751 := \left(\left(\left((1^5) + F(F(7)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - (5) \right)$$

$$54754 := - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - ((5 + F(7 \times F(4)))) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$54756 := \left((6 - 5) + F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{4+5})}$$

$$54761 := (1 + F(6 + 7))^{\sqrt{4}} + 5$$

$$54765 := \left(\left((5 + F(F(6) + F(7))) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54769 := \left(F(9) - \left(F(F(6) + F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times - (5) \right)$$

$$54776 := \left(F(F(6)) + \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4+5}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54786 := \left(F(F(6)) + \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$54787 := \left(- (F(7)) + \left(\left(F(F(8)) + (7 \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$54789 := \left(F(9) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) + (7 - \sqrt{4}) \right) \times - (5) \right) \right)$$

$$54794 := \left((4^{\sqrt{9}}) - (F(7 \times F(4))) \times - (5) \right)$$

$$54795 := \left(5 \times \left(F((F(9) - F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4} + (5)) \right) \right)$$

$$54829 := \left(F((9 + 2)) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times - (5) \right) \right)$$

$$54835 := \left(\left(F(F((5 + 3))) + \sqrt{F(8)^{\sqrt{4}}} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54845 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{5^4} + F(F(8)) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54855 := \left(\left((5 \times 5) + F(F(8)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5$$

$$54864 := \left(F(\sqrt{4} \times 6) \right) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times - (5) \right)$$

$$54865 := \left(\left((5 + F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54866 := \left(F(F(6)) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$54867 := \left((7 \times F(F(6))) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times - (5) \right) \right)$$

$$54869 := \left(F(9) + \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(F(8)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54874 := \left(F \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(7) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times - (5) \right)$$

$$54879 := \left(F \left(- \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(7) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times - (5) \right)$$

$$54884 := (F((4+8)) - ((F(F(8)) + \sqrt{4}) \times - (5)))$$

$$54887 := ((7 \times F(8)) - ((F(F(8)) + \sqrt{4}) \times - (5)))$$

$$54888 := ((8 \times F(8)) - ((F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times - (5)))$$

$$54890 := 0 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54891 := 1 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54892 := 2 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54893 := 3 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54894 := 4 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54895 := 5 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54896 := 6 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54897 := 7 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54898 := 8 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54899 := 9 + (F(9) + F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54946 := ((6^{F(4)}) - (F(F(F(\sqrt{9 \times 4})))) \times - (5)))$$

$$54963 := (3 \times (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})))) + (F((F(4) \times 5))))))$$

$$54965 := (((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F((\sqrt{4} + (5))))))$$

$$54975 := 5 \times (F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{4}) \times 5$$

$$54979 := (- (9) - (- ((F(F(7)) + \sqrt{9}) \times F(F((\sqrt{4} + (5)))))))$$

$$54988 := ((F((- (8) + F(8))) + \sqrt{9}) \times F(F((\sqrt{4} + (5))))))$$

$$54997 := ((F(F(7)) + F(9)) - (F(F(F(\sqrt{9 \times 4})))) \times - (5)))$$

$$55454 := (F(F((\sqrt{4} + (5)))) \times ((F(4)^5) - (5)))$$

$$55895 := ((F(F((5 + \sqrt{9}))) + (F((8 + 5)))) \times 5)$$

$$55945 := ((F(F((5 + F(4)))) + (\sqrt{9^5})) \times 5)$$

$$55966 := (F(F(6)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + (\sqrt{9^5})) \times 5))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 55984 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 5\right)\right) \times - (5)\right)\right)\right) \\
 56169 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(1 + \left(6^5\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 56174 &:= \left(\left(\left(4 + F(F(7))\right)\sqrt{\sqrt{16}}\right) + (5)\right) \\
 56259 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F((5 \times 2))\right) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5)))\right) \\
 56445 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)^{F(4)}\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right) \times 5\right) \\
 56464 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - \left(6^5\right)\right)\right) \\
 56598 &:= \left(- (F(8)) - \left(- \left(\sqrt{9^5}\right) \times F((F(6) + (5)))\right)\right) \\
 56619 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \left((1 - 6)\right)\right) \times F((F(6) + (5)))\right) \\
 56848 &:= \left(\left(F(8) + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times F(((F(8) - F(6)) + (5)))\right) \\
 56897 &:= \left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left((F(F(8)) - (6)) \times - (5)\right)\right) \\
 56927 &:= \left(\left((F(7) \times F(2))^{\sqrt{9}}\right) - \left(F(F(F(6))) \times - (5)\right)\right) \\
 56935 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((5 + 3))^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right) \times 5\right) \\
 56937 &:= \left(\left(F(7)^3\right) + \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(F(F(6)))\right) \times 5\right)\right) \\
 56969 &:= \left(F(9) - \left(\left(- \left(\left(F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right)\right) - F(F(F(6)))\right) \times 5\right)\right) \\
 57296 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(F(6)) + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) \times 2\right) - \left(F(7) + (5)\right)\right) \\
 57314 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F((1 + 3) \times 7 - 5) \\
 57324 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (F(2 + 3 \times 7) + 5) \\
 57349 &:= (9 - \sqrt{4}) \times F(3)^{F(7)} + 5 \\
 57379 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times \left(7 \times \left(\left(F(3)^{F(7)}\right) + (5)\right)\right)\right) \\
 57384 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(F\left(\left(F(8) + F(3)\right)\right) + (7 \times 5)\right)\right) \\
 57389 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times F\left(\left(F(8) + F(3)\right)\right)\right) + (75)\right) \\
 57464 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(F\left(\left(F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (75)\right)\right) \\
 57492 &:= \left(\left(- (2) \times F\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4}\right)\right)\right) \times - \left((F(7) + (5))\right)\right) \\
 57547 &:= \left(F(F(7)) - \left(- \left(\sqrt{4}\right) \times F\left(\left((5 + F(7)) + (5)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 57779 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + (F(7))\right) + F(F(7))\right) \times F(F(7))\right) - (5)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$58384 := \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(8)) \right) / - (3) \right) \times - \left(F(8) - (5) \right) \right)$$

$$58479 := \left(\left(9 + F(F(7)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - (85) \right)$$

$$58483 := \left(F(F(-((F(F(3)) - 8))) \times (\sqrt{4^8} - (5))) \right)$$

$$58564 := 4 \times (6 + 5)^{\sqrt{F(8)-5}}$$

$$58674 := \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right) \times (F(F(6)) + (F((8 + 5)))) \right)$$

$$58746 := \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times F(8) - (5) \right) \right)$$

$$58826 := \left(\left(F(6)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (5)) \right)$$

$$58926 := \left(F((F(F(6)) - 2)) - \left(-(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$58959 := 9^5 + (\sqrt{9} - F(8)) \times 5$$

$$58968 := F(8) \times 6^{\sqrt{9}} \times (8 + 5)$$

$$58994 := -F(F(\sqrt{4}) + 9) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8 \times 5}}}$$

$$58996 := -F(6) + 9 \times (\sqrt{9^8} - 5)$$

$$59029 := \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) \times - \left(20 - (9^5) \right) \right)$$

$$59045 := -5 + F(\sqrt{4}) + 09^5$$

$$59054 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (5 + 09^5)$$

$$59059 := F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5 + 09^5$$

$$59069 := - \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - \left(F(F(6)) + (09^5) \right) \right)$$

$$59083 := F(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^8}}) + 09^5$$

$$59266 := \sqrt{6^6} + F(2) + 9^5$$

$$59274 := (\sqrt{4} + F(7))^2 + 9^5$$

$$59279 := \left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)) \right) + \left(F(2) \times (9^5) \right) \right)$$

$$59284 := \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F((8 - F(2)))) \right) + (9^5) \right)$$

$$59314 := (F(4) \times 13)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5$$

$$59319 := (\sqrt{9} \times 13)^{F(9-5)}$$

$$59374 := \left(\left(F(4) \times F(7) \right)^3 \right) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 59427 &:= F(7 \times 2) + F(\sqrt{4}) + 9^5 \\
 59485 &:= -5 + F(8)^{\sqrt{4}} + 9^5 \\
 59488 &:= F(8) \times F(8) - \sqrt{4} + 9^5 \\
 59489 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - \left(\left(F(8)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) + \left(9^5\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 59497 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) - 9\right) \times \sqrt{4}\right) + \left(9^5\right) \\
 59531 &:= \left(1 + 3^5\right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 5 \\
 59541 &:= \left(\left(\left(1 + \left(F(4)^5\right)\right)^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) + (5)\right) \\
 59541 &:= \left(1 + F(4)^5\right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 5 \\
 59566 &:= \sqrt{F(6)^6} + 5 + 9^5 \\
 59627 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(7)\right) \times \left(2^{F(6)}\right)\right) - F\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (5)\right)\right)\right) \\
 59639 &:= \left(- (9) - \left(- \left(\left(F(3)^{F(6)}\right)\right) \times F\left(F\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + (5)\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 59644 &:= \left(- (4) - \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{F(6)}\right)\right) \times F\left(F\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + (5)\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 59648 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\left(F(8) / F(4)\right)\right)\right) \times \left(F(6) \times \left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)^5\right)\right)\right) \\
 59649 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{F(6)}\right)\right) \times F\left(F\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + (5)\right)\right)\right)\right)\right) \\
 59663 &:= \left(- (F(3)) - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(F(6)\right)\right) + F\left(\left(F(6) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times - (5)\right) \\
 59664 &:= \left(- \left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) - \left(\left(F\left(F\left(F(6)\right)\right) + F\left(\left(F(6) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times - (5)\right) \\
 59665 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(- (5) + F\left(F(6)\right)\right)\right) + F\left(F\left(F(6)\right)\right)\right) \times F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times 5 \\
 59674 &:= \sqrt{\left(-\sqrt{4} + 7\right)^{F(6)}} + 9^5 \\
 59686 &:= \left(F\left(F(6)\right) - \left(\left(F\left(F(8)\right) + F\left(\left(F(6) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)\right) \times - (5)\right) \\
 59749 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - \left(\left(- (F(4)) \times F\left(F(7)\right)\right) - \left(9^5\right)\right)\right) \\
 59774 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(\left(- (F(7)) - F\left(F(7)\right)\right) \times - \left(\sqrt{9^5}\right)\right)\right) \\
 59779 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) + \left(\left(- (F(7)) - F\left(F(7)\right)\right) \times - \left(\sqrt{9^5}\right)\right)\right) \\
 59794 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^9} + F\left(F(7)\right)\right) + \left(9^5\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 59898 &:= \left(- (F (F (8))) + \left(F \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + (F (8)) \right) \right) \times (9 - 5) \right) \right) \\
 59949 &:= (F (9) - 4)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 9^5 \\
 61485 &:= \left(\left(5 \times \left(F (F (8)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F \left((-1) + F (F (6)) \right) \right) \\
 61495 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 4 \right) + F \left((1 + F (F (6))) \right) \right) \\
 61498 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F (8) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(F (4) \times (1 + F (F (F (6)))) \right) \right) \\
 61599 &:= \left(\left(\left(F (9) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{F(5-1)} \right) + F (F (F (6))) \right) \\
 62475 &:= \left(\left(\left((-5) + F (F (7)) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)^2 \right) + F (F (F (6))) \\
 62476 &:= \left(\left(\left((-6) + F (F (7)) \right) \sqrt{4} \right) + F (2) \right) + F (F (F (6))) \\
 62584 &:= 4 \times \left(F (8) + \sqrt{5^{2 \times 6}} \right) \\
 62749 &:= \left(F (9) + \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F (7) \right) \times F \left((-2) + F (F (6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 62874 &:= \left(\left(\left((-\sqrt{4}) \times F (F (7)) \right) + F (F (8)) \right) - F (2) \right) \times 6 \\
 63296 &:= \left(F (6)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times (2 + F (F (3) \times F (6))) \right) \\
 63369 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(\left(F \left((F (6) + 3) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \times - (F (6)) \right) \right) \\
 63374 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(F (F (7)) \times - \left((F ((3 \times 3)) \times F (6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 63379 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(F (F (7)) \times - \left((F ((3 \times 3)) \times F (6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 63384 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + F (8 + 3) \right)^{F(3)} \times F (6) \\
 63462 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left((2 + F (6)) \right) \sqrt{4} \right) - 3 \right) \times F (F (6)) \right) \\
 63469 &:= \left(\left(9 \times F \left(\left(F (F (6)) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + F \left((3 \times 6) \right) \right) \\
 63483 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left((F (3) + 8) \right) \sqrt{4} \right) - F (3) \right) \times F (F (6)) \right) \\
 63489 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(F (F (8)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - \left((3^6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 63496 &:= \left(\left(\left(F (F (6)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \times F \left((4 \times 3) \right) \right) - F (6) \\
 63498 &:= \left(F (8) \times \sqrt{9} \times 4 \right)^{F(3)} - 6 \\
 63524 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(- \left(\left(F \left((2 \times 5) \right)^{F(3)} \right) \right) \times F (F (6)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 63894 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + (F (8)) \right)^3 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 63896 &:= \left(F(6) - \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(8) \right) \right)^3 \times - (6) \right) \right) \\
 63939 &:= - \left(\left(F((F(9)/F(3))) - \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(3) \times F(6)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 63948 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times F((9+3)) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 63958 &:= \left(\left((8 \times 5)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(3) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 63979 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (9) + \left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right)^3 - F(F(6)) \right) \\
 63984 &:= \left(\left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} - F(3) \right) \times F(6) \\
 63987 &:= \left(- (F(7)) - \left(\left(\left(F(8) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right)^3 \times - (F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 63992 &:= \left(2 \times \sqrt{9} + F(9) \right)^3 - F(6) \\
 63996 &:= (6 + F(9))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(3) - 6 \\
 63998 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - F((F(9) - 9)) \right) + \sqrt{3^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \\
 64058 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{504}) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 64266 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 64278 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(F(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{(2+4) \times 6} \right) \\
 64279 &:= \left(\left(- (\sqrt{9}) - F \left(\left(F(7) + \left((2^4) \right) \right) \right) \right) / - (F(6)) \right) \\
 64307 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(03) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 64366 &:= \left(\left(\left(6^6 - F(F(3)) \right) + F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64368 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(\left(6^3 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 64386 &:= \left(- (6) \times \left(\left(- \left(8^3 \right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 64537 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) + F((3+5)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 64549 &:= -F(9 + \sqrt{4} + 5) + 4^{F(6)} \\
 64592 &:= F(2 \times 9) \times \sqrt{5^4} - F(6) \\
 64594 &:= F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) \times \sqrt{5^4} - 6 \\
 64595 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - (5 \times F((F(4) \times 6))) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64597 &:= \left(- (F(7)) \times \left(- (F(9)) - \left(5 \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64668 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) \times 6) - F(F(6)) \right) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64675 &:= \left((-5) \times F(7) \right) \times \left(- (F(6)) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64679 &:= \left(\left((F(9) + F(F(7))) + F(6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} - F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 64683 &:= \left(\left((F(F(3)) - F(F(8))) \times - (6) \right) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64689 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left((F(F(8)) \times 6) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64727 &:= F(7)^2 \times \left(F \left(7 \times \sqrt{4} \right) + 6 \right) \\
 64736 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6))^3) - (F(7)) \right) \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + (6) \right) \right) \\
 64744 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + (F(4) \times F(F(F(6)))) \right) \right) \\
 64746 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) \times 7 \right) - \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} \right) \\
 64764 &:= \left(F(4) \times \left(\left((F(F(6)) \times 7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 64769 &:= \left(\left(F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \right) \times \left(F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 64788 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(F(8) - (F(7)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \\
 64829 &:= F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + 2 \times F(8)^4 / 6 \\
 64847 &:= 7 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F(8)^{F(4)} \right) + 6 \\
 64848 &:= F(8) + \sqrt{4} \times F(8)^4 / 6 \\
 64869 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 6 \right) \times \left((F(8)^{F(4)}) + (6) \right) \right) \\
 64878 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \left(7 \times (F(8) - \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \\
 64897 &:= 7 \times \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(8)^{F(4)} + F(6) \right) \\
 64927 &:= \left(\left(- (F((F(7) + 2))) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(4^{F(6)} \right) \\
 64967 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left((F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}}) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 64969 &:= \left(\left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \times 9 \right) + \left(4^{F(6)} \right) \right) \\
 64974 &:= \left(F(4) \times \left(\left(- (F(F(7))) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 65443 &:= \left(- (F(F((3+4)))) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + (5) \right) \times F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 65466 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$65467 := \left(- (F (F (7))) + \left(\left(F (F (F (6))) - \left(\left(F (\sqrt{4}) - (5) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$65469 := \left(- (\sqrt{9}) + \left(\left(F (F (F (6))) - F ((4 + 5)) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$65482 := \left(- (2) - \left(\left(F (F (8)) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \times - (6) \right) \right)$$

$$65483 := - \left(\left(F (F (3)) + \left(\left(F (F (8)) - \sqrt{4^5} \right) \times - (6) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$65494 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(F (\sqrt{9})^{F(4) \times 5} \right) - F (F (6)) \right) \right)$$

$$65496 := \left(F (6) \times F (\sqrt{9}) \right)^4 - 5 \times F (6)$$

$$65497 := -F (7) \times \sqrt{9} + \left(-F (\sqrt{4}) + 5 \right)^{F(6)}$$

$$65499 := -F (9) - \sqrt{9} + \left(-F (\sqrt{4}) + 5 \right)^{F(6)}$$

$$65524 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(F ((F (2) + (5)))^5 \right) - (6) \right) \right)$$

$$65534 := -\sqrt{4} + F (3)^{5+5+6}$$

$$65539 := \sqrt{9} + F (3)^{5+5+6}$$

$$65544 := \sqrt{4} \times (F (4) + 5)^5 + F (6)$$

$$65549 := \left(- (F (9)) + \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - \left((5^5) \right) \right) \right) \times F (F (6)) \right) \right)$$

$$65589 := \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \times (5 + 5) \right) - F (F (6)) \right)$$

$$65596 := \left(- (F (6)) - \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) - \left((5^5) \right) \right) \times F (F (6)) \right) \right)$$

$$65597 := \left(- (7) - \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) - \left((5^5) \right) \right) \times F (F (6)) \right) \right)$$

$$65598 := \left(\left(F (F (8)) - \left(\sqrt{9} + (5 + 5) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65624 := - \left(\left(F (\sqrt{4}) - \left(\left(- ((F (2) - (6)))^5 \right) \times F (F (6)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$65634 := \left(\left(\left(- (\sqrt{4}) + F (F ((F (3) + (6)))) \right) - (5) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65635 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- (F (3)) - \left(F (F (6)) \times \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$65636 := \left(\left(F (F (F (6))) \times \sqrt{36} \right) - (5 \times F (6)) \right)$$

$$65645 := \left(- (5) \times \left(- (4) - \left(F (F (6)) \times \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right)$$

$$65647 := \left(7 + \left(\left(\left(- (F (\sqrt{4})) + F (F (F (6))) \right) - (5) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$65648 := \left(\left(\left(F (F (8)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 6 \right) - (5 \times F (6)) \right)$$

$$65649 := \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(\left(- (4) + F (F (F (6))) \right) - (5) + F (F (F (6))) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65651 &:= \left(((1 + 5) \times F(F(F(6)))) - \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) \\
 65656 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \sqrt{-5 + F(F(6))} \right) \times 5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 65659 &:= \left(F(9) + \left((5 \times F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \\
 65661 &:= \sqrt{16^{F(6)}} + \sqrt{5^6} \\
 65663 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{36} \times F(F(F(6))) \right) - (5 + F(6)) \right) \\
 65664 &:= \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(((F(6) + F(6)) + (5))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 65665 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- (F(6)) - \left(F(F(6)) \times \sqrt{5^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 65669 &:= \left(\left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 6 \right) + (5 + 6) \right) \\
 65672 &:= \left(\left(-((F(2) - (7))) \times F(F(F(6)))) - \sqrt{-5 + F(F(6))} \right) \right) \\
 65684 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 6 \right) + F((-5) + F(6)) \right) \\
 65685 &:= \left((5 + (F(F(8)) \times 6)) + \sqrt{-5 + F(F(6))} \right) \\
 65688 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{8 + 6 - 5}) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 65689 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 6 \right) - ((5 - 6)) \right) \\
 65691 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{1 \times 9} + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 65692 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(F(F(6))) \right) + (-5) + F(F(6)) \right) \\
 65693 &:= \left(F(3) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 65696 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times 6 \right) + (5 + F(F(6))) \right) \\
 65697 &:= \left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 65698 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \right) + (5 \times F(6)) \right) \\
 65699 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - 9 \right) + \left((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) \times 6 \right) \right) \\
 65736 &:= F(6) \times \left(F(3)^{F(7)} + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) \\
 65739 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((F(3) \times F(F((F(7) - (5)))) + (F(F(6)))) \right) \right) \\
 65746 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + (\sqrt{4} \times 7) \right) \times 5 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$65754 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left((F(7) - (5)) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65764 := \left(\left(\left(4^{F(6)} \right) + F \left(F(7) \right) \right) - \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}} \right)$$

$$65796 := \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + \left(\sqrt{9+7} \times 5 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65844 := \left(F(4) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F \left(F(8) \right) \right) + 56 \right) \right)$$

$$65856 := \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} + 5} \right) \times 6$$

$$65879 := \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(F \left(F(7) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) - (5) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$65897 := \left(F \left(F(7) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(F(8) \right) \right) - (5) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$65928 := \left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) + \left(2 \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65934 := \left(\left(43 + F \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65946 := \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F(4) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65976 := \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F(7) - \sqrt{9} \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$65987 := \left(F \left(F(7) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) + F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + (5) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$66188 := \left(\left(8^{\sqrt{8+1}} \right) - \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right)$$

$$66194 := \left(\sqrt{4^9} + \left(\left(- (1) - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right)$$

$$66274 := \left(F \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7) \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(2 - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$66399 := \left(\left(9^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(\left(- \left(F \left(F(3) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$66426 := \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + \sqrt{\left(F(2) + 4 \right)^6} \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$66444 := \left(\left(\left(\left(4^4 \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$66456 := \left(\left(\left(65 \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$66468 := \left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$66494 := \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(\left(\left(F(9) \times 4 \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right)$$

$$66568 := \left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) - \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \times \sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) \times F(6) \right)$$

$$66569 := - \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(\left(- \left(\left(6^5 \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66648 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{F(4)^6} \times 6 \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 66663 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{36} \times F(F(F(6))) \right) + F((F(6) + F(6))) \right) \\
 66664 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + F((F(6) + F(6)))) \right) \\
 66669 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 6 \right) + F((F(6) + F(6))) \right) \\
 66684 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(8)) \right) - (-F(6) \times F(F(6))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 66696 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (-F(6) \times F(F(6))) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 66744 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F((4+7)) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 66784 &:= \left(\left(F(-(\sqrt{4} - F(8))) \right) - 7 \right) \times (F(6) + F(6)) \\
 66893 &:= \left(-3 + \left(\left(F(-(\sqrt{9} - F(8))) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times -F(6) \right) \\
 66894 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(F(-(\sqrt{9} - F(8))) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times -F(6) \right) \\
 66896 &:= \left(\left(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(((F(8) - F(6)) + (6))) \right) \\
 66899 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(F(-(\sqrt{9} - F(8))) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times -F(6) \right) \\
 66928 &:= \left(\left(F((F(8) - 2)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times (F(6) + F(6)) \right) \\
 66944 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(\left(-F(4) - F(-\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(6)) \right)) \right) \right) \times -F(6) \right) \\
 66948 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((F(8) - 4)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - 6 \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 66956 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(-5 \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 66966 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + (6^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \times 6 \right) - 6 \right) \\
 66969 &:= \left(-\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(-\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times -6 \right) \right) \\
 66972 &:= \left(\left(\left(-((F(2) - 7))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 67179 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9+7} + 1 \right)^7 \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 67599 &:= \left(\left(F(9) - \left(-\sqrt{9^5} \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 67686 &:= \left(6 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(6) - \sqrt{7^6} \right) \right) \right) \\
 67798 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(8 + \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 67926 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - 2 \right) + F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67938 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F\left(\left(\frac{3}{\sqrt{9}} + F(7)\right)\right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 67968 &:= \left((8 \times 6) \times \left(\left(-(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(7)) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right) \\
 67986 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (F(6)) - F(F(8)) \right) - F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7\right)\right) \right) \times - (6) \right) \\
 68247 &:= \left(\left(- (F(7)) - \left(- (\sqrt{4}) \times F((2 + F(8))) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 68274 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times (7 + F((2 + F(8)))) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 68467 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 8\right)\right) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 68471 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times - (\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right) \\
 68472 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(- (F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times - (\sqrt{4}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 68473 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times - (\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right) \\
 68474 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) \times - (\sqrt{4}) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (6) \right) \right) \\
 68485 &:= F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right) - F(4)^8 + F(F(6)) \\
 68497 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \left(- (9) + \sqrt{4^8} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 68592 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{9^5} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 68672 &:= \left(-F(2) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{(6 + F(F(8))) \times F(6)} \\
 69077 &:= \left(- (F(7)) + \left(70 \times F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 69192 &:= (2 + 91)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times F(6) \\
 69376 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times F(7) \right) - F(3) \right) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} \right) \right) \\
 69484 &:= \left(\left(4^8 \right) - \left(- (4) \times F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6)\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 69489 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left(\left(F((8 \times F(4))) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 69498 &:= \left(F(8 \times \sqrt{9}) / 4 - 9 \right) \times 6 \\
 69546 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) / - (\sqrt{4}) \right) + F\left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right)\right) \right) - 6 \right) \\
 69579 &:= \left(9 \times \left(\left(F((F(7) + 5)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 69624 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + 2^{F(6)} \times F(9) \right) \times F(6) \\
 69629 &:= -\sqrt{9} + 2^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6) \\
 69634 &:= \sqrt{4} + F(3)^{F(6)} \times F(9) \times F(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$69649 := \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(4^6 \right) \right) \times \left(9 + F \left(6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69664 := 4 \times \left(\sqrt{F \left(6 \right)^6} \times F \left(9 \right) + F \left(6 \right) \right)$$

$$69679 := \left(- \left(F \left(9 \right) \right) - \left(7 \times \left(F \left(\left(F \left(6 \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69698 := \left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + \left(F \left(9 \right) \times \left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69759 := \left(- \left(9 \right) + \left(F \left(\left(5 + F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right) \right)$$

$$69767 := \left(\left(\left(\left(7^6 \right) - 7 \right) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69768 := \left(8 + 6 + F \left(7 \right) \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \times 6 \right)$$

$$69789 := \left(\left(F \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(- \left(7 \right) + F \left(9 \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69839 := \left(\left(9 \times \left(- \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69849 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(4 \right) - F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} \right)$$

$$69863 := \left(F \left(\left(- \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$69869 := \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \right)$$

$$69878 := \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \times 7 \right) - F \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69879 := -9 + \left(F \left(7 \right) \times F \left(8 \right) \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F(6)}$$

$$69881 := - \left(\left(F \left(\left(1 + F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times - \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69888 := \left(-8 + F \left(8 \right) \right) \times F \left(8 \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F(6)}$$

$$69896 := \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^8} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(F \left(6 \right) \right)$$

$$69938 := \left(\left(\left(\left(F \left(8 \right) + F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) / F \left(6 \right) \right)$$

$$69959 := \left(\left(\left(\left(9^5 \right) - F \left(9 \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69966 := \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$$

$$69971 := -1 + \left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \times F \left(9 \right) \right) \times 6$$

$$69972 := \left(F \left(2 \right) \times 7 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F \left(9 \right) \times 6$$

$$69973 := \left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) - \left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \right) \times - \left(6 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$69974 := \sqrt{4} + 7^{\sqrt{9}} \times F \left(9 \right) \times 6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69976 &:= 6^7 / F(\sqrt{9}) / F(\sqrt{9}) - F(6) \\
 69992 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(2) - (\sqrt{9^9}) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 69993 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(3) - \left((\sqrt{9^9}) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 69994 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left((\sqrt{9^9}) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 69995 &:= \left(F(F((5 + \sqrt{9}))) - \left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 69996 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - \left(- (9) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 69997 &:= F(7) + 9^{\sqrt{9}} \times 96 \\
 69998 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(9 \times \left(\sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 70844 &:= \left(4 \times F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F((8 + (0 \times 7))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 71149 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(\sqrt{9 \times 4}))) \right) / -((1 + 1)) \right) \times - (F(7)) \\
 71764 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times (1 + F(7)) \right) \\
 71997 &:= \left(\left(\left(7^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - F(9) \right) \times F(F((1 \times 7))) \right) \\
 72695 &:= \left(F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - \left((F(6) + 2) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 73395 &:= \left(\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(F((3 + 3))) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 73644 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \times \left(F(F(6)) - (3^7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 73645 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{5^4}) + (- (6) \times (- (3) + F(F(7)))) \right) \\
 73674 &:= \left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} - 6 \right) \times (F(3) + 7) \\
 73719 &:= 9 \times \left(-1 + \sqrt{(7 - 3)^{F(7)}} \right) \\
 73728 &:= (8 + F(2)) \times \sqrt{(7 - 3)^{F(7)}} \\
 73729 &:= 9 \times 2^{F(7)} + F(\sqrt{-3 + 7}) \\
 73749 &:= \sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \times 3 + 7 \right) \\
 73868 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times 6) + \left(\sqrt{8 / F(3)}^{F(7)} \right) \right) \\
 73869 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + \left((6 \times F(F(8))) + \left(F(3)^{F(7)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 73899 &:= 9 \times \left(-F(\sqrt{9}) + F(8) + F(3)^{F(7)} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 73968 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (F(3) + F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 73969 &:= (F(9) \times F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(3) - F(7) \\
 73976 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F\left(7 \times F(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) - F(F(3)) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 73977 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) + \left(F(7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)^{F(3)} \right) - (7) \right) \\
 73982 &:= -2 + (8 \times F(9))^{\sqrt{-3+7}} \\
 73983 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(3)) - \left((8 \times F(9))^{\sqrt{-3+7}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 73989 &:= (F(9) \times 8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(3) + 7 \\
 73996 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(6) \times F(9) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(F(3)) \right) + (F(7)) \right) \\
 73998 &:= (8 \times F(9))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(3) \times 7 \\
 74096 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times \left(-(90) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) / - (F(7)) \right) \\
 74394 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(F(9) \times \left(F(F(3)) + \left(F(4)^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74426 &:= \left(F\left((F(6) + F(2)) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(F(4)^7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 74448 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + F(4) \right) \times (4 + 7) \\
 74487 &:= 7 \times \left(\left(F(8) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)^{F(4)} - 7 \right) \\
 74494 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(9) \times \left(4 + F(4)^7 \right) \\
 74536 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times F\left((F(3) + (5)) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + (7) \right) \\
 74557 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - \left(F((5 \times 5)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 74559 &:= \left(F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times \left(F((5 \times 5)) + \left(-(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74564 &:= \left(F\left((4 + F(F(6))) \right) - \left(-(5) - \left(-(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74567 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(6) - F(\sqrt{5^4}) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 74572 &:= \left(\left((-2) \times F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{5^4}) \right) + (F(7)) \right) \\
 74644 &:= \left((-4) + F\left((4 + F(F(6))) \right) \right) - \left(F\left((\sqrt{4} \times 7) \right) \right) \\
 74646 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + (F(F(6))) \right) \times (4 + 7) \\
 74649 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F\left((4 + F(F(6))) \right) \right) - \left(F\left((\sqrt{4} \times 7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74656 &:= \left(\left(F(6) + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) \right) - \left(F\left((\sqrt{4} \times 7) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74676 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) \times (\sqrt{4} \times 7) \right) \\
 74695 &:= \left(F \left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - (6 \times F((F(4) + (7)))) \right) \\
 74698 &:= \left(\left((F(8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \times F(6) \right) + F \left((\sqrt{4} + F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 74736 &:= \left(\left((F(6)^3) + (7) \right) \times F \left(- \left((F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(7))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 74745 &:= \left((F(\sqrt{5^4}) - F(F(7))) - 47 \right) \\
 74761 &:= \left(- (1) + \left((F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 74762 &:= \left((F((2+6)) \times F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 74763 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left((F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 74764 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((F(F(6)) \times F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 74769 &:= \left(- \left((F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)}) \right) + F \left((F(7) - F(\sqrt{4})) + (F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 74784 &:= \left((F((4 + F(8))) - F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) - (7) \right) \\
 74786 &:= \left((- (6) + F \left((- (8) + F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) - F(F(7)) \\
 74785 &:= F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 74788 &:= \left(F(F(8)) - \left((- (F(8) \times F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 74789 &:= \left((- (\sqrt{9}) + F \left((- (8) + F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) - F(F(7)) \\
 74793 &:= \left((F((F(3) + 9)) + F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(F(7)) \\
 74794 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} + F(((F(9) - F(7)) + (4)))) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 74796 &:= \left(F \left(\left((6 \times \sqrt{9}) + (7) \right) \right) + 4 \right) - F(F(7)) \\
 74798 &:= - \left((F(F(8)) + \left((9 - F(7 \times \sqrt{4})) \right) \times F(F(7))) \right) \\
 74799 &:= \left((F((F(9) - 9)) - F(F(7))) \times F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + (7) \\
 74844 &:= \left(\left(- \left((4^4) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \\
 74864 &:= \left(F((4 + F(F(6)))) - \left((F(8) + \sqrt{4}) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 74867 &:= \left(- (F(7)) \times \left((F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times - (F(7)) \right) \\
 74874 &:= - \left(F \left(- \left((F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(7))) \right) \right) - ((F((F(8) + (4))) - (7))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74884 &:= \left(F((4 + F(8))) - \left(F\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) / 7 \right) \right) \\
 74885 &:= F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right) + \left(-F(8) + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times 7 \\
 74895 &:= \left(F\left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right)\right) - \left(\left(8 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times F(7)\right) \right) \\
 74897 &:= \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{7+9} + F(8)\right)\right) - \sqrt{4^7} \right) \\
 74938 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times F\left(\left(\left(F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}\right) + F(4)\right)\right) \right) / F(7) \right) \\
 74945 &:= -5 \times \left(F(4) - F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times F(7) \\
 74948 &:= \left(F((F(8) + 4)) - \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{4}\right) \times 7\right) \right) \\
 74955 &:= F(5 \times 5) - \left(9 + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) \times 7 \\
 74957 &:= \left(\left(-F(7) + F\left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right)\right)\right) - F((F(4) + (7))) \right) \\
 74964 &:= \left(F((4 + F(F(6)))) - \left(\left(F(9) \times \sqrt{4}\right) - (7)\right) \right) \\
 74965 &:= \left(F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}\right) - \left(F(9) + \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(7)\right)\right) \right) \\
 74977 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - F\left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right) + \sqrt{4}\right) \times - (7) \right) \\
 74978 &:= \left(F\left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{7+9}\right)\right) - 47 \right) \\
 74984 &:= \left(\left(F((4 + F(8))) - F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - (F(4) \times F(7)) \right) \\
 74985 &:= F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right) - 9 \times F(4) - F(7) \\
 74989 &:= - \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (F((9 + 4)))\right) \times 7\right) \right) \right) \\
 74995 &:= \left(F\left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right)\right) - \left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4}\right) + F(7)\right) \right) \\
 74998 &:= \left(\left(\left(-F(8) + F((F(9) - 9))\right) + F\left(\sqrt{4}\right)\right) - (7) \right) \\
 75024 &:= -F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + F\left(2^{05} - 7\right) \\
 75039 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) + \left(\left(F((30 - 5)) + F(7)\right)\right) \right) \\
 75046 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + F\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{05}} - (7)\right)\right) \right) \\
 75169 &:= \left(F\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)\right) + 1\right)\right) + \left(F((5 + 7))\right) \right) \\
 75245 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{5^4}\right) + F(F((2 + 5)))\right) - (F(7)) \right) \\
 75246 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (6) \times \sqrt{4}\right) + F(25)\right) + F(F(7)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75248 &:= \left(\left((-8) - \sqrt{4} \right) + F(25) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75249 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - F(25) \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75254 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (5 - F(25)) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75259 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9-5}) + F(25) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75261 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{16}) + F(25) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75264 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(6) \right) - F(25) \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75266 &:= \left(F(6) + F(\sqrt{625}) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75269 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F(6) \right) + F(25) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75297 &:= \left(\left(F(7) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(25) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 75466 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \right) + F\left(\sqrt{4^5} - (7)\right) \\
 75795 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + (5^7) \\
 75889 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times - (5))) \times 7) \right) \\
 75928 &:= - \left(\left(F((8 - F(2)))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (5^7) \right) \\
 75949 &:= -F(9) \times 4^{\sqrt{9}} + 5^7 \\
 75957 &:= \left(\left(- (F(F(7))) + F\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}\right) \right) \right) + (5 \times F(F(7))) \\
 75964 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - (95) \right) \times 7 \\
 75999 &:= \left(\left(F\left(9 + F(\sqrt{9})\right) \right) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} + (5)\right)\right) \right) \times - (7) \\
 76146 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times F((1 + F(6)))\right) \right) \times 7 \\
 76174 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{7-1}} - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \times - (7) \\
 76245 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{5^4}) + F(2 \times F(6)) \right) + F(F(7)) \\
 76247 &:= \left(- \left(F\left(7 \times \sqrt{4}\right) - 2 \right) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \\
 76249 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^{4^2} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 76259 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + ((- (52) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76298 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{9} \right)^2 \right) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76347 &:= \left(- (F (F (7))) + \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4^3} \right) \right) - 6 \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76364 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(6)}} \right) + F (3) \right) \right) + (F (F (F (6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76369 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F(6)} \right) - 3 \right) \right) + (F (F (F (6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76374 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F (F (7)) \right) \right) + \left((- (F (3)) + F (F (F (6)))) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76379 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F (F (7)) \right) + \left((- (F (F (3))) + F (F (F (6)))) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76384 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times F (F (8)) \right) - F ((3 + 6)) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76389 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left((F (F (8)) \times (F (F (3)) + (6))) - F (F (7)) \right) \right) \\
 76396 &:= \left(\left(\left(F (F (F (6))) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times (F (F (3)) + (6)) \right) - F (F (7)) \right) \\
 76399 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left((- ((F (9) - F (3))) + F (F (F (6)))) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76423 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{(3 + 2)^4} \right) - (- (6) \times F (F (7))) \right) \\
 76424 &:= \left(\left((42 - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right)) \times F (6) \right) \times F (F (7)) \right) \\
 76425 &:= \left(\left(F \left((5^2) \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) - (- (6) \times F (F (7))) \right) \\
 76426 &:= \left(\left(F (F (F (6))) - \left(F (2) + \sqrt{F (4)^6} \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76433 &:= \left(\left(F (F (F ((3 + 3))) - \sqrt{F (4)^6} \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76434 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(- \left((3^{F(4)}) \right) + F (F (F (6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76453 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F ((F (3) + (5))^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) + (F (F (F (6))) \times 7) \right) \right) \\
 76459 &:= \left((F (9) \times - (5)) - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F (F (F (6))) \right) \times - (7) \right) \right) \\
 76461 &:= \left(\left((- (1) + F (F (F (6)))) - \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F (F (6)) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76462 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(2^{F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4}} \right) - F (F (F (6))) \right) / - (7) \right) \right) \\
 76463 &:= \left(F (3) + \left(\left(F (F (F (6))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + F (F (6)) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76464 &:= \left(F (4) + \left(\left(F (F (F (6))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + F (F (6)) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76469 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times F (F (F (6))) \right) + \left(\left((4^{F(6)}) - F (7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76471 &:= \left(- (F ((- (1) + F (7)))) + \left(\left(- \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F (F (F (6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76474 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left((F ((7 \times F (4))) - F (F (6))) \times 7 \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76479 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - F \left(\left(F(7) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76481 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76483 &:= \left(F \left(F(3) \right) + \left(\left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76484 &:= \left(\left(\left(4^8 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(\left(F(6) + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76489 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F(8) \right) \right) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76493 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(\left(\left(- (9) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76494 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(\left(- (9) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76495 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(\left(4^{F(6)} \right) + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76496 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + \left(\left(\left(4^{F(6)} \right) + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76497 &:= \left(- \left(F(7) \right) + \left(\left(- \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^4 \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76499 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(\left(- (9) \times \sqrt{4} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76519 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(- (15) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76529 &:= \left(- \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(\left(- \left(F \left((2 + 5) \right) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76546 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times - (5) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76547 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times - (5) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76549 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times - (5) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76554 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(- \left((5 + 5) \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76557 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(7) \times \sqrt{5 \times 5} \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76564 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F(6) \right) \right) + \left(\left(- (5) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76569 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times - (6) \right) + \left(\left(- (5) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76574 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times - \left(F(7) \right) \right) + \left(\left(- (5) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76579 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F(7) - (5) \right) \right) \right) - 6 \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76583 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{F(3) \times 8} \right) + \left(\left(- (5) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76586 &:= \left(- \left(F(6) \right) + \left(\left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) - \sqrt{-5 + F \left(F(6) \right)} \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76589 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + ((F(F(8)) - 5) \times (-6) + F(7)) \right) \\
 76591 &:= \left((1 + \sqrt{9}) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \right) \\
 76595 &:= \left((5 + \sqrt{9}) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \right) \\
 76596 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - 5 \right) \times (6 \times F(7)) \\
 76597 &:= \left((F(7) - \sqrt{9}) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \right) \\
 76598 &:= \left((8 + \sqrt{9}) + ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \right) \\
 76599 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{9}) + ((-F(9-5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \right) \\
 76609 &:= \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 06 \right) \times F(F(F(6))) - F(7) \right) \\
 76614 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + ((1 - F(F(F(6)))) \times (6 - F(7))) \right) \\
 76615 &:= \left((F(\sqrt{5-1}) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (6 - F(7)) \right) \\
 76618 &:= \left((-8 + \sqrt{16}) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76619 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{9}) + ((1+6) \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) \right) \\
 76624 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + ((F(2) + 6) \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) \right) \\
 76634 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + (((F(F(3)) + 6) \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(7)) \right) \\
 76639 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + ((F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7)) \right) \\
 76643 &:= \left((3 + F(F(\sqrt{4} + 6))) \times (-6) + F(7) \right) \\
 76644 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + ((F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-6) + F(7)) \right) \\
 76649 &:= \left(\left(F(F(9) / \sqrt{4}) \right) \times (F(6) \times 6) - 7 \right) \\
 76650 &:= 0 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76651 &:= 1 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76652 &:= 2 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76653 &:= 3 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76654 &:= 4 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76655 &:= 5 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76656 &:= 6 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76657 &:= 7 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76658 &:= 8 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76659 &:= 9 + \left(\sqrt{-5 + F(F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))} \right) \times 7 \\
 76661 &:= \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{16}) \right) + ((- (6) - F(F(F(6)))) \times - (7)) \right) \\
 76664 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (6) \right) \times (6 + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \right) \\
 76668 &:= \left(\sqrt{8 + F(6)} + ((- (6) - F(F(F(6)))) \times - (7)) \right) \\
 76679 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + ((F((F(7) + F(6))) + F(6)) \times 7) \right) \\
 76681 &:= \left(\sqrt{1+8} + ((- (F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times - (7)) \right) \\
 76682 &:= \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} + ((- (F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times - (7)) \right) \\
 76691 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(6) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76693 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(6) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76694 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(6) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76696 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \sqrt{9} \right) + ((- (F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times - (7)) \right) \\
 76698 &:= \left(- (8) + \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 6 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76699 &:= \left(\left(\left(- (9) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times (6 - F(7)) \right) \\
 76714 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + ((F((1 \times 7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76716 &:= \left(\sqrt{F(6) + 1} + ((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76719 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - (((1 + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) \right) \right) \\
 76745 &:= \left(\left(- (5) + \sqrt{4^7} \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76764 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (6) \right) \times (- (F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 76779 &:= \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(7) \right) \right) \right) + ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(7)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76796 &:= \left(- (F(6)) + \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(7) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76797 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + F(7) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \\
 76844 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + \left(\left((4 \times 8) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76847 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{74}} \times F(F(8)) \right) - F(6) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76848 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times F(8) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) - 7 \\
 76849 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9 - \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) - (6) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 76874 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76879 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((7 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(6)) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76902 &:= \left(\left(\left(20 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76927 &:= \left(\left(F((F(7) + 2)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76945 &:= \left(F\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(- (6) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76946 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{64} \times 9 \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76949 &:= \left(F\left(\left(9 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left((F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76956 &:= \left(6 \times \left(- (5) - \left(F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right) \right) \times - (F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76958 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left((5 + \sqrt{9}) \times 6 \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76967 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + \left(\left(\left(- (F(6)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (7) \right) \right) \\
 76972 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(2) + \left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76979 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + \left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76983 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(F\left(\left(8 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times (6 \times F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76984 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + \left(F\left(\left(8 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times (6 \times F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76986 &:= F\left((6 \times 8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \times 6 \times F(7) \\
 76989 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(F\left(\left(8 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times (6 \times F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76993 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((F(F(3)) + 9)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76996 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(6) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(9) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 76997 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(7 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76998 &:= \left(\left(- (F(F(8))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - \left(F \left(- \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - (F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) \times - (F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 76999 &:= \left(F \left(\left(9 + \sqrt{F(9) - 9} \right) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 7) \right) \\
 77189 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + F(F((1+7)))} \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 77445 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{5^4}) + \left((F(4^7)) \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 77484 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77518 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{(-1+5)^7} \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 77679 &:= \left(\left(F \left(- \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(7) \right) \right) \right) + (F(F(F(6))) + 7) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 77798 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) + ((F(7) \times F(7))) \right) \times 7 \\
 77847 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times ((8 \times F(7)) + F(F(7))) \right) \\
 77869 &:= -F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} + (-8 + F(7))^7 \\
 77891 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)^7 \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77892 &:= \sqrt{\left(F(2) + \sqrt{9} + F(8) \right)^7} - F(F(7)) \\
 77893 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)^7 \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77894 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(- \left((\sqrt{9} - 8) \right)^7 \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 77973 &:= \left(F((3 + F(7))) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (77) \right) \right) \\
 77978 &:= -F(8) \times 7 + \left(-F(\sqrt{9}) + 7 \right)^7 \\
 77987 &:= \left(7 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(7)) \right) \times F(7) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78124 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + (-2 - 1 + 8)^7 \\
 78246 &:= \left(\left(F(6) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times \left((- (F(2)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 78254 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left((F(F((5+2))) + F(F(8))) \times - (7) \right) \right) \\
 78288 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{(8+8)^2} \times F(8) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 78289 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + \left((F(8) \times (2 \times 8)) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 78296 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - \left((- (2) \times F(8)) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78359 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(\left(5^{- \left(F \left(F \left(3 \right) - 8 \right) \right) } + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78428 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + \left(2 + \sqrt{4^8} \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 78478 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \times - \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 78487 &:= \left(\left(\left(7 \times F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(8 \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 78499 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9^9} \right) \times - \left(4 - 8 \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 78566 &:= F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) + \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8 \times 7}}} \\
 78594 &:= \sqrt{4} \times \left(F \left(9 \right)^{-5+8} - 7 \right) \\
 78624 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F \left(2 \times 6 \right) \times F \left(8 \right) \times F \left(7 \right) \\
 78647 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) + \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4}^{F(6)} \right) + F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 78685 &:= F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) + 6 \times F \left(8 + 7 \right) \\
 78968 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + \left(F \left(8 + 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79368 &:= \left(\left(8 \times \left(F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(3 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F(7)} \right) \right) \\
 79376 &:= F \left(6 \right) \times F \left(7 \times 3 \right) - F \left(\sqrt{9} \right)^{F(7)} \\
 79399 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(9 \right) - 9 \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(3 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{9^7} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79478 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(7 \right) - F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times F \left(9 \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 79499 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(9 + F \left(9 \right) \right)^{F(4)} \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) - 7 \\
 79646 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + 6 \right) \right) + \left(- \left(F \left(9 \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79664 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) + 6 \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79669 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(F \left(6 \right) \times \left(F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(9 + 7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79677 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{7^6} \right) - 9 \right) - F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 79678 &:= \left(- \left(8 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{7^6} - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79685 &:= F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) + \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(7 \right) \right) \\
 79688 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(8 \right) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(8 \right) \times F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 79696 &:= \left(F \left(6 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F \left(F \left(F \left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(9 + 7 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 79775 &:= \left(- (F ((5 + 7))) + \left((7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times F (F (7)) \right) \right) \\
 79855 &:= \left(F ((5 \times 5)) + \left(- (F (8)) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - F (F (7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79866 &:= \left((F (6) + F (F (6))) \times \left(F (F (8)) - \left(F (\sqrt{9})^{F(7)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 79872 &:= (-F (2) + F (7)) \times 8^{\sqrt{9}} \times F (7) \\
 79876 &:= \left(- (F (6)) - \left(- (7) \times \left(F (F (8)) + \left(F (\sqrt{9}) \times F (F (7)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79877 &:= \left(- (7) - \left(- (7) \times \left(F (F (8)) + \left(F (\sqrt{9}) \times F (F (7)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79884 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F (\sqrt{4}) - 8 \right) \times \left(F (F (8)) + \left(F (\sqrt{9}) \times F (F (7)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79898 &:= \left(- (F (8)) + \left(\left(- \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) - 8 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F (F (7)) \right) \right) \\
 79919 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 1 \right) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times F (F (7)) \right) \\
 80498 &:= \left(\left(F (F (8)) / F (\sqrt{9}) \right) + F ((4 + F (08))) \right) \\
 81179 &:= - \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) + \left(- \left((F (7) - 1) \times F ((- (1) + F (8))) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 81796 &:= \left(\left(\left(F (F (6)) + F (F (\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times F (7) \right)^{F(\sqrt{1+8})} \\
 81976 &:= \left(F (6) \times \left(\left(F (F (7)) \times - (\sqrt{9}) \right) + F (F ((1 \times 8))) \right) \right) \\
 82568 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F (F (F (6))) - \left(5^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 82944 &:= 4 \times (F (4) + 9)^{\sqrt{2 \times 8}} \\
 82946 &:= \left(\left(F (F (F (F (6) - F (\sqrt{4})))) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + (F ((2 + F (8)))) \right) \\
 82947 &:= \left(\left(\left(F (F (7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) + F (F (\sqrt{9})) \right) + (F ((2 + F (8)))) \right) \\
 83499 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F (9) / F (\sqrt{9}) \right)^4 \right) - F (F (3)) \right) - (F (8)) \right) \\
 83521 &:= (12 + 5)^{\sqrt{F(3) \times 8}} \\
 83598 &:= \left(\left(F (F (8)) / F (\sqrt{9}) \right) + \left(5^{- \left((F (F (3)) - 8) \right)} \right) \right) \\
 83619 &:= - \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) - \left(- (1) + F (F (6)) \right) \times F \left(- \left((F (3) - F (8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 83696 &:= \left(- (F (6)) \times \left(\left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) + F (F (6)) \right) \right)^{F(3)} - F (F (8)) \right) \right) \\
 83764 &:= \left(\left(F \left(- \left(\left(F (\sqrt{4}) - F (F (6)) \right) \right) \right) \times F (7) \right) - F \left(- \left((F (3) - F (8)) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84368 &:= \left(- (8) \times \left(\left((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 84374 &:= - \left(\left(F((4 + F(7))) + \left(- (3) \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84387 &:= \left(\left((F(7) \times F(8)) - F(3) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 84617 &:= \left(F(7) \times \left(F((-1) + F(F(6))) - \sqrt{4^8} \right) \right) \\
 84664 &:= \left(\left(F(4) \times \left(F(6) \times F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 84674 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) \times (6 + F(4)) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 84697 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) - \left(F(9) \times F(6) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 84777 &:= \left(- (7) \times \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times \left(- (7) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 84872 &:= (-F(2) + F(7) \times 8)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \\
 84882 &:= (-2 + 88) \times F(\sqrt{4} \times 8) \\
 84968 &:= \left(86 \times \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + \left(F(\sqrt{4} \times 8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84984 &:= \left(\left(- (4) \times F(F(8)) \right) \times - (\sqrt{9}) - F((F(4) \times 8)) \right) \\
 84985 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(F(8) \times F(9) - F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84986 &:= \left(\left(F(6) \times F(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) \right) \\
 85184 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times (F(8) + 1) \right)^{-5+8} \\
 85346 &:= F \left(F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3 - \sqrt{5^8} \\
 85397 &:= F(7) \times \left(\sqrt{9^{3+5}} + 8 \right) \\
 85664 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (6) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F(F(F(6))) - (5) \right) \right) \times - (8) \right) \\
 85683 &:= 3 \times (F(8) - F(6))^{\sqrt{-5+F(8)}} \\
 85738 &:= F(F(8)) \times F(F(3)) - F(F(7)) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \\
 85827 &:= -F(F(7) - F(2)) + F(F(8)) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \\
 85867 &:= -F(7) \times F(6) + F(F(8)) + F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) \\
 85869 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times (F(6) + F(8)) \right) \times F((-5) + F(8)) \right) \\
 85893 &:= \left(3 \times \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(8) \right) \right) - (5 + F(8)) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$85916 := F(F(F(6))) - F(1+9) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85936 := F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3)) - F(9) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85937 := F(7 \times 3) - F(9) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85938 := F(F(8)) + F(F(3)) - F(9) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85946 := (F(F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{9} - \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85956 := F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times \sqrt{9} + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85958 := F(F(8)) - F(5 + F(\sqrt{9})) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85961 := (-1 + F(F(F(6)))) - 9 + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85962 := F(F(2+6)) - 9 + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85963 := 3 \times F(6 \times \sqrt{9} + 5) - 8$$

$$85964 := (F((4 + F(F(6)))) - (((F(\sqrt{9}) + 5) - F(F(8))))))$$

$$85965 := -5 + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85967 := -F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + 9 + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85969 := -(((F(\sqrt{9}) - F(((F(6) - \sqrt{9}) \times 5)))) - F(F(8))))$$

$$85971 := 1 \times F(7 \times \sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85972 := F(2) + F(7 \times \sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85973 := F(3) + F(7 \times \sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85974 := F(4) + F(7 \times \sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}})$$

$$85976 := (F((F(F(6)) + \sqrt{7+9})) - (-5 - F(F(8))))$$

$$85977 := (F(F(7)) \times (((7^{\sqrt{9}}) + 5) + F(8)))$$

$$85979 := (F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(F(7)) \times (F((9+5) - 8)))$$

$$85980 := 0 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85981 := 1 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85982 := 2 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85983 := 3 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85984 := 4 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85985 := 5 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85986 := 6 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85987 := 7 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85988 := 8 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85989 := 9 + F(F(8)) + 9 + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$85996 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(9) - 9) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}$$

$$85998 := F(F(8)) + 9 \times \sqrt{9} + F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}}\right)$$

$$86348 := \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 3 \right) + \left(F((6+8)) \right) \right)$$

$$86416 := \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(- (1) \times F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$86448 := \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) + 4 \right) - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right)$$

$$86456 := \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(5 - F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right) \right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$86544 := \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 4^5 \right) \right) - \left(- (F(6)) \times F(F(8)) \right) \right)$$

$$86564 := \left(- (4) - \left(F(6) \times \left(\sqrt{5^6} - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$86568 := \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times F(6) \right) + \left(\sqrt{5^6} \times - (8) \right) \right)$$

$$86569 := \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(F(6) \times \left(\sqrt{5^6} - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$86584 := \left(\left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) + \left(\sqrt{5^6} \right) \right) \times - (8) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86794 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - ((-97) + F(F(F(6)))) \times -(8) \right) \\
 86839 &:= \left(-\left(9^3\right) + \left(F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{F(6) \times 8}\right) \right) \\
 86856 &:= F(6) \times \left(5 + \sqrt{8^6}\right) \times F(8) \\
 86869 &:= \left(\left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \times F\left(-\left(F(6) - F(8)\right)\right) \right) - \left(-F(6) \times F(F(8))\right) \right) \\
 86896 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times -\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 86936 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F(3) - \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{F(6)}}} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 86945 &:= \left(\left(-\left(5^4\right) + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) - \left(-F(6) \times F(F(8))\right) \right) \\
 86954 &:= \left(\left(-4 - F\left(5 \times \sqrt{9}\right) \right) - \left(-F(6) \times F(F(8))\right) \right) \\
 86958 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) \times -5 \right) \times F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(6 + F(8)) \right) \\
 86959 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) - \left(F\left(5 \times \sqrt{9}\right) + \left(-F(6) \times F(F(8))\right) \right) \right) \\
 86974 &:= \left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7)\right) \right) - \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times -(8) \right) \right) \\
 86976 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(7 - \sqrt{\sqrt{9^{F(6)}}} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 86984 &:= \left(\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - F(F(8)) \right) - \left(-9 \times F(6)\right) \right) \times -(8) \right) \\
 86989 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) - \left(F(F(8)) + \left(-9 \times F(6)\right) \right) \times -(8) \right) \\
 86992 &:= \left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \times \left(\left(-9 \times F(6)\right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 87263 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{3^6}\right) / 2 \right) - F(F(7) + 8) \right) \\
 87294 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + \left(\left(-F(9) + F(F(F(2) + 7))\right) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 87299 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left(-F(9) + F(F(F(2) + 7))\right) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 87374 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(-F(3) + F(F(7) + F(8))\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87384 &:= \left(-\sqrt{4} - F(8) + F(3 \times 7) \right) \times 8 \\
 87428 &:= \left(F(F(8)) \times 2 + \left(\left(\sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 87454 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-5 + \left(4 \times \left(-F(7) + F(F(8))\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87462 &:= \left(-2 - \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \times F(7) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87463 &:= -\left(\left(F(F(3)) + \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4}\right) \times F(7) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87466 &:= \left(- (6) + \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(7)) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87469 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{F(6)} \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F(7) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \\
 87479 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(7)) \right) \right) \right) + \left(F((F(4) \times 7)) \times - (8)) \right) \right) \\
 87488 &:= \left((8 \times F(F(8))) - \left(\sqrt{4} + 78 \right) \right) \\
 87494 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left((-9) + F((F(4) \times 7)) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 87495 &:= 5 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + F(4)^7 \times 8 \right) \\
 87496 &:= \left(\left(- (6) - \sqrt{9} \right) + F((F(4) \times 7)) \right) \times 8 \\
 87498 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - 9 \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times 7 \right) + F(F(8)) \\
 87499 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left((-9) + F((F(4) \times 7)) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 87514 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(F((1+5)) \times (-7) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 87528 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{25} \right) \times - \left(F(7) - F(8) \right) \right) \\
 87544 &:= \left(-F(4) + F(\sqrt{4+5} \times 7) \right) \times 8 \\
 87546 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left((-5) + F(7) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 87548 &:= \left(\left(- (F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left((-5) + F(7) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) \\
 87549 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(F((-5) + F(7))) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 87574 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (7) \right) - \left((-5) + F(7) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 87579 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(7)) \right) - \left((-5) + F(7) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 87584 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + F((8-5) \times 7) \right) \times 8 \\
 87591 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F(F((-5) + F(7))) \right) \times - (8) \right) \right) \\
 87592 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(2) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F((-5) + F(7))) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 87593 &:= \left(F(F(3)) + \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F(F((-5) + F(7))) \right) \times - (8) \right) \right) \\
 87594 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F(F((-5) + F(7))) \right) \times - (8) \right) \right) \\
 87599 &:= \left(\left(F(9) - \sqrt{9} \right) + \left((-5) + F(7) \right) \times F(F(8)) \right) \\
 87614 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left((-1) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + 7 \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 87619 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((-1) + F(F(F(6))) \right) + 7 \right) \times 8 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87627 &:= \left(\sqrt{7+2} - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8))) \right) \\
 87629 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} + 2) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8))) \right) \\
 87634 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + (((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7) \times 8) \right) \\
 87646 &:= \left((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4})) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8))) \right) \\
 87649 &:= \left(\sqrt{9^4} - (-F(6) \times F((F(7) + 8))) \right) \\
 87654 &:= \left(((\sqrt{4} + 5) - F((6 + F(7)))) \times -F(8) \right) \\
 87659 &:= \left(((F(F(\sqrt{9}) + 5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 87664 &:= \left(((\sqrt{4} \times 6) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times 8 \right) \\
 87668 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{8 + F(6)} + (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8))) \right) \right) \\
 87669 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{9}) - (F(6) \times (-((6 + 7)) - F(F(8)))) \right) \\
 87674 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - ((F(7) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times -8) \right) \\
 87679 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9} + 7) - (F(6) \times (-7) - F(F(8))) \right) \\
 87693 &:= \left(F((F(3))^{\sqrt{9}}) - (F(6) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(8))) \right) \\
 87694 &:= \left((((\sqrt{4} \times 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + F(F(8)) \right) \\
 87696 &:= \left((-((F(6) - \sqrt{9})) + F((6 + F(7)))) \times F(8) \right) \\
 87697 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + ((F(\sqrt{9}) + 6) \times (-F(7) + F(F(8)))) \right) \\
 87699 &:= \left(-((F(9) \times \sqrt{9})) - (F((6 + F(7))) \times -F(8)) \right) \\
 87759 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9} \times 5) - F(7) \right) \times 7 \times F(8) \\
 87784 &:= \left(((F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(8))) + (F(7) + F(7))) \times 8 \right) \\
 87798 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) - \sqrt{9}) + F(F(7))) - (-7 \times F(F(8))) \right) \\
 87799 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(((F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(7)) - 7)) \times -F(8)) \right) \\
 87839 &:= \left(-F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(F(-((F(F(3)) - 8))) \times -F((-7 + F(8)))) \right) \\
 87894 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{4}) - (((F(9) + F(F(8))) + 7) \times -8) \right) \\
 87899 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - (((F(9) + F(F(8))) + 7) \times -8) \right) \\
 87924 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + F(2 \times 9) \right) \times (F(7) + F(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87948 &:= \left(F \left(8 + \sqrt{4} + 9 \right) + 7 \right) \times F(8) \\
 87953 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(3) \times 5 \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times F(7) + 8 \right) \\
 87963 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(3) + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F(7) - 8 \right) \\
 87964 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F(7) + F(8) \right) \right) \\
 87968 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - F(7) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 87969 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) + 7 \right) \times F(8) \\
 87984 &:= \left(\left(- F(4) + F(F(8)) \right) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 7 \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \\
 88064 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 60 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 88179 &:= \left(F \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + F(7) \right) \right) - \left(-1 + (-8) \times F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 88185 &:= \sqrt{5^8} + (-1 + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\
 88279 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F \left(F(7) - 2 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times -8 \right) \right) \\
 88284 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right) + F \left(-2 + F(8) \right) \right) \times F(8) \right) \\
 88296 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(F(6) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + 2 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 8 \\
 88347 &:= \left(- \left(\left(F(7) \times \sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(- \left(F(3) - F(8) \right) \right) \right) \times -F(8) \right) \\
 88435 &:= \left(-5 \times \left(\left(3 - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) \right) + F(8) \right) \right) \\
 88445 &:= \left(-5 \times \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) \right) + F(8) \right) \right) \\
 88448 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left(8 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 88450 &:= 0 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right) \\
 88451 &:= 1 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right) \\
 88452 &:= 2 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right) \\
 88453 &:= 3 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right) \\
 88454 &:= 4 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right) \\
 88455 &:= 5 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right) \\
 88456 &:= 6 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right) \\
 88457 &:= 7 + 5 \times \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) - F(8) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88458 &:= 8 + 5 \times (F(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8)) - F(8)) \\
 88459 &:= 9 + 5 \times (F(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8)) - F(8)) \\
 88494 &:= ((-((F(\sqrt{4}) - F(9))) + F(-((\sqrt{4} - F(8)))))) \times F(8) \\
 88495 &:= (-5) \times ((-9) - F((F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(8)))) + (F(8))) \\
 88545 &:= (-5) \times (\sqrt{4} - F((F(F(-((5-8)))) + (F(8)))))) \\
 88554 &:= (-F(\sqrt{4})) - (-5) \times F((F(F(-((5-8)))) + (F(8)))) \\
 88568 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (5^{F(\sqrt{8+8})))) \\
 88584 &:= ((F((F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(8)))) \times 5) + (8 + F(8))) \\
 88592 &:= ((\sqrt{2^{9+5}} + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 88699 &:= (((F((9 + \sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8) - (F(8))) \\
 88719 &:= -((F(F(\sqrt{9})) + ((F((-1) + F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times -8)) \\
 88784 &:= (((\sqrt{F(4)^8} - F(F(7))) - F(F(8))) \times -8) \\
 88848 &:= (((F(8) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 8) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \\
 88896 &:= (-F(6)) \times ((F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(8))) + (-8) \times F(8)) \\
 88966 &:= ((6 \times F(F((F(F(6))/\sqrt{9})))) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 88972 &:= (-F((2 \times 7))) \times (-\sqrt{9} - F((-8) + F(8))) \\
 88992 &:= (((F((2+9)) \times F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 89275 &:= (-5) \times (-F((F(7) - F(2))) - F((F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F(8)))))) \\
 89296 &:= (F(6) \times (((\sqrt{9} \times 2)^{\sqrt{9}}) + F(F(8)))) \\
 89394 &:= F(4) \times (F(9) - 3)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(8) \\
 89448 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (\sqrt{4} + F((4+9)))) \times 8) \\
 89456 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F((5 + \sqrt{4})))) + \sqrt{9}) \times 8) \\
 89536 &:= (F(6) \times (((3^5) + \sqrt{9}) + F(F(8)))) \\
 89542 &:= (F((2^4)) + (5 \times F((F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F(8))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89586 &:= \left(- (F (F (6))) \times \left(- (85) - F \left(- \left(\left(F (\sqrt{9}) - (F (8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89616 &:= \left(F (6) \times \left(\left(16^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F (F (8)) \right) \right) \\
 89647 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F (F (7)) - \sqrt{4} \right) + F (F (F (6))) \right) \times 9 \right) - F (F (8)) \right) \\
 89648 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(4 + F (F (F (6))) \right) + \left(F (\sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 89649 &:= \left(- (9) \times \left(\left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F (6) \right) \right) - F (\sqrt{9}) \right) - F (F (8)) \right) \right) \\
 89656 &:= \left(F (6) \times \left(\left(5 + F (F (F (6))) \right) + \left(F (\sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 89715 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(1 - F (F (7)) \right) - F \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) + (F (8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89725 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (F (2)) - F (F (7)) \right) - F \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) + (F (8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89735 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(\left(- (3) - F (F (7)) \right) - F \left(\left(F (F (\sqrt{9})) + (F (8)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89747 &:= F (7 \times \sqrt{4}) \times 7 \times F (9) + F (8) \\
 89775 &:= \left(\left(5 + \left(7 \times F \left(\left(F (7) + F (\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F (8) \right) \\
 89786 &:= \left(F (6) \times F (F (8)) \right) + \left(\left(F (7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F (8) \right) \\
 89835 &:= \left(5 \times \left(F \left(\left(F (F (3)) + (F (8)) \right) \right) + \left(F (\sqrt{9})^8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 89872 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(\left(F (F (7)) - (F (8)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 91136 &:= F (6)^3 \times F (11) \times F (\sqrt{9}) \\
 91916 &:= \left((F (F (6)) + 1) \times - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F (19) \right) \right) \right) \\
 91938 &:= \left(\left(- (F (8)) - F (F (3)) \right) \times \left(F (\sqrt{9}) - (F (19)) \right) \right) \\
 91979 &:= -\sqrt{9} + (F (7) + 9) \times F (19) \\
 91981 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(\left(F (8) + F (F (\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times F (19) \right) \\
 91983 &:= \left(F (F (3)) + \left(\left(F (8) + F (F (\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times F (19) \right) \\
 91984 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(F (8) + F (F (\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times F (19) \right) \\
 92449 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F (9) - (4) \right) \right) + F (\sqrt{4}) \right) / (F (2) \times 9) \right) \\
 92495 &:= 5 \times \left((F (9) \times 4)^2 + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 92568 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F (F (F (6))) + \left(5^{F(2)+\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}92664 &:= (F(4 \times 6) - 6^2) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92694 &:= \left(\left((4 - F(\sqrt{9} \times F(6))) \right) \times - (2) - F(9) \right) \\92696 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(6)) + F(2) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92698 &:= \left(\left(- (F(8)) + F(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)) \right) \right) + 2 \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92699 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{9}) - \left(F(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)) \times - (2) + F(9) \right) \right) \\92732 &:= \left(- (2) + F(((F(3) \times F(7)) - 2)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92733 &:= F(3 + 3 \times 7) \times 2 - \sqrt{9} \\92734 &:= \left(F((F(4) + (3 \times 7))) - F(2) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92736 &:= F(6 \times (-3 + 7)) \times \sqrt{F(2) + \sqrt{9}} \\92737 &:= \left(F(((F(7) - F(3)) + F(7))) \times 2 + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\92738 &:= F(8 \times 3) \times F(\sqrt{7+2}) + F(\sqrt{9}) \\92739 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(((F(3) \times F(7)) - 2)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \\92742 &:= \left(F(24) + \sqrt{7+2} \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92744 &:= \left(4 + F(\sqrt{4} \times F(7) - 2) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92746 &:= (F(6 \times 4) + 7 - 2) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92748 &:= \left(F((8 \times F(4))) + (7 - F(2)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92754 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (F((5 + 7) \times 2) + 9) \\92763 &:= \left((F((3 \times F(6))) + F(7)) \times 2 + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\92764 &:= (F(4 \times 6) + F(7)) \times 2 + F(\sqrt{9}) \\92778 &:= \left(F(8) + F(((F(7) + F(7)) - 2)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92796 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) + F(7) \right) \times 2 + F(9) \\92846 &:= (F(6 \times 4) + F(8 + 2)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92864 &:= (F(4 \times 6) + 8^2) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\92969 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(-((2 - 9)))) \\93024 &:= F(-\sqrt{4} + 20) \times (F(3) + F(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 93025 &:= (F(-5 + 20) / F(3))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 93266 &:= (6^6 - 23) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 93294 &:= \sqrt{4} \times ((F(9) + 2)^3 - 9) \\
 93366 &:= (6^6 + 3^3) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 93636 &:= ((6 + 3) \times F(6 + 3))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 93639 &:= (9 \times F(3 + 6))^{F(3)} + \sqrt{9} \\
 93756 &:= (6 \times ((5^{7-F(F(3))}) + F(F(\sqrt{9})))) \\
 93873 &:= (F((F(3) \times 7)) \times (83 \times \sqrt{9})) \\
 94249 &:= (F(9) \times F(4)^2 + F(\sqrt{4}))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 94375 &:= (-5) \times ((F(F(7)) \times -((3^4))) - F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 94466 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(6)) - 4)^4)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 94468 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(F(6)) - 4)^4) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 94647 &:= (7 \times ((\sqrt{4} \times F((F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4})))) - 9)) \\
 94668 &:= ((8 + 6) \times (F((F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4}))) - \sqrt{9})) \\
 94676 &:= (((F(F(6)) - 7) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4})))) - F(9)) \\
 94699 &:= (((\sqrt{9}) + F((F(F(6)) + 4))) - 9) \\
 94702 &:= (F(20) \times 7 - 4) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 94716 &:= (((F((F(F(6)) - 1)) \times 7) + F(4)) \times F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 94718 &:= (((F((F(8) - 1)) \times 7) + 4) \times F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 94752 &:= ((-((2^5)) \times F((F(7) + F(4)))) \times -(\sqrt{9})) \\
 94792 &:= ((-2) + (\sqrt{9} \times F(F(7)))) \times (4 \times F(9)) \\
 94831 &:= F(13) \times (F(8)^{\sqrt{4}} - F(9)) \\
 94864 &:= ((F(4) + (F((-6) + F(8))) / \sqrt{4}))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 94865 &:= (((5 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(8))) - F(\sqrt{4})) / \sqrt{9} \\
 94874 &:= ((\sqrt{4} \times F(7)) \times ((F(F(8)) + F(\sqrt{4})) / \sqrt{9}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 95489 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left(F \left((\sqrt{4} \times 5) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 95568 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left((5+5)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 95779 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left((F(F(7)) + F((F(7) + (5)))) \times - (F(9)) \right) \right) \\
 95889 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left((F(8) \times (5^{\sqrt{9}})) \right) \right) \\
 96163 &:= \left((F(3) + F(F(6))) \times F \left((16 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 96232 &:= \left(23 \times \left(F((-2) + F(F(6))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 96399 &:= \left(\left((-F(\sqrt{9})) - F(F((9 - F(3)))) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 9 \\
 96426 &:= \left(\left((F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) - F(\sqrt{4})) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (9) \right) \\
 96435 &:= \left(\left((F(F((5 + F(3)))) - \sqrt{4}) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times - (9) \right) \\
 96466 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{F(6)^6} \times - (4)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 9) \right) \right) \\
 96478 &:= \left(\left(F((F(8) - (7))) \times (\sqrt{4}^{F(6)}) \right) - F(9) \right) \\
 96498 &:= \left((-((F(F(8)) + 9)) + F(F((F(\sqrt{4}) + (6)))) \right) \times - (9) \\
 96568 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - (\sqrt{5^6} \times - (9)) \right) \right) \\
 96579 &:= \left(((-9) + F(F(7))) - (5) \right) \times \left(F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 96646 &:= \left((F(F(6)) + F((- (\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)))) \right) \times \left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 96684 &:= \left(((- (F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + F((- (6) + F(F(6)))) \right) \times - (\sqrt{9}) \\
 96687 &:= \left((F(7) + F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{6^6}) \right) \times 9 \\
 96696 &:= \left(\left((F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(F(6))) - F(6) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 96759 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9} \times - (5)) \times F(7) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 9 \\
 96768 &:= \sqrt{8^6} \times (F(7) + F(6)) \times 9 \\
 96829 &:= \left(((9 - F(2)) \times F(F(8))) + (F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \\
 96899 &:= \left((-9) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) - F((F(6) + 9)) \\
 96916 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) - 1) + (\sqrt{9} \times F((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})))) \right) \\
 96918 &:= \left((F(F(8)) + 1) + (\sqrt{9} \times F((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9})))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 96935 &:= \left(F \left(\left(5^{F(3)} \right) \right) - \left(9 + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times - \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 96975 &:= \left(\left(- (57) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \\
 96985 &:= F \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{58}} \right) + \left(F(9) + F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 96993 &:= \left(\left(F \left(- \left(F(3) - 9 \right) \right) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) \times - (9) \\
 97246 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right)^4 \right) + \left(- (2) + F(7) \right) \right) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97248 &:= \left(F(8)^4 + 2 + F(7) \right) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97333 &:= -3 + (33 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 97334 &:= -\sqrt{4} + (33 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 97339 &:= \sqrt{9} + (33 + F(7))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 97344 &:= ((4 + 4) \times 3 \times F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 97364 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) - F(3)^7 \right) \right) \times - (9) \\
 97383 &:= \left(\left(- (3) \times F \left(F(8) \right) \right) + F \left(F(3) \times 7 \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97389 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - F \left(F(8) \right) \right) + F(3)^7 \right) \times - (9) \\
 97416 &:= \left(61 \times F \left(F(4 + F(7)) \right) \right) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97467 &:= \left(F \left(F(7) \right) + \left(\left(F \left(F(6) \right)^4 \right) - F(7) \right) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97569 &:= \left(9 \times \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \times - (5) \right) + F \left(7 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97643 &:= \left(\left(3 + \left(\sqrt{4}^{F(6)} \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(7 \times F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97648 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F(8) \right) - \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(F(6) + \left(F \left(F(7) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 97655 &:= \left(5 - 5^{F(6)} \right) / \left(-7 + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97669 &:= \left(9 \times F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) \right) - \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) / F(7) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97784 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F \left(F(8) + 7 \right) \right) / F(7) - F \left(F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97788 &:= \left(\left(8 \times F \left(F(8) + 7 \right) \right) \right) / F(7) / F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97815 &:= \left(\left(- \left(F \left(5 - 1 \right) \right) \right) \times F \left(F(8) \right) + F \left(F(7) \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97818 &:= \left(- \left(F(8) \right) \times \left(\left(1 - F(8) \right) \times F \left(F(7) \right) + F \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 97833 &:= \left(\left(3 \times \left(- \left(F(3) \right) - F \left(F(8) \right) \right) \right) + F \left(F(7) \right) \right) \times - \left(\sqrt{9} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97836 &:= \left(F(F(6)) - \left(((-3) \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97845 &:= \left(-5 \times \left(((-4) \times F(8)) \times F(F(7)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 97848 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{F(4)^8} \right) + 7 \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 97849 &:= \left(F(9) - \left(((-F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97861 &:= \left((((-1) + F(F(6))) \times F(8)) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 97862 &:= \left((((-F(2)) + F(F(6))) \times F(8)) \times F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 97863 &:= \left((((F(F(3)) - F(F(6))) \times -F(8)) \times F(F(7)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97869 &:= \left((9 \times (6 + F(F(8)))) - (F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 97956 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(5 \times F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - 7 \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 97967 &:= \left(((7 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9) - F(F(7) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 97969 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} + 6) \times F(9) + 7 \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 97973 &:= \left((-3 - F(F(7))) + \left(F((F(9) - 7)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 97974 &:= \left(\left(-\sqrt{4} - F(F(7)) \right) + \left(F((F(9) - 7)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 97976 &:= \left(-F((6 + 7)) + \left(F((F(9) - 7)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 97979 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((F(9) - 7)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98144 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + ((-41) + F(F(8))) \times -9 \right) \right) \\
 98194 &:= (4 + F(9)) \times F(18) + F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 98199 &:= \left(F(9 \times \sqrt{9}) + 1 - F(8) \right) / F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 98209 &:= \left(F(((F(9) + F(02)) - 8)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98213 &:= \left(F(3^{1+2}) + 8 \right) / F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 98233 &:= F(3^3) / 2 + F(8) + \sqrt{9} \\
 98243 &:= \left(\left(F(3^{F(4)}) / \sqrt{\sqrt{2} \times 8} \right) + F(9) \right) \\
 98256 &:= \left(F(6)^5 - 2 \times 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 98258 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{8^5 \times 2} \right) - (F(F(8)) \times -9) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98264 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\sqrt{F(4)^6} \right) / 2 \right) + (F(8) + F(9)) \right) \\
 98272 &:= F(27) / 2 + F(8) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 98274 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(7)) \right) + ((F(2) - F(F(8))) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98279 &:= \left(\left((- (\sqrt{9}) - F(F(7))) + F(2) \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98296 &:= \left(- \left(\left((6^{\sqrt{9}}) + 2 \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \right) \\
 98297 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - ((- (2) - F(F(8))) \times - (9)) \right) \right) \\
 98298 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times 9) - \left(- ((2 - 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \\
 98299 &:= - \left(\left(F \left(F \left((9 - F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) - ((- (2) - F(F(8))) \times - (9)) \right) \right) \\
 98324 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left(\left(F(2^3) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) \right) \right) \\
 98345 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F \left((5 + \sqrt{4}) \right)^{F(3)} \right) + (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \right) \\
 98346 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4^3}) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) \right) \\
 98347 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) - F(3) \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \right) \\
 98349 &:= \left(\left(F \left((9 + F(\sqrt{4})) \right) \right) \times - (3) \right) + (F(F(8)) \times 9) \\
 98358 &:= \left(8^5 - 3 + F(8) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 98366 &:= - \sqrt{(6 + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(3) + F(F(8)) \times 9} \\
 98367 &:= \left((- (7) \times F(F(6))) + \left((- (3) \times F(F(8))) \times - (\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98389 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left(- ((3 - 8)^{\sqrt{9}}) \right) \right) \\
 98397 &:= F(7) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(3 + 8) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 98399 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + ((F((9 - F(3))) - F(F(8))) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98406 &:= \left(\left((- (6) \times \sqrt{04}) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98424 &:= \left(\left(F(F((4 \times 2))) - (\sqrt{4} + 8) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98425 &:= 5 \times \left(2 + F(4)^8 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98427 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F((F(7) - 2)) - \sqrt{4} \right) + (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \right) \\
 98434 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (((- (3) \times F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$98439 := \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(\left(F(3) \times - (4) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98444 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(F(F((4+4))) - 8 \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98445 := 5 \times \left(\sqrt{4} + F(4)^8 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$98447 := \left(- (F(7)) + \left(\left(\left(- (4) - \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98448 := \left(\left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) \times F(4) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - (F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right)$$

$$98451 := \left(\left(\left(- ((1 \times 5)) - \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right)$$

$$98452 := \left(F(2) + \left(\left(\left(- (5) - \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98453 := \left(F(3) + \left(\left(\left(- (5) - \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98454 := \left(F(4) + \left(\left(\left(- (5) - \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98455 := \left(- (5) + \left(\left(\left(- (5) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98456 := \left((F(6) \times - (5)) - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right)$$

$$98457 := \left(- (75) + \left(\left(\left(- (\sqrt{4}) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$98458 := \left(\left(8 \times \left(- (5) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(F(F(8)) \times - (9) \right) \right)$$

$$98460 := 0 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98461 := 1 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98462 := 2 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98463 := 3 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98464 := 4 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98465 := 5 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98466 := 6 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98467 := 7 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98468 := 8 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98469 := 9 + \left(-F(6) + \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9$$

$$98476 := \left((F(6) \times - (7)) + \left(\left(- (\sqrt{4}) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98481 &:= \left((((1 - F(F(8))) \times - (F(4))) - 8) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\ 98482 &:= 2 + \left(8 + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(F(8)) - F(9) \\ 98483 &:= \left(3 + \left(\left((8 + F(\sqrt{4})) \times F(F(8)) \right) - F(9) \right) \right) \\ 98485 &:= \left(- (5) + \left((F(F(8)) \times F(4)) - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\ 98487 &:= \left(\left((- (F(7)) + F(F(8))) + (\sqrt{4} + 8) \right) \times 9 \right) \\ 98488 &:= \left(8 + \left(\left((8 + F(\sqrt{4})) \times F(F(8)) \right) - F(9) \right) \right) \\ 98489 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(8))) - \left((\sqrt{4} \times 8) + 9 \right) \right) \\ 98491 &:= \left((1 + \sqrt{9}) + ((- (F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\ 98492 &:= \left((2 + \sqrt{9}) + ((- (F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\ 98493 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) - 4) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\ 98494 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) - 4) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\ 98495 &:= \left((5 + \sqrt{9}) + ((- (F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\ 98496 &:= (F(6) \times 9)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (F(8) - F(\sqrt{9})) \\ 98497 &:= \left(F(- ((7 - 9))) - \left((\sqrt{4} - F(F(8))) \times 9 \right) \right) \\ 98499 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) - 4) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\ 98504 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (0 - 5)) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \\ 98511 &:= \left(((1 + F((1 + 5))) \times F(F(8))) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\ 98512 &:= \left(((F(2) + F((1 + 5))) \times F(F(8))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 98514 &:= \left((F(4) \times F(F((1^5) \times 8))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\ 98516 &:= \left((- ((6 - 15)) \times F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\ 98517 &:= \left(((F(7) + ((1 - 5))) \times F(F(8))) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\ 98524 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + \left(\left((F(2)^5) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\ 98527 &:= \left(F(7) + \left((- ((2 - 5)) \times F(F(8))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\ 98529 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{9}) + ((F(- ((2 - 5))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\ 98534 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + ((- ((3 - 5)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98538 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) \times -((F(3) - (5)))) + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98541 &:= \left(\sqrt{1 \times 4 + 5} + F(F(8)) \times 9 \right) \\
 98542 &:= \left(F(2) + \left((\sqrt{4+5} + F(F(8))) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98543 &:= \left(F(3) + \left((\sqrt{4+5} + F(F(8))) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98544 &:= \left(F(4) + \left((\sqrt{4+5} + F(F(8))) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98545 &:= \left(-(5) + \left(\left((F(\sqrt{4}) - (5)) - F(F(8)) \right) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98547 &:= \left(\left(-(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98549 &:= \left(\left(-(9) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98554 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times -(5) \right) + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98559 &:= \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9-5}) \times 5) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98561 &:= \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98563 &:= \left(\sqrt{F(3) \times F(6)} + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98568 &:= 8 \times (6 + 5 \times F(8))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 98569 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(6) \right) + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98574 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(7) \right) + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98579 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) \times \left((F(7) \times 5) - (F(F(8)) \times -(9)) \right) \right) \\
 98589 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + \sqrt{\sqrt{5^8} \times 9} \\
 98593 &:= \left(F\left((3 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98594 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(9) \right) + \left((-5 - F(F(8))) \times -(9) \right) \right) \\
 98596 &:= \left(-(F(6)) + \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98597 &:= \left(-(7) + \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98599 &:= \left(\left((F(9) / F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \right) - (F(F(8)) \times -(9)) \right) \\
 98624 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left((2 \times 6) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98639 &:= \left(\sqrt{\left(\sqrt{9} + F(3) \right)^6} - (F(F(8)) \times -(9)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98642 &:= \left(\left(2 \times \sqrt{4^6} \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98646 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 6 \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98647 &:= \left(\left(- (7) \times (\sqrt{4} - F(F(6))) \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98648 &:= - \left(\left(F(8 + \sqrt{4}) \right) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98659 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (((- (5) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98662 &:= \left(\sqrt{2 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 6) + (F(F(8)) \times 9)} \right) \\
 98667 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) - (\sqrt{6^6})) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98669 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9} + (6)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \right) - F(9) \right) \\
 98674 &:= - \left(\left((F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(7))) - ((- (F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \right) \\
 98679 &:= \left(F(- (F(F(\sqrt{9})) - F(7))) + (F(F(6)) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9))) \right) \\
 98684 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} - F(8)) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98695 &:= \left((- (5) - \sqrt{9}) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98696 &:= \left((F(F(6)) / - (\sqrt{9})) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98697 &:= \left((- (7) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98698 &:= \left((- (8) + \sqrt{9}) + ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98699 &:= - \left(\left((F(\sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{9})) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \right) \\
 98743 &:= \left((- (F(3) + \sqrt{4})) + F(F(7)) \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \\
 98744 &:= (- (4) - \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times F(7)) + F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) \\
 98747 &:= \left(F(F(7)) + (F(4) \times F((F(7) + 8))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98748 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) / - (\sqrt{4})) - F(7) \right) \times - \left((F(8) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98752 &:= \left((\sqrt{25} + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98754 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + (5)) + F(F(7)) \right) - (F(F(8)) \times - (9)) \right) \\
 98764 &:= \left(- (\sqrt{4}) + (((F(F(6)) + (7)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right) \\
 98768 &:= \left(8 \times \left(((6 \times F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 98769 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (((F(F(6)) + (7)) + F(F(8))) \times 9) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98774 &:= \left(F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 7 \right) \right) + \left(\left(- F(7) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98776 &:= \left(\left(- F(6) \right) + \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(F(F(7)) - F(8) \right) \right) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 98784 &:= 4 \times 8 \times 7 \times F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 98792 &:= \left(F(F(-((2-9))) \right) \times \left(\left(F(F(7)) - F(8) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98797 &:= \left(F(7) + \left(\left(- (9) + F(F(7)) \right) \times \left(F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) \\
 98819 &:= \left(\left(9 \times \left(F((1+8)) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 98874 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (7) \right) \times - (8) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98889 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(F(8) + F(8) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98894 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(\left(\left(F(9) + 8 \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98937 &:= \left(\left(\left(- F(7) \right) - F \left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \\
 98946 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{4 \times 9} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98973 &:= \left(\left(F(3) + \left(\left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98974 &:= \left(\left(\left(- F(4) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - \left(F(F(8)) \times - (9) \right) \\
 98975 &:= \left(\left(- (5) + \left(F(F(7)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - \left(F(F(8)) \times - (9) \right) \right) \\
 98976 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + \left(\left(\left(7^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98977 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(F(7)) \right) - \left(\left(- (9) \times F(F(8)) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 98979 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(7)) \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + \left(F(F(8)) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98982 &:= \left(\left(\left(F((2+8)) - \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 98989 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 \times F(F(8)) \right) + F(9) \right) + \left(F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 98998 &:= \left(\left(\left(\left(F(8) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + \left(F(F(8)) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 98999 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9})^9 \right) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - F(F(8)) \right) \times - (9) \right) \right) \\
 99243 &:= \left(\left(\left(3^4 \right) + F \left(F \left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99376 &:= \left(\left(F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + (7) \right) \right) - \left(3^9 \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 99498 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) \times 9 \right) + F \left(\left(4^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99576 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + (-7 + (5^{\sqrt{9}})) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99646 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((4^6 \times 9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 99666 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((-6 \times F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99669 &:= \left((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) + \left(F(F(6)) \times F \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 99695 &:= 5 \times \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(6)} + \sqrt{9^9} \right) \\
 99765 &:= \left(\left((-5 + F(F(F(6)))) + F \left(\left(F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99783 &:= \left(\left((-3 + F(F(8))) + F \left(\left(F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99819 &:= \left(9 \times \left((1 + F(F(8))) + F \left((9 + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 99837 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(7) - F(F(3)))) + \left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times 9 \right) \\
 99858 &:= \left((-8 + F((-5 + F(8)))) \times \left(F(9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 99878 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times 7) + \left(F \left((F(8) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \times 9 \right) \right) \\
 99937 &:= 73 \times \left(F(9) + \sqrt{9} \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 99957 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times (5 + F(9))) \times \left(9 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 99964 &:= \left(-4 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left((F(9) - F(F(\sqrt{9})))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 99987 &:= -F(7) + \left(8 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} \\
 99991 &:= (1 + 9)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} - 9 \\
 99995 &:= \left(-5 + \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} \right) \right) \\
 99997 &:= \left(F(7) - \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} - \sqrt{9} \\
 99998 &:= \left(8 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 99999 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \right)^{\sqrt{F(9)-9}} \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

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